

Study on the Influence Mechanism of Employees'
Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour in Temporary Teams: A
Case Study of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd.

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Declaration

I declare that I have composed this thesis myself and that it embodies the results of my own research. Where appropriate, I have acknowledged the nature and extent of work carried out in collaboration with others included in the thesis.

Ling Fu

ABSTRACT

To a certain extent, enterprise competition is essentially a competition in organisational knowledge and capabilities. The acquisition, sharing, and dissemination of knowledge play a crucial role in enhancing enterprise's competitiveness. In the airline industry, cabin crew are the primary staff with whom passengers interact directly. Therefore, knowledge and skills related to aviation safety and service are critically important for cabin crew.

This research project arises from real enterprise operations and aims to address practical workplace problems. Within an organisational context, this study explores the mechanisms and patterns influencing knowledge sharing among temporary cabin crew teams in airlines. The study applies and tests existing research findings on knowledge sharing, and examines the associations between variables typical of temporary teams—such as responsibility, achievement orientation, organisational climate, member familiarity, risk perception, and the quality of pre-flight preparation interaction, and knowledge sharing behaviour. Taking Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd. as a case study, this research starts from real-world issues, systematically analyzes the characteristics and patterns associated with factors of knowledge sharing in cabin crew teams, and proposes targeted improvement strategies and implications.

This study employed a mixed-methods approach (quantitative and qualitative) to comprehensively examine the perceptions, intentions, and influencing factors of employees in temporary teams. In the first stage, qualitative methods were used to conduct interviews with cabin crew members and aviation security officers. Through these interviews, the study refined and summarized participants' perceptions of the intentions, behaviours, and influencing factors of knowledge sharing in temporary

teams were refined and summarized. All participants stated that a sense of responsibility and personal achievement orientation were the main drivers of knowledge sharing, which aligns with most existing research findings. They also believed that risk-related concerns or constraints, such as time pressure and workload, as well as the organisational fairness atmosphere, associate with the depth and frequency of knowledge sharing. However, no consensus was reached on whether member familiarity, technical skill level, and the quality of pre-preparation interaction affected knowledge sharing behaviour.

In the second stage of the research project, a theoretical model of knowledge sharing in temporary teams was empirically tested through model derivation, hypothesis formulation, and validation. Based on personality trait theory, Trait Activation Theory (TAT), Situational Strength Theory (SST), and interview results, hypotheses were proposed regarding structural factors and pre-preparation quality factors that associate with knowledge sharing in temporary teams. Questionnaire-based model analysis empirically demonstrates that Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing (KS). The moderating effect of Member Familiarity (FA) on the relationship between responsibility and knowledge sharing was statistically insignificant. In addition, Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing (KS). Moreover, no significant evidence supported that interaction level, emotional state, or entropy during pre-flight preparation, or team member familiarity, had any moderating effect on Knowledge Sharing (KS). Through interviews and survey data, this study validated the applicability of relevant theories to the case enterprise and the influencing mechanisms and factors were further refined.

Based on the research conducted, this study explored feasible approaches to improve knowledge sharing behaviour in temporary teams. Corresponding strategies were

proposed to improve employees' attitudes, enhance their knowledge sharing ability, and foster a learning-oriented environment. The findings indicate that employees' organisational citizenship behaviour has improved, and satisfactory results have been attained. These improvements have played a positive role in resource management, organisational knowledge development, and the creation of a learning organisation.

Keywords: Knowledge Sharing (KS), Temporary Team, Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Trait Activation Theory (TAT), Situational Strength Theory (SST), Crew Resource Management (CRM), Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

AO	Achievement Orientation
BI	Behavioural Intention
CAAC	Civil Aviation Administration of China
CRM	Crew Resource Management
DDO	Deliberately Developmental Organisation
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organisation
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KM	Knowledge Management
KS	Knowledge Sharing
KSI	Knowledge Sharing Intention
OCB	Organisational Citizenship Behaviour
OF	Organisational Fair Atmosphere
OJT	Organisational Justice Theory
PBC	Perceived Behavioural Control
RP	Risk Perception
RS	Responsibility
SN	Subjective Norms
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SST	Situational Strength Theory
TAT	Trait Activation Theory
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

1.1.1 Civil Aviation Industry and Knowledge Management

It is widely recognised that Chinese air transportation market is already fully competitive. Under the supervision of the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) and its dispatched subordinate agencies, various entities—including state-owned support institutions such as airport companies, aviation fuel suppliers, air traffic control bureaus, aviation equipment firms, and aviation information providers—work together with transport airlines of different sizes and ownership types such as state-owned, private, and joint-stock to compete for market share. The goal is to offer passengers intercity travel services, serve societal needs, and generate profits.

Market competition is essentially a competition of knowledge and capabilities (Grant 1996; Spender 1996). The emergence of Knowledge Management (KM) theory reflects organisations' growing focus on internal capabilities. Knowledge management offers a framework for studying an enterprise's internal strengths. It encompasses knowledge innovation, knowledge retention, and knowledge sharing (Argote 2013). In the enterprise environment, the dominant view emphasizes that organisations must leverage their knowledge base to gain a competitive advantage (Carter and Scarbrough 2001). As early as over two decades ago, organisational learning and knowledge management became central to enterprise operations (Argote et al. 2003).

In airline management, knowledge management and sharing are essential to ensuring both safety and service quality. As recognised by industry regulators (CAAC 2024) and evidenced in practices such as sharing operational safety experiences and data, incorporating best practices into safety standards, integrating specialized knowledge across various aviation domains, and training employees in safety-related knowledge are all key aspects of the industry's reliance on knowledge management.

Currently, many civil aviation enterprises have established knowledge management systems with distinct features. For example, the knowledge management system of China Eastern Airlines includes functions such as knowledge search, knowledge mapping, and Q&A, and incorporates libraries for regulations and standards, method guidance, reference cases, and business documents (Zou, Jianxin. 2012). Some companies have also formed cross-departmental knowledge management teams that regularly discuss business issues and share case studies.

In addition to explicit knowledge, such as operation manuals, cabin crew manuals, aviation security officer manuals, and procedural systems, the tacit knowledge accumulated during operations, including the development of intuition and judgment, is an important factor in employee growth. Relying solely on written regulations and manuals for training cannot effectively improve employees' practical working skills. Judgment, communication and coordination, emergency response, and equipment operation must be developed and refined through long-term practice. The sharing of tacit knowledge can accelerate employees' skill acquisition, enhance team efficiency, and is a vital component of training. For example, Lufthansa Flight Training, a subsidiary of Lufthansa Airlines, emphasizes knowledge dissemination and sharing, aiming to enhance the practical capabilities of cabin crew through periodic, problem-oriented training. The safety operation management learning team of Lufthansa Airlines consists of both horizontal and vertical members, forming a "strong matrix" organisational learning structure (Yuan, Rong. 2023).

Knowledge has long been considered a valuable resource for organisational development and sustained competitive advantage, especially for organisations operating in uncertain environments (Miller and Shamsie 1996). The internal transferability of knowledge is therefore crucial for a company's ability to gain an advantage by accessing scarce internal knowledge (Szulanski 1996). Just as a company's unique capabilities may be difficult for others to imitate, its knowledge management practices may also be hard to replicate internally. From this perspective, knowledge sharing plays an important role in organisational knowledge management. It enables enterprises to develop and utilize their internal knowledge resources, drive innovation, and maintain a competitive edge in a highly competitive market (Grant 1996). In addition, knowledge sharing supports the continuous development of organisational knowledge and helps build a learning organisation.

Employees are both the source of knowledge in an organisation and the carriers of knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing helps employees update their knowledge, supports personal growth and career development, and promotes feedback, enrichment, and correction of knowledge, allowing knowledge to grow exponentially (Quinn et al. 1996). However, surveys have shown that 76% of employees in American companies admit to withholding knowledge from colleagues. Even in a collectivist culture like China, 46% of employees reported hiding knowledge from coworkers (Peng and Pierce 2015).

1.1.2 The Basic Management Situation of Colorful Guizhou Airlines

Colorful Guizhou Airlines is a state-owned enterprise based in Guizhou Province, China. It was established on June 19, 2015. As a mid-sized transportation airline, it carries the important mission of “displaying the colorful Guizhou and connecting with the colorful world.” The company is positioned as a compound aviation enterprise

with a “combination of main and branch lines.” Focusing on the goals of the “three primacies” (safety first, service first, image first) and the “five first-class” (first-class safety, first-class service, first-class performance, first-class management, first-class image), the company aims to build a civil air transport brand with regional competitive advantages. Picture 1 shows the A320neo fleet of Colorful Guizhou Airlines.

Picture 1 The A320neo Fleet of Colorful Guizhou Airlines

Location: Guiyang Longdongbao International Airport, Date: Dec 2025, Photo by: Colorful Guizhou Airlines & Ling Fu

As of December 2025, the company’s registered capital was 1.8 billion RMB yuan (Source: Colorful Guizhou Airlines Annual Report 2025). It has more than 1,800 employees, 85.4% of whom are front-line production technicians. The fleet includes 20 aircraft, with 9 E190s and 11 A320s, and is expanding rapidly. The company operates 50 routes and serves 60 destinations. Its fleet, workforce, and market share continue to grow. The airline has established a route network centered in Guiyang, covering key regional hubs including Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei, the Yangtze River Delta,

the Pearl River Delta, Central China, Northeast China, Northwest China, and other major cities (Colorful Guizhou Airlines 2025).

The company follows a standard hierarchical management system and has a total of nineteen departments.

Figure 1 Organisation Chart

In terms of operational standards, the company follows the regulations, consultation notices, and industry standards issued by the Civil Aviation Administration of China. The manual and procedure management system developed by the company has passed the operational qualification review by the Civil Aviation Administration and has obtained the CCAR-121 certificate for large aircraft public transport carriers. The production and operation of each department are conducted under general guidelines such as the “Operation Manual” and “Operation Specifications” approved by the Civil Aviation Administration. Each profession and department have also developed its own manuals, such as the “Cabin Crew Manual,” “Cabin Crew Training Outline,” and “Aviation Security Officer Manual,” which serve as the basis for employees’ and departments’ daily work. Pre-flight coordination between cabin crew and aviation

security officers, as well as flight execution and task implementation, is carried out in accordance with the above-mentioned manuals and procedures.

Although the company follows a hierarchical management system, temporary teams are often formed in production departments based on specific operational tasks. For example, according to consultation notices issued by the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC), staff at the Aviation Operations Center (AOC) coordinate the scheduling of operational resources within a defined space. The team includes operation control personnel such as dispatchers, meteorologists, performance engineers, and flight information officers; dispatch seat personnel from departments such as flight, cabin crew, security, and fleet; on-duty staff from support departments such as airworthiness maintenance, information technology, and terminal management; and personnel from functional departments such as marketing. These team members are dispatched from different departments and rotate on a fixed schedule. The composition of the temporary team changes daily, and the work is carried out under the leadership of the on-duty manager. As early as 2000 and 2011, the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) issued consultation notices to regulate AOC operations and management (CAAC 2011). Over the years, the temporary team structure at AOC has achieved positive results. Internal communication and coordination within each shift-based team have improved. Processes for handling information—such as decision-making after an aircraft malfunction—are now generally clear. Information sharing and collaboration among team members are effective, and past barriers and information silos between departments have largely disappeared.

Since 2023, the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) has started implementing Cabin Crew Resource Management (CRM), introducing new requirements for team collaboration. Some research findings have also been gradually adopted within the industry. However, current CRM theories do not focus on team

knowledge sharing and instead mainly address communication and collaborative decision-making. Few airlines explicitly mention knowledge sharing in their manuals or systems, and they have not elevated the development of organisational knowledge capabilities to the appropriate level. Meanwhile, aviation security officers and cabin crew members are managed by different departments under the Civil Aviation Administration. The existing regulations provide limited guidance on their coordination, cooperation, and communication. They are not treated as a unified cabin work team but are typically classified by their respective specialties.

For Colorful Guizhou Airlines and the civil aviation industry as a whole, implementing the requirements of Crew Resource Management (CRM) and genuinely encouraging employees to communicate, share, and collaborate remains a challenge. Various forms of tacit knowledge closely related to operations are highly valuable for cabin crew. If a learning atmosphere can be fostered, employees' willingness to share knowledge enhanced, and the habit of knowledge sharing cultivated, this will contribute to improved safety and service quality. It will also be highly beneficial in building the enterprise's unique competitive advantage.

1.1.3 Cabin Crew Responsibilities and Team Management

The following description of cabin crew roles and operational practices is based on industry-wide professional knowledge and common operational understandings in civil aviation, rather than specific academic literature. Transport airlines are production and operation units. The crews involved in production services include flight crews and cabin crews. The former work in the cockpit, while the latter work in the cabin. The cabin team includes both cabin crew members and aviation security officers. As front-line staff who interact directly with passengers, their main responsibilities are as follows. First, they are responsible for maintaining cabin safety. This includes following all safety procedures in the manuals, reminding passengers to

use cabin equipment properly, and handling incidents that disrupt onboard order. In severe cases, they must deal with serious public safety threats such as hijacking or aircraft bombing and maintain order in the cabin. Second, they provide high-quality services to passengers. The team is trained in relevant service skills, responds promptly to passengers' diverse needs, and answers questions about flight operations and company policies. Third, various emergencies can occur onboard, such as seat adjustment disputes, smoking violations, medical emergencies, service complaints, turbulence, or even water landings. In these situations, tacit knowledge—such as experience, judgment, and skill that are not written in manuals—is extremely important. This type of knowledge must be gained through long-term practical experience.

The cabin crew, including flight attendants and aviation security officers, are the employees who interact directly with passengers. Enhancing their knowledge and skills is critical to aviation safety, service quality, and enterprise competitiveness. The OA system of Colorful Guizhou Airlines integrates explicit knowledge such as regulations and company policies, and also includes an online learning platform. For cabin crew, daily theoretical study and regular refresher training are the main channels for acquiring professional knowledge. However, this is not sufficient. How to make full use of flight operation scenarios to improve employees' professional knowledge and work skills is a question worth further exploration.

Due to the implementation of regulatory management in the civil aviation industry, Colorful Guizhou Airlines also emphasizes the concept of “being manual employees.” Organisational knowledge in airlines is often documented in various manuals, including general outlines such as the “Operation Manual” and “Operation Specifications,” as well as professional manuals such as the “Flight Attendant Manual,” “Flight Attendant Training Outline,” “Aviation Security Plan,” “Flight Dispatcher Manual,” and “Flight Operation Manual.” Clearly, this represents explicit

knowledge that has been codified in written form. Another category of important knowledge, such as work experience, skills, and decision-making judgments has not yet been fully documented or is not easily expressed in written language, and therefore cannot be fully reflected in the manual system.

1.1.3.1 Attendant Duties and Qualification Requirements

According to the regulations of the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC), flight attendants must meet recent work experience requirements. They are required to have completed at least two flight segments on the same type of aircraft within the past 12 months before they are allowed to operate that aircraft. If they have not flown within the last 12 months, they must complete two additional flight segments under the supervision of inspectors and pass an assessment.

Although the captain is the highest administrative officer on the flight, the chief flight attendant is undoubtedly the core and leader of the entire cabin team. He or she serves as the central point for information flow and is the decision-maker for cabin affairs, possessing the most extensive experience and skills, including tacit knowledge for handling emergencies. For flight attendants, after obtaining the training qualification certificate, completing on-board flight instruction, and acquiring the “takes on tasks” qualification, further knowledge and experience are often gained through flight operations and the guidance of the chief flight attendant or other senior crew members. The chief flight attendant must unite the team, assign tasks reasonably, ensure cooperation, and lead by example.

1.1.3.2 Aviation Security Officers Qualification Requirements

The captain is fully responsible for flight security, while the aviation security officer is in charge of the specific implementation of security measures, with support from

other crew members. The main responsibilities of the aviation security officer include conducting cockpit and cabin security checks, verifying non-passenger personnel boarding, preventing unlawful intrusions, handling disruptive behaviour, and implementing security measures for special transportation tasks.

Qualification requirements include regular training: at least 20 days (160 hours) of concentrated training within 36 months after obtaining the certificate; daily training: at least 24 hours of theoretical and practical training every 12 months; and additional training: emergency drills, dangerous goods handling, special routes (high-altitude/polar), and other required training.

1.1.3.3 Pre-flight Preparation

According to regulations (CAAC 2024), the pre-flight preparation meeting is a necessary procedure before the official execution of a mission. The pre-flight briefing consists of two stages: a 20-minute preparation session for the cabin crew, which includes flight attendants and the aviation security officer, followed by a 10-minute session for the entire crew, including pilots, flight attendants, and aviation security officers, totaling 30 minutes. Considering the distance from the crew preparation room to the boarding gate, it is only necessary to ensure arrival at the gate one hour before departure. Generally, the offline meeting time for temporary teams does not exceed two hours before the scheduled flight. Although the manual outlines items and checklists for pre-flight collaboration, establishing mutual trust and understanding within such a short time remains a challenge. The cramped and noisy cabin environment can cause discomfort and stress for the crew. In such conditions, giving instructions and performing verifications become more difficult, and feelings of irritability may arise. The key points of the pre-flight briefing (direct preparation stage) include, but are not limited to: alcohol testing and physical condition reporting, obtaining flight information, checking the number of crew members and relevant

documents/manuals, and business preparation, including aircraft knowledge, cabin safety, and special flight requirements. These key items must be communicated in a timely manner.

At this stage, the temporary team meets offline for the first time, becomes acquainted, and gathers the information required for the flight. During this stage, “aircraft type knowledge, cabin safety knowledge, and business requirements for announcements” are usually addressed through a question-and-answer format, with the chief flight attendant asking and the flight attendants responding. Flight attendants and aviation security officers check each item on the inspection sheet, confirming certificates and licenses, personal equipment, flight task assignments, and other related items. There are no mandatory requirements for mutual communication and interaction, but in practice, this process helps team members become familiar with one another and break the ice.

1.1.4 The Difficulty of Knowledge Management for Temporary Teams

In recent decades, considerable research in organisational behaviour and management studies has focused on teams, particularly their effectiveness, dynamic processes, and contextual antecedents (Kozlowski and Bell 2003; Mathieu et al. 2008; Ilgen et al. 2005). However, the cabin crew is a temporary team, with different personnel combinations arranged for each flight mission. As part of the service industry, tacit knowledge such as judgment, skills, and work experience, is critical for frontline employees who face unpredictable customer interactions (Nonaka 1991). In the civil aviation context, cabin crew members frequently encounter situations that are not fully covered by standard operating procedures, making experiential knowledge particularly valuable (Helmreich and Merritt 1998). However, in a service context that involves direct interaction with passengers, contextualized training that embeds learning in realistic work scenarios, has been identified as essential for developing

practical competence in safety-critical industries (Salas et al. 2012; Cannon-Bowers and Bowers 2011, pp.597-650). In aviation, simulation-based and scenario-based training are increasingly emphasised as complements to classroom instruction (FAA 2023; ICAO 2020). For example, a young passenger giving birth on board, two passengers arguing over a seatback, or passengers occupying the aircraft due to delays are all situations where experience must be gained through real practice. Therefore, training provided by institutions alone is not sufficient. Actual in-flight work is also an important stage for communication and discussion among team members.

The temporary team presents new challenges. The composition of the cabin crew for a specific flight is determined only after the airline releases production tasks and scheduling plans a few days before the flight. During the pre-flight preparation stage, team members meet for the first time, establish direct contact, begin task collaboration, and officially form a team. The temporary team is officially disbanded after returning to their accommodation upon completion of the flight. Therefore, the life cycle of such a team is very short, and the quality of task division, mutual cooperation, and coordination is critical. Skipping or neglecting procedures may lead to serious consequences. For example, during critical operations such as opening or closing the cabin door, two crew members must work together to complete the checklist items, rather than relying on memory, to ensure full compliance and avoid accidents such as accidental deployment of the inflatable slide. In emergencies—such as a fire caused by a mobile phone lithium battery—simply memorizing knowledge points is not enough to ensure proper handling according to procedures. The development of such skills relies heavily on practice.

Such temporary teams are vulnerable (Meyerson et al. 1995, pp.166-195; Edmondson 1999), with uncertainties in cohesion, mutual trust, and the quality of collaboration. Moreover, trust cannot replace confirmation, cross-checking, and other procedural steps. It is still necessary to complete the tasks specified in the checklist together.

However, a good level of trust promotes communication, sharing, and collaboration. The sharing and transfer of experience and skills in specific situations are of practical importance.

In the digital age, online work modes have reduced opportunities for cabin crew members to meet in person, thereby lowering the level of mutual familiarity. This is a phenomenon worth attention. Could this effect knowledge exchange among cabin crew during flights? Many companies, including Colorful Guizhou Airlines, have adopted systems such as Office Automation (OA) and remote meetings. As a result, opportunities for cabin crew to interact have declined, and mutual familiarity and understanding have significantly decreased. This has made the cabin crews on each flight more characteristic of temporary teams. The reduction in face-to-face interaction has also led to a sense of isolation among employees, making it even more important for them to exchange industry information, company updates, and other forms of knowledge during flights.

When evaluating and advancing staff, organisations do not merely examine flight hours and theoretical test passes, but competency in general. At the workplace, knowledge sharing is critical in three key viewpoints. First, service experience not only improves expertise on rules and standards, but crew also gets updates on industry developments and company news. With fewer offline opportunities available, this can provide a sense of belonging to the organization and the team. Second, minimising person-to-person misconceptions and advancing communication and handling skills can raise the overall safety and service efficiency of the team. Third, it is important to fully utilize this contextual training opportunity. Its realism and duration exceed the fixed, time-limited retraining that occurs once every three years, helping maintain operational proficiency and emergency response capability.

How the characteristics and circumstances of temporary teams influence members' intention and behaviour in knowledge sharing remains unclear. Understanding the mechanisms of knowledge sharing in temporary teams holds significant theoretical and practical value.

1.2 Research Questions and Objectives

Based on identified research gaps and practical needs, this study aims to clarify the mechanisms influencing knowledge sharing within temporary cabin teams in airlines. It seeks to identify how key individual and team characteristics affect the intention and behaviour related to knowledge sharing, and to propose improvement strategies to promote employee knowledge sharing and enhance enterprise competitiveness.

1.2.1 Research Aims

As mentioned above, the crew members on board are not very familiar with each other, and their opportunities to meet are mainly during the flight. Although there are occasional meetings and training sessions in person offline, those do not belong to the working cabin crew team of a particular flight. This study focuses on the mechanisms underlying knowledge sharing behaviour among temporary cabin crew teams during flight operation process.

This study aims to explore how responsibility, risk perception, team familiarity, and organisational fairness atmosphere contribute to knowledge sharing behaviour within temporary cabin crews on board, and to propose targeted and practical improvement plans.

1.2.2 Research Objectives

Compared to relatively permanent teams, temporary teams have distinct characteristics. In this study, cabin crew members with changing compositions were used as samples, including flight attendants and aviation security officers working in the same cabin. Since the crew composition varies for each flight, members differ in their level of familiarity with each other, their perceptions of the organisation, and their understanding of the costs and risks associated with knowledge sharing. Members' perceptions of organisational fairness and support also shape their organisational citizenship behaviour. Before carrying out flight tasks, airline crews go through a pre-flight preparation stage, during which they complete checklists and get to know one another. Prior to this stage, members usually have no prior contact. This formalized and somewhat ritualistic stage is not typically found in many fixed teams. How this stage effects knowledge sharing during the flight is also worth examining. Therefore, the factors mentioned above should be considered key focuses of this research.

The research objectives of this study are:

- (a) To determine whether the familiarity among temporary team members can predict their knowledge-sharing behaviour. Familiarity is indicated by the frequency of previous collaboration.
- (b) To examine whether the quality of social interaction and openness during the pre-flight preparation stage can predict team members' knowledge-sharing behaviour. This includes communication and interaction beyond the manual-prescribed tasks, covering emotional tone, depth, and density.
- (c) To assess the predictive effect of organisational fairness atmosphere on knowledge-sharing behaviour.
- (d) To assess the predictive effect of risk perception on knowledge-sharing behaviour.

1.2.3 Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following questions:

- (a) How does familiarity affect the knowledge-sharing behaviour of temporary team members?
- (b) How do social interaction and openness during pre-flight preparation impact the knowledge-sharing behaviour of temporary team members?
- (c) How does the organisational fairness atmosphere affect the knowledge-sharing behaviour of temporary team members?
- (d) How does risk perception exert an effect on the knowledge-sharing behaviour of temporary team members?

1.3 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in applying existing knowledge management theories to the specific context of the airline industry. By considering the characteristics and nature of temporary cabin teams, it investigates the mechanisms of knowledge sharing and evaluates existing research findings in this setting.

First, this study enhances knowledge sharing in the aviation industry, improving practitioners' skills and emergency response capabilities, thereby strengthening enterprise competitiveness and service quality. It provides organisational support—such as employee cognition, team synergy, and learning capacity—to promote effective knowledge-sharing behaviours. Although cabin crew roles are labor-intensive, their core responsibilities often shift between safety and service, creating ambiguity. This role confusion may lead to employee uncertainty and raise concerns about air transport safety. Such contradictions highlight the need to examine employees' intrinsic motivation for engaging in Organisational Citizenship

Behaviours (OCB), such as knowledge sharing. To emphasize the professionalism of cabin work, industry authorities and airlines consistently state that cabin crew members' primary duty is to ensure safety rather than to provide service. However, in actuality, their work is primarily service-oriented. Based on this, it is necessary to test whether employees' intrinsic intention for engaging in OCB like knowledge sharing is sufficient.

Second, it looks at the unique issues of transient cabin crew teams, whose very short lifecycle (CAAC 2024) limits the formation of trust—a key facilitator of knowledge sharing (De Long and Fahey 2000). Cabin crew careers are characterized by high pressure, safety risks, and diverse intentions, further complicated by an oversupply of graduates from lower-tier college programs. Structural features include varying levels of familiarity due to prior pairings and hierarchical positions based on experience. Effective team management is essential for flight safety (Margerison et al. 1986), and interpersonal interaction has been shown to enhance team identity and facilitate knowledge sharing (Swan et al. 1999). Aviation operations require specific knowledge to be prepared in advance (FAA 2023), yet existing studies rarely consider job or technical gradients as influencing variables. Unlike general studies on assimilation and socialization (Moreland and Levine 2002), and the research on establishing bidirectional psychological safety within a team (Tynan 2005), this study innovatively links pre-flight collaboration, which can also be regarded as ice-breaking, with the actual behaviors of teams in operation.

Third, this study contributes to the advancement of cabin resource management (CRM) implementation. ICAO (2020) confirms that crew coordination has a direct impact on aviation safety and service quality. Safety management has evolved from mechanical improvements to human error prevention and, more recently, to organisational systems such as SMS (ICAO 2024). Although CAAC has recently mandated CRM training for cabin crews (Wei, Xia. et al. 2024), many employees still

struggle to understand its practical value. By identifying barriers to knowledge sharing, this research offers actionable strategies to strengthen organisational learning.

Fourth, this study tests existing knowledge-sharing theories in digital contexts, where reduced face-to-face interaction affects cabin crews. Early research focused on IT systems (Hansen and Avital 2005), yet technical solutions alone fail to ensure knowledge sharing (Babcock 2004; KPMG 2000). Subsequent studies shifted attention to organisational factors, including organizational climate (Chih-Chien 2004; Willem and Scarbrough 2006), relationships (De Vries et al. 2006; Swan et al. 1999), incentives (Kim and Lee 2006), and individual traits (Bock et al. 2005; Cabrera et al. 2006).

However, these frameworks primarily target fixed teams (Qin, Kaiyin. et al. 2010) and overlook the unique characteristics of temporary teams, such as technical hierarchies, member familiarity gradients, and pre-flight preparation. While interdependence is generally believed to promote knowledge sharing (De Long and Fahey 2000), aviation safety standards may constrain this mechanism. In addition, existing models require further validation in the context of Chinese organisational culture. In conclusion, this research holds practical significance. It focuses on the issue of knowledge sharing, conducts in-depth analysis, explains the characteristics and mechanisms of knowledge-sharing patterns, and proposes actionable solutions to help enterprises enhance their competitiveness and achieve high-quality development.

1.4 Outline of the Dissertation

This dissertation comprises six chapters.

Chapter 1: introduces the research background, identifies the practical and theoretical gaps in temporary cabin crew teams, and presents the research aims, questions and scope of the study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review and Hypotheses. This chapter systematically reviews key theories relevant to the study, including knowledge, knowledge-sharing behaviour, and temporary teams. It also discusses theoretical perspectives such as trait arousal theory, organisational citizenship behaviour, and organisational fairness. Based on identified theoretical gaps and practical needs, the chapter proposes research hypotheses.

Chapter 3: Methodology. This chapter introduces the research methods used in this study and explains the rationale behind their selection. It covers sample selection, data collection procedures, the design of interviews and questionnaires, as well as the methods of data analysis. The relevant concepts and measurement approaches are also clarified.

Chapter 4: Research Findings. First, through interviews and qualitative analysis methods, a more comprehensive and broader understanding of the characteristics and patterns of knowledge sharing among cabin temporary team members was achieved. Second, based on the results of video observation and questionnaire surveys, regression analysis was conducted to empirically test the proposed hypotheses. This chapter focuses on the moderating effects of responsibility and achievement orientation among temporary team members on their intention and behaviours toward knowledge sharing, as well as the roles of member familiarity and perceived organisational fairness within the temporary team.

Chapter 5: Organisational Practice for Knowledge Sharing. This chapter designs and implements improvement plans aimed at enhancing employees' awareness and

attitudes toward knowledge sharing, strengthening their sharing capabilities, fostering a positive organisational climate, and testing the effectiveness of these initiatives.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Discussion. This chapter summarizes the research findings and highlights the theoretical contributions and practical implications of the study. It also discusses the study's limitations and proposes directions for future research.

The structure and technical route of the thesis is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2 Technology Roadmap

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Existing research on knowledge sharing is relatively extensive. Early studies emphasized its important role within organisations, followed by a focus on knowledge management systems (Hansen and Avital 2005). Later, researchers and industry observers recognized that relying solely on such systems could not effectively promote employees' knowledge-sharing behaviours (Babcock 2004; KPMG 2000). As a result, research gradually shifted toward organisational, team, and individual-level factors.

There is abundant research literature at three levels, which will be elaborated on in the following sections. At the organisational level, studies have focused on factors such as organisational culture (Chih-Chien 2004; Ismail Al-Alawi et al. 2007; Schepers and Van den Berg 2007; Willem and Scarbrough 2006). It is generally agreed that a climate of fairness, organisational support, and strong reciprocal relationships between individuals and the organisation contribute to knowledge sharing. In addition, researchers have extensively studied reward systems and performance management (Ferrin and Dirks 2003; Kim and Lee 2006;), as well as interpersonal relationships (Bakker et al. 2006; De Long and Fahey 2000; De Vries et al. 2006; Swan et al. 1999).

At the individual level, research focuses on the intention and behaviour associated with knowledge sharing (Bock et al. 2005; Cabrera et al. 2006; De Vries et al. 2006; Lin 2007; Lin 2007a). In behavioural studies, there are also two major paradigms: the technology-centered paradigm (Hendriks 1999; Nonaka 1994; Senge 1998) and the human-centered paradigm (Bock et al. 2005; Hansen and Avital 2005; Sundaresan and Zuopeng 2004). The former emphasizes knowledge interaction, focuses on the

knowledge innovation process and innovation capabilities, explores learning mechanisms in knowledge sharing, and investigates the role of ICT technologies. The latter centers on the individual as the main actor. From a market perspective, it examines knowledge exchange behaviour; from a power perspective, it explores power dynamics; and from a social-psychological perspective, it considers altruistic behaviour, extra-role behaviour, and self-determined behaviour.

Relevant scholars have conducted extensive research on organisational justice, trust, and organisational citizenship behaviour. However, most of these studies focus on fixed teams, and research on knowledge sharing in temporary teams remains limited. Existing studies on temporary teams mainly involve knowledge-intensive teams with longer life cycles, such as engineering construction teams (Anumba et al. 2005), new product development teams (Edmondson and Nembhard 2009), and film and television production teams (Bechky 2006). Clearly, these findings provide valuable insights for studying knowledge sharing within temporary cabin teams.

2.1 Research on Knowledge Sharing Behaviour and its Influencing Factors

2.1.1 The Definition of Knowledge and Knowledge Sharing

There are various criteria for classifying knowledge. Generally, based on the degree of programmability, knowledge can be divided into explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge (Polanyi 1983, pp. 3–25). Tacit knowledge is a valuable resource for enterprises because it is difficult to obtain, reproduce, and extremely costly (Grant 1996). Nonaka (1991) further developed this theory and divided tacit knowledge into cognitive tacit knowledge and technical tacit knowledge. The former refers to abstract concepts, judgments, and intuitions stored in an individual's mental model, which are difficult to externalize or articulate. The latter refers to skills acquired only through continuous practice and training. Later, Hakanson (2007) introduced several concepts

within Knowledge-Based Theory, defining knowledge as including explicit knowledge, internalized knowledge, procedural knowledge, and implicit knowledge. It is widely accepted in academia that tacit and explicit knowledge are not simply binary but exist on a continuum (Spender 1996). Furthermore, based on where knowledge is stored, some scholars (McLure Wasko and Faraj 2000) classify it into knowledge stored in organisations, groups, and individuals. Similarly, Collins (1993) proposed categories such as embrained knowledge, embodied knowledge, encultured knowledge, and symbol-type knowledge.

The competitive advantage of an enterprise stems from the sharing, absorption, and innovation of knowledge. In terms of the relationship between firms and knowledge, firms are knowledge-bearing entities that use knowledge to produce products and provide services (Foss 1996). By sharing, absorbing, and innovating this knowledge, firms can achieve better business performance. Differences in efficiency are determined by the effectiveness of knowledge retention and application. Knowledge-based theory explains why some firms are more innovative (Foss 1996) and possess comparative competitive advantages (Hakanson 2010). To some extent, enterprise competition is a competition of organisational knowledge. Knowledge is an asset for both individuals and organisations (Grant 1996). Some critics (Foss 2003) argue that individual knowledge and capability should be included in explaining enterprise capabilities. The lack of a clear methodological individualist foundation for concepts such as routines, capabilities, and competencies has led to certain explanatory challenges in modern organisational capability theory. Some scholars believe that in the knowledge economy era, enterprises should focus on intellectual capital (Dean and Kretschmer 2007), and they need to emphasize the sharing and transformation of employees' knowledge.

The academic community has provided various definitions of knowledge sharing. According to Nonaka (1994), group knowledge is formed through the continuous

exchange between explicit and tacit knowledge. Knowledge sharing behaviour refers to employees consciously and willingly providing their unique experiences and knowledge to others within the organisation (Vuori and Okkonen 2012). Gong et al. (2012) noted that through communication, employees can access more diverse knowledge and effectively integrate shared resources. Srivastava et al. (2006) defined knowledge sharing as the exchange of work-related ideas, information, and suggestions among team members. Similarly, Wang and Noe (2010) described knowledge sharing as the exchange of processed information, including ideas, facts, experiences, and judgments related to the performance of individuals, teams, and organisations. Skills, experience, and judgment—knowledge that must be acquired and transmitted through practice—are especially critical for cabin crew members. Clearly, knowledge sharing among cabin crew also includes this type of tacit knowledge. Therefore, this study adopts a broad definition of knowledge sharing, referring to the exchange of job-related information, ideas, suggestions, and skills to collectively enhance team performance.

Hendriks (1999) pointed out that knowledge sharing is a communication process, but unlike commodities, knowledge cannot circulate freely. When learning from others, individuals must reconstruct the information and possess the foundational knowledge required to understand and share what others offer. In essence, knowledge sharing is a conscious act and an intentional process. The source of knowledge does not relinquish ownership but instead shares it jointly with the recipient. Knowledge sharing primarily occurs at the individual level and is driven by individual behaviour. This behaviour enables organisational members to quickly understand and absorb each other's information, experience, and skills, which can stimulate thinking and promote the creation of new knowledge within the organisation.

Cabin crew members must handle both passenger interactions and various emergency situations. Relying solely on memorizing manual regulations is neither realistic nor

sufficient for addressing all issues. Operational skills—such as the use of cabin emergency equipment, bandaging injured passengers, and managing lithium battery fires—along with long-term experience, judgment, and other forms of tacit knowledge (e.g., identifying abnormal passenger behaviour, mediating conflicts, and controlling disruptive actions), must be acquired and passed down through practice. Therefore, knowledge sharing is essential. A related concept is knowledge transfer, which refers to the process by which one unit (an individual, team, or department) within an organisation is influenced by the experience of another (Argote and Ingram 2000). Ipe (2003) noted that, compared to knowledge sharing, knowledge transfer emphasizes the organisation’s leading role and has defined objectives and a clear direction of flow. This dissertation focuses on employees’ spontaneous knowledge-sharing behaviours rather than organisational-level knowledge transfer.

Table 1 The Definition of Knowledge and Knowledge Sharing

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
1983	Polanyi	Divide knowledge into explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge.
1991	Nonaka	Proposed the SECI model, namely socialization, combination, externalization, and internalization. Classified tacit knowledge into cognitive tacit knowledge and technical tacit knowledge.
1993	Collins	Knowledge is classified into four types: embrained knowledge, embodied knowledge, encultured knowledge, and symbol-type knowledge.
1994	Nonaka	Group knowledge is formed through an ongoing exchange of ideas between basic knowledge and hidden knowledge.
1996	Foss	Firms are knowledge-carrying entities, which use knowledge to produce products and provide services.
1996	Grant	Knowledge is an asset for individuals and organisations.
1999	Hendriks	Knowledge sharing is a communication process and must involve the act of reconstruction.
2000	McLure Wasko and Faraj	Knowledge is classified into: knowledge stored in enterprises, knowledge stored in groups, and knowledge stored in individuals.
2000	Argote and Ingram	Knowledge sharing is knowledge transfer, that is, the process in which one unit (individual, team, department)

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
		within an organisation is influenced by the experience of another unit.
2006	Srivastava et al.	Defined knowledge sharing as the sharing of work-related ideas, information and suggestions among team members.
2007	Hakanson	Knowledge includes explicit knowledge, internalized knowledge, procedural knowledge, and implicit knowledge.
2010	Wang and Noe	Determined the content of knowledge sharing as information processed by individuals, including ideas, facts, experiences and judgments related to the performance of individuals, teams and organisations.
2012	Vuori and Okkonen	Knowledge sharing behaviour refers to the behaviour that employees consciously and willingly provide unique experience and knowledge to other employees in the organisation.
2012	Gong et al.	Through communication with others, employees can capture more heterogeneous knowledge and efficiently synthesize shared resources.

2.1.2 Research on Influencing Factors of Knowledge Sharing

The existing literature and research findings have examined both the positive and negative factors influencing knowledge sharing. These factors are generally categorized into three levels: individual, environmental, and team. At the individual level, factors such as responsibility and self-evaluation have been studied. At the environmental level, elements such as context and stress have been investigated. At the team level, the focus has been on organisational policies and culture. Most studies have reached similar conclusions. However, due to cultural differences, some divergent findings have emerged, such as the influence of personal achievement orientation on knowledge sharing (Moon et al. 2008; Chae et al. 2019; Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022; Zhang, Chunmei. 2020). These related studies are closely aligned with the focus of this dissertation.

At the organisational level, general research results show that an organisational culture emphasizing trust and cooperation is helpful for employees' knowledge

sharing (Chih-Chien 2004; Ismail Al-Alawi et al. 2007; Schepers and Van den Berg 2007; Willem and Scarbrough 2006). Chih-Chien (2004) believes that when employees feel organisational competition, their willingness to share knowledge will decrease. Ismail Al-Alawi et al. (2007) state that a culture based on interpersonal trust and communication is positively associated with knowledge sharing within the organisation and give specific practical suggestions for managers in the Arab cultural context. In terms of cross-cultural aspects, Yujong Hwang and Kim (2007) find that individuals with higher levels of collectivism show more behaviours of sharing knowledge by email. Internalization and identification fully explain how collectivist culture affects attitudes towards knowledge sharing. Some scholars (Kim and Lee 2006) examine the compensation system of organisations and find that performance-based compensation encourages more knowledge sharing. They also point out that in the public sector, the longer an employee has worked, the more willing they are to share. Ferrin and Dirks (2003) find that the reward structure influences trust, and a collective reward system better supports employees' knowledge sharing than a competitive one. Regarding fixed teams, some scholars (De Vries et al. 2006) believe that the longer a team exists, the stronger its cohesion is, which helps knowledge sharing. A friendly and communicative style increases the willingness to share, and job satisfaction promotes both willingness and enthusiasm.

To improve the possibility of a certain kind of behaviour favorable to the enterprise, it is necessary to create a suitable atmosphere for the behaviour to occur. A good team atmosphere is enough to influence the subjective norm (SN). Some studies have explored organisational factors from the perspectives of cultural identity, values, and team atmosphere. The weakening of communal communication causes a feeling of estrangement (Ri 2020). Wang, Xianya. et al. (2014) believed that a trust atmosphere, a communication atmosphere, and a fair atmosphere significantly affect employees' tacit knowledge-sharing behaviour.

Some scholars believe that trust and a fair and safe atmosphere within the team are important factors for individuals when making decisions on knowledge sharing. Bakker et al. (2006) hold that when individuals perceive the honesty, integrity, and fairness of other members, the behaviour of knowledge sharing will increase. However, ability trust has a negative impact on knowledge sharing instead. Lin (2007b) pointed out that distributive justice indirectly affects knowledge sharing through organisational commitment and trust in co-workers; procedural justice and cooperativeness influence knowledge sharing only through organisational commitment; instrumental ties and expressive ties affect knowledge sharing through trust in co-workers. The research of Cohen-Charash and Spector (2001) found that a sense of procedural fairness helps improve job performance; satisfaction is related to distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice; organisational commitment and trust are mainly related to procedural justice. De Long and Fahey (2000) studied and believed that the level of mutual trust among employees has a significant positive impact on the flow of knowledge among employees within the organisation. Swan et al. (1999) hold that interpersonal interaction can enhance employees' team identity and promote their knowledge sharing. He criticized the excessive reliance on IT technology in the field of Knowledge Management (KM), arguing that it overlooks the social and tacit characteristics of knowledge, especially the difficulty of capturing and transmitting tacit knowledge through IT systems. Some knowledge-sharing literature focuses on the social and organisational context and incentive structure in which tasks and situations are situated, such as organisational environment, strength of employee relationships, incentive policies, interpersonal and team characteristics, cultural features, and individual characteristics (Wang and Noe, 2010).

Table 2 Research on Knowledge Sharing at the Organisational Level

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints	Research Perspective
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1999	Swan et al.	Interpersonal interaction can enhance identity recognition and promote knowledge sharing.	Interpersonal perspective
2000	De Long and Fahey	The level of trust has a significant impact on the flow of knowledge.	Trust perspective
2001; 2006; 2007b	Cohen-Charash and Spector; Bakker et al.; Lin	found that the sense of organisational fairness was positively correlated with the employees' knowledge-sharing behaviour.	Cultural perspective
2003; 2006	Ferrin and Dirks; Kim and Lee	A performance-based compensation system is conducive to knowledge sharing.	Human resources perspective
2004; 2006; 2007; 2007; 2014	Chih-Chien; Willem and Scarborough; Ismail Al-Alawi et al.; Schepers and Van den Berg; Wang, Xianya. et al.	An organisational atmosphere of fairness, organisational support, and strong exchange behaviours between individuals and the organisation are conducive to knowledge sharing.	Cultural perspective
2006; 2006	De Vries et al.; Bakker et al.	The longer a team has been established, the stronger its cohesion will be, and the more willing its members are to share knowledge.	Team characteristics perspective
2010	Wang and Noe	Proposed a research framework for knowledge sharing that encompasses five key areas: organisational context, interpersonal and team characteristics, cultural features, individual traits, and intentional factors.	Interpersonal perspective

At the individual level, Cabrera et al. (2006) studied personality factors and found that psychological variables are most predictive of knowledge sharing, especially self-efficacy and openness. Regarding attitude, when individuals see knowledge sharing as more useful, they are more willing to take relevant actions (Brock et al. 2005; Lin 2007). The higher the job satisfaction and the stronger the commitment to the

organisation, the more willing one is to engage in knowledge-sharing behaviour (Lin 2007a; De Vries et al. 2006).

Table 3 Research on Knowledge Sharing at the Individual Level

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints	Research Perspective
1994	Nonaka	Provide technical and organisational support to facilitate knowledge sharing.	Interactive perspective
1998	Senge	Knowledge sharing is a process of creation and learning.	Learning perspective
1999	Hendriks	Research on Incentives for Knowledge Sharing Based on ICT.	Communication Perspective
2004	Sundaresan and Zuopeng	Knowledge sharing is a decision-making model that maximizes benefits.	Market perspective
2005	Hansen and Avital	Knowledge sharing implies that an individual's power within an organisation is undermined.	Power perspective
2005	Bock et al.	Attitude and subjective norms have a significant positive impact on intention. Anticipated reciprocal relationship has a positive effect on attitude. Self-esteem has a positive influence on subjective norms. Organisational atmosphere has a significant impact on subjective norms and intention. Emphasized internal factors to explain voluntary knowledge-sharing.	Social psychological perspective
2006	Cabrera et al.	Found that psychological variables are the most predictive of knowledge sharing, especially self-efficacy and openness.	Social psychological perspective
2006	De Vries et al.	The higher the job satisfaction and the greater the commitment to the organisation, the more willing one is to engage in knowledge-sharing behaviour.	Social psychological perspective

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints	Research Perspective
2007	Lin	When individuals consider knowledge sharing to be more useful, they are more willing to take relevant actions. Found that attitude significantly positively influences the intention to share knowledge. Reciprocal benefits, knowledge self-efficacy, and enjoyment in helping others all significantly and positively influence attitude and intention.	Social psychological perspective
2007a	Lin	emphasized the crucial moderating role of exchange ideology in the knowledge sharing mechanism, suggesting that managers should adopt targeted management strategies based on the differences in employees' personal beliefs.	Social psychological perspective
2020	Xu, Ri.	The weakening of communal communication creates a feeling of estrangement.	Social psychological perspective

According to the above research, the organisational atmosphere and individuals' perception of risk influence organisational citizenship behaviour, including knowledge sharing. Cabin crew members' different views of the organisation also lead to different impacts.

These research findings on fixed team knowledge sharing provide valuable insights for cabin temporary teams. First, the cabin temporary team is also a group, so the rules of fixed team knowledge sharing may partly apply to temporary teams. For example, organisational fairness atmosphere refers to the characteristics of the entire organisation or department. Can individuals still perceive this influence in randomly changing temporary teams, and does it lead to changes in knowledge sharing behaviour? Another example is that perceived risk is an individual's consideration of costs and competitive advantages, which negatively affects knowledge sharing and

may even lead to knowledge concealment. Are individuals in temporary teams also influenced by this? Second, temporary teams have their own features in terms of organisational atmosphere, rapid trust, and relationship strength. These features may create new influence relationships. Compared to fixed teams, does the unique familiarity shift in temporary teams affect knowledge sharing? These are all questions worth studying.

2.2 Research Related to Temporary Teams

The concept of the temporary team was first proposed by Goodman (1976). He studied management issues in temporary systems, using the theater case as an example. By discussing research subjects such as the drama group, the audit group, and the research and development group, he defined them as a collection of technicians formed within a specific period to complete a complex task. This definition highlights the core characteristics of a temporary team: the technical expertise of team members and the complexity of the task.

Subsequently, Lundin and Söderholm (1995, 2003) pointed out in their research that temporary organisations might be a future direction of development. Through a comprehensive and systematic analysis of them, they laid a foundation for later scholars to carry out in-depth research on temporary organisations. They proposed that attention should be paid to the contextualization of the organisation, which includes four dimensions: time, geography, human factors, and concepts. Chinese scholars Qian, Yan. and Liu, Hong. (2007) further defined a temporary team as a form of enterprise organisation with fixed time nodes or time status indicating the end of the organisational mission. It is generally equivalent to a temporary organisation.

Qin, Kaiyin. et al. (2010), from the perspectives of personnel composition and task nature, described the temporary team as a short-term team formed by personnel from

different functional departments with different professional knowledge, helping enterprises effectively complete short-term tasks. Temporary teams usually have the following characteristics: temporary nature, interdependence, clear goals, short-term tasks, and organisational dependence. The formation factors of temporary teams were significantly positively correlated with knowledge sharing and rapid trust, and knowledge sharing was significantly positively correlated with rapid trust and performance.

Table 4 The Comparison Between Temporary Teams and Fixed Teams

Organisation and Characteristics	Temporary Organisation	Fixed Organisation
Time Management	Manage the Limited Time	Long-Term Survival and Development
Focus Point	Complete the Task	Achieve Strategic Goals
Organisational Form	Temporary Organisation	Formal Organisation

Based on literature studying knowledge sharing within enterprises through trust, especially interpersonal trust within the enterprise, which includes cognitive trust and emotional trust, the research covers both the individual level (Levin et al. 2003) and the organisational level (Panteli and Sockalingam 2005). Meyerson et al. (1995, pp. 166–195), in their in-depth study of rapid trust in temporary teams, described in detail the unique nature of such teams. In recent years, research on rapid trust has shown an upward trend and has gradually become a new direction in organisational and social trust theory. In these studies, rapid trust among team members is generally seen as an important intermediate variable for knowledge sharing. It includes institutional trust, emotional trust, and cognitive trust, and is regarded as an antecedent of intention for knowledge sharing. Research on the mediating role of rapid trust is already quite thorough, and this project does not repeat that discussion.

However, existing research mainly focuses on trust and knowledge sharing in fixed teams, but it lacks in-depth exploration of rapid trust and knowledge sharing in temporary teams. There have been few detailed studies on the knowledge-sharing behaviours and mechanisms of cabin crew temporary teams. The specific relationship between the constituent factors and knowledge sharing has not been analyzed, making the discussion appear general and unclear about the moderating and dominant factors of knowledge sharing. Most temporary teams studied are practice-oriented groups for technical breakthroughs, with few studies on teams that complete specific production tasks.

2.3 The Theoretical Perspectives Related to This Research

2.3.1 TPB

Regarding knowledge-sharing behaviour, many scholars have used the Theory of Rational Behaviour (TRA) and its extended Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to explain it (Chae et al. 2019). TRA was proposed by American scholars Ajzen and Fishbein in 1975. The theory holds that individual behaviour is driven by Behavioural Intention (BI), which is determined by the individual's attitude toward the behaviour (BA) and the Subjective Norm (SN). BA is an individual's judgment of whether they like or dislike the behaviour. It is a stable tendency formed through learning and shaped by behavioural beliefs. Belief refers to an individual's opinion about something. Subjective Norms (SN) are shaped by normative beliefs and the intention to comply. Normative Beliefs (NB) refer to the group's view on whether an individual should perform a certain behaviour. In turn, behaviour influences both behavioural beliefs and normative beliefs.

With the development of the theory, some scholars have examined the ways social influence affects intentional behaviour. Moan and Rise (2006) assessed Past Behaviour (PB), moral norms, self-identity, group identification, group norms, and action planning to improve the prediction of intentions. This theory assumes that people are rational and consider the meaning and consequences of actions by integrating information before acting.

Because TRA assumes that behaviour occurs under the control of individual willpower, it is used to predict and explain individual behaviour. However, in practice, the degree of individual volitional control is often influenced by many factors, such as time, money, information, and ability. As a result, TRA cannot reasonably explain behaviour that is not fully controlled by individual will. Therefore, Ajzen (1991) proposed the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) based on TRA. TPB places the concept of self-efficacy beliefs, or Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC), within a broader framework of the relationships among beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behaviours.

According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), behaviour is influenced by both Behavioural Intentions (BI) and Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC), while PBC comes from control beliefs. Behavioural Intention (BI) is determined by Behavioural Attitude (BA), Subjective Norm (SN), and Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC). Attitude, subjective norm, and perceived Behavioural control influence one another. PBC refers to the extent to which an individual perceives the performance of a behavior as easy or difficult, that is, the resources and opportunities they believe are available to do so. The more resources and opportunities individuals believe they have, the fewer obstacles they expect, and the stronger their perceived control over behaviour.

Figure 3 TPB

Source: (Ajzen 1991, p. 182)

The advantage of this theory is that it fully considers the constraining or promoting effects of subjective norms (SN) on human behaviour, which offers insights for enterprises to motivate employees to share and create knowledge. The predictive power of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) on individual behaviour has been questioned. Gotlieb et al. (1994) criticized that it is not entirely clear how the antecedents of intention are formed. Bagozzi (1992) argued that the theory does not explain the motivational process and the role of predictive factors in forming the antecedents of intention. Sheeran and Webb (2016) asserted that TPB overstates the cognitive control of behaviour, as individuals may have clear intentions but still fail to act. Ajzen (2011, p. 1123) also acknowledged that demographic variables such as education, age, gender, and income may influence intentions and behaviours indirectly by affecting more direct determinants in the theory.

Many scholars have used the TPB theory to summarize the factors influencing knowledge-sharing decisions, including formal incentives, reciprocity, power

perception, management expectations, peer expectations, and knowledge management systems (Hansen and Avital 2005). Bock (2005) empirically studied the significant effects of organisational atmosphere, sense of self-worth, and reciprocal expectations on attitudes toward knowledge sharing and subjective norms. The TPB framework has been widely applied in many individual-level studies on knowledge sharing. It is a human-centered research paradigm that explores how social psychology influences individual sharing behaviour. It is also applicable to this study.

Table 5 Research Related to TPB

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
1975	Ajzen and Fishbein	Propose TRA.
1991	Ajzen	The development of TRA into TPB and the proposal of PBC and SN are also Intentions. But behavioural intention mainly comes from conscientiousness and altruism.
2005	Hansen and Avital	The factors influencing knowledge sharing decisions include formal incentives, reciprocity, perception of power, management expectations, peer expectations, knowledge management systems, etc.
2005	Bock	An empirical study has been conducted on the significant influences of organisational atmosphere, sense of self-worth, and reciprocal expectations on attitudes towards knowledge sharing and subjective norms.
2005	Kraft et al.	Measuring PBC by perceived difficulty may not be enough, and PBC should be divided into instrumental and affective attitudes.

2.3.2 Personality Trait Theory

Among the many research papers on individual-level knowledge sharing, individual intentions are often analyzed from a social-psychological perspective, such as responsibility and altruism. This approach stems from personality trait theory. The theoretical basis of this study includes the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and

personality trait theory. The following section introduces the main schools of personality trait theory and the reasons for choosing the theory as the basis of this research topic.

2.3.2.1 Basic Concepts of Personality Trait Theory

Allport (1921, pp.441-455) first proposed the concept of personality traits in *Personality and Character*. Later, Allport (1961, pp.22–35) developed a complete theory of personality traits and published *Pattern and Growth in Personality*. Allport's personality traits are divided into two main categories: common traits and individual traits. The former refers to traits shared by most people or groups within a certain social and cultural context, while the latter refers to traits unique to an individual.

The main dimensions of the Three-Factor Model (Eysenck 1970 cited in Forrest 1971) are: extraversion, reflected in the difference between introversion and extroversion; neuroticism, shown in emotional stability differences; and psychoticism, reflected in negative traits such as loneliness, coldness, hostility, and oddity.

Cattell and Cattell (1995) proposed 16 mutually independent personality traits using the factor analysis method and developed the 16 Personality Factor Test (16PF). They identified 16 relatively independent personality dimensions, including A (Affinity for people), B (Intellectual ability), C (Emotional stability), D (Dominance), E (Extraversion), F (Conscientiousness), G (Daring), H (Sensitivity), I (Imagination), J (Suspiciousness), K (Sophistication), L (Anxiety), M (Radicalism), N (Independence), O (Self-discipline), and P (Tension), to describe the personalities of all people. Many researchers believe the 16PF is overly complex, while Eysenck's (1970) model is too limited in scope.

McCrae and Costa (1997) proposed the Five-Factor Model (FFM) of personality using a factorial analysis of the 16PF factors. FFM consists of the following five dimensions: Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. It became the most popular model for describing broad characteristics of personality. As for the intention to share knowledge, it is a common belief that personality factor of responsibility among organizational employees reflects an extension of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen 1991). However, many scientists suggest that personality trait of responsibility deserves more detailed investigation. For instance, Conscientiousness as one of the factors of the Five-Factor Model is too broad, according to Hough and Oswald (2005). As Ashton (1998) claims: "Narrow traits are better predictors of job performance than are the factors that subsume them". Furthermore, Harrison et al. (2006) emphasize the idea that "specific behavioral intentions are best predictors of specific behaviors, and broad attitudes are best predictors of broad behavioral outcomes". Costa and McCrae (1992) distinguish six sub-components of conscientiousness: competence, order, self-discipline, deliberation, dutifulness, and achievement striving. On the other hand, Hogan et al. (1997) and Saucier and Ostendorf (1999) suggest the existence of four facets of conscientiousness: achievement (industriousness), order, cautiousness (decisiveness–consistency), and dependability (dutifulness).

Although conscientiousness is often viewed as the factor most closely related to job performance (Judge et al. 2013), an increasing number of scholars argue that it is not one-dimensional but consists of two aspects that affect individual behaviour and outcomes differently (Dudley et al. 2006; Dunn et al. 1995; Hough 1992; Judge and Zapata 2015). These two aspects are dutifulness (or dependability) and achievement striving. Moon et al. (2008) argues that dutifulness and achievement striving reflect other-centered and self-centered traits, respectively, and that they are positively and negatively related to taking charge. It is important to distinguish between them. This idea aligns with Ajzen's TPB theory. According to TPB, behavioural intention is

mainly influenced by conscientiousness and altruism (Ajzen 1991). This study adopts that view and strictly distinguishes between responsibility and the pursuit of self-achievement. It examines how these traits affect knowledge-sharing intention from both self-interested and altruistic perspectives, and how they are influenced by team characteristics. According to Chae et al. (2019), dutifulness and achievement striving are positively and negatively correlated with knowledge-sharing behaviour, respectively. This distinction highlights how different intentions lead to different effects in knowledge sharing. For details, see Table 6.

Table 6 Research Related to Trait Theory and Knowledge Sharing

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
1921	Allport	Propose the concept of personality traits.
1961	Allport	Stand out a complete theory of personality traits. Personality Traits are divided into two major categories: Common Traits and Individual Traits.
1970	Eysenck	A three-factor model is proposed, including extraversion, neuroticism and psychoticism.
1992	Costa and McCrae	Categorize conscientiousness into competence, order, self-discipline, deliberation, dutifulness, and achievement striving six categories.
1995	Cattell and Cattell	Sixteen mutually independent personality traits were proposed, and the 16 Personality Factors Test (abbreviated as 16PF) was developed.
1996	Cheung et al.	Personality trait models and scales have certain limitations in a cross-cultural context.
1997	Costa and McCrae	The Five Factors Model (FFM) was developed based on the 16PF. The five factors are: Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. This theory is the most widely accepted model of personality structure.

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
1998	Ashton	Narrow traits are better predictors of job performance than are the factors that subsume them.
1997; 1999	Hough and Oswald	Conscientiousness is subdivided into achievement (industriousness), order, cautiousness (decisiveness-consistency) and dependability (dutifulness).
2006	Harrison et al.	Specific behaviour intentions are the best predictors of specific behaviours and broad attitudes best predict broad behavioural outcomes.
2008	Moon et al.	Dutifulness and achievement striving represent other-centered and self-centered dimensions, respectively, and are positively and negatively correlated with taking charge.
2013	Judge et al.	Conscientiousness was seen as the factor most consistent with job performance.
1992; 1995; 2006; 2015	Hough; Dunn et al.; Dudley et al.; Judge and Zapata	View conscientiousness not as one-dimensional, but as consisting of two aspects that have different effects on individual behaviour and outcomes, namely dutifulness (or dependability) and achievement striving.
2019	Chae et al.	Dutifulness and achievement striving are positively and negatively correlated with knowledge sharing behaviour, respectively.

However, some research (Cheung et al. 1996) has found that these trait theories and measures have their shortcomings when applied across cultures. For instance, the unique culture-specific aspects of Chinese society, such as the concepts of popularity, face, and harmony, are not adequately addressed. Consequently, some researchers (Wang and Cui 2003) have created a personality traits scale for the Chinese population.

2.3.2.2 Cultural Contingency in Personality-Behaviour Relationships

While there is considerable evidence to support the validity of the Five-Factor Model and other trait theories in Western environments, a series of studies have shown that the manifestation and outcomes of personality traits can vary across cultures

(Hofstede 1983; Cheung et al. 1996). Within collectivist societies like China, the quest for individual accomplishment is frequently viewed not only in the context of personal gain but also in terms of organizational achievements (Zhang, Chunmei. 2020). As a result, certain traits, including achievement orientation (AO), may behave in ways different from those observed in individualistic environments, where the emphasis is more on self-interest and competition (Moon et al. 2008; Chae et al. 2019). The recent work conducted in China has started to highlight some of these differences by suggesting that achievement motivation among collectivist societies may lead to cooperation and knowledge sharing rather than withholding information (Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022). This cultural contingency has important implications for theorising knowledge sharing in non-Western organisational contexts and informs the hypotheses developed later in this chapter.

2.3.3 TAT & SST

The Trait Activation Theory (TAT) extends personality trait theory by emphasizing the role of situational factors in activating individual traits. In temporary teams, changing circumstances are an important variable that can affect individual intention for knowledge sharing. Therefore, TAT also serves as an important theoretical foundation for this study.

The theory that internal traits and external situations jointly determine individual behaviour has long been a consensus in modern psychology (Robbins and Judge 2014, pp.62-79). Interactive psychology, which emphasizes the combined importance of personality traits and situational factors, is considered the theoretical foundation of trait activation (Tett and Guterman 2000). The proposal of Trait Activation Theory (TAT) (Tett et al. 2003), from the perspective of interactionist psychology, explores the dynamic link between external situations and internal traits, emphasizing the predictive role of situational factors.

Figure 4 TAT

Source:(Tett, Burnett, and Zedeck 2003)

The traits hidden within an individual can be activated in suitable work situations. Once activated, these traits can prompt individuals to display corresponding work behaviours. Throughout the process of trait activation, individuals receive intrinsic rewards, which refer to inner satisfaction. This inner satisfaction, together with extrinsic rewards based on job performance, reshapes an individual's work behaviour. Tett et al. (2003) used the activation of the Big Five personality traits as an example within the framework of three situational levels: task, social, and organisational. They explained the meanings of situational characteristics such as job demand, distracter, constraint, releaser, and facilitator. For different Big Five traits, different levels of situational factors support trait activation and matching. Regular task-oriented work, frequent communication, and high dependence on colleagues can help activate the sense of responsibility trait. Among the five situations, job demand shows the most obvious positive moderating effect.

Table 7 The Relationship Between Five Situations and “Trait – Behaviour”

Comparative dimension	Role in trait–performance relationship	Situational feature				
		Job demand	Distraction	Constraint	Release	Facilitator
Frequency	Predictability	Chronic	Chronic	Chronic	Acute	Acute
Activation status	Strength	+	+	-	-	*
Behavioural value	Direction	+	-	+/-	+/-	+/-

Tett and Burnett (2003) proposed that trait arousal involves not only personality but also the stimulation of knowledge, skills, and abilities in related situations. Managers can make full use of individual talents by analyzing whether personality, knowledge, skills, and abilities fit the job, thus promoting effective work behaviour and improving performance. This theory was further developed by scholars such as De Hoogh et al. (2005), Barrick et al. (2013), and Judge and Zapata (2015).

Personality and Assessment (Mischel 1968 cited in Mischel 2009) is a classic critique of traditional trait theory. The book argues that behavioral changes are best understood through the dynamic interaction between the individual and the situation, a perspective that eventually led to his Cognitive-Affective Processing System (CAPS) theory. His research has advanced the study of situational influences, including the Situational Strength Theory (SST). Barrick and Mount (1993) pointed out that autonomy moderates the relationship between the Big Five personality dimensions and job performance. The predictive validity of agreeableness was stronger in high-autonomy jobs than in low-autonomy ones, it was negatively correlated with performance, suggesting that less agreeable managers might excel in such contexts. They provided strong empirical evidence that job autonomy, as a weak situation, allows personality to predict performance. Meyer et al. (2009) conducted a meta-analysis on the moderating effect of situational strength on the relationship

between conscientiousness and performance. Their findings showed that in weaker situations, conscientiousness has a stronger predictive effect on performance. Based on this situationalist view, Andrews (2009) found that when both procedural fairness and distributive fairness are low, political skill is positively correlated with performance and OCB. When both are high, the correlation becomes negative. SST and TAT are seen as two sides of the same coin. Situational strength offers a new perspective for studying knowledge sharing, a typical organisational citizenship behaviour.

2.3.4 OCB and Helping Behaviour

The concept of helping behaviour originally came from altruism, which was seen as offering help to others without expecting anything in return (Smith et al., 1983). Later, Podsakoff et al. (2000), in their study of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), included helping behaviour as one of its seven dimensions. They defined helping behaviour as including altruism, politeness, benevolent mediation, praise, interpersonal support, and most other forms of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour. Based on the definition of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), Bamberger and Levi (2009) defined helping behaviour in the workplace as employees voluntarily using their own time and energy to support others' work. Helping behaviour in a team refers to the voluntary assistance of colleagues with work-related problems and tasks (Mossholder et al. 2011). Helping behaviour can improve relationships and enhance efficiency. According to existing research, knowledge sharing is considered a form of helping behaviour.

Table 8 The Definition of Helping Behaviour

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
1983	Smith et al.	Helping behaviour is an act of giving help to others without expecting anything in return.
2000	Podsakoff et al.	Helping behaviour consists of altruism, polite manners, kind mediation and applause, interpersonal

Year	Scholar	Main Viewpoints
		promotion, and most organisational citizenship behaviours, etc.
2009	Bamberger and Levi	The act of employees spending their own time and energy for free to support others' work.
2011	Mossholder et al.	The act of voluntarily helping colleagues solve work-related problems and tasks.

2.3.5 Risk Perception and Knowledge Concealment

Contrary to knowledge sharing, knowledge hiding is based on considerations of personal risks, gains, and losses. Many research findings on the sharing behaviour of fixed teams point out the dilemma between knowledge sharing and the loss of personal advantage. Knowledge hiding reflects this dilemma and is rooted in risk-benefit analysis. Cabrera et al. (2002) emphasized this trade-off. Connelly (2012) first provided a clear definition of knowledge concealment, referring to the deliberate act of hiding or withholding knowledge when others request it. After the concept was proposed, it quickly attracted widespread attention from scholars both domestically and internationally. Current studies indicate that knowledge concealment can reduce individual or organisational performance (Chatterjee et al. 2021; Wang, Yonggui. et al. 2019), harm interpersonal relationships based on mutual trust, and lower individual or team creativity (Zhao, Hongdan. and Xia, Qing. 2019). These negative effects show the importance of understanding knowledge hiding as distinct from knowledge sharing in organisational behaviour research.

The main risks of knowledge sharing are as follows. First, there is the risk of knowledge diffusion. Individual knowledge is a personal resource that can improve work efficiency and bring economic benefits, power, and reputation (Hansen and Avital, 2005). Once knowledge is shared, the owner loses control and may face the risk of unlimited dissemination toward external parties through recipients. The diffusion of knowledge can result in the loss of these advantages within the

organisation. Second, there is the risk of no return. Knowledge sharing is a form of social exchange behaviour, which relies on the principle of mutual benefit to be maintained, regulated, and promoted. Whether the knowledge recipient provides any return depends entirely on their self-awareness and willingness to honor this principle. Third, there is the risk of misuse. The fear that shared knowledge may be used incorrectly, possibly harming one's reputation or interests within the organisation, often discourages sharing (Andrews and Delahaye 2000; Riege 2005). If the knowledge recipient is incompetent, misuse becomes more likely. Selecting a capable sharing partner can reduce this risk. Fourth, there is the risk of exposing personal weaknesses and becoming a target for criticism or competition. Fifth, there is the risk of not being recognized. Receiving knowledge requires psychological effort (DePaulo and Fisher 1980), and in some cases, recipients may feel uncomfortable or even resentful. In Eastern cultures that emphasize modesty, active sharing may lead to negative feedback. Based on these concerns, team members may choose to adopt knowledge hiding strategies. Knowledge sharing and knowledge hiding represent different decisions based on individual risk assessments. This study considers perceived risk an important moderating variable.

2.3.6 Organisational Justice Theory

Studies have shown that organisational fairness has a significant impact on employees' organisational citizenship behaviour. Organisational Justice Theory (OJT) focuses on individuals' perceptions of fairness within their organisation (Greenberg 1987). It is mainly divided into three dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. Colquitt (2001) further divided interactional justice into informational justice and interpersonal justice. Cohen-Charash and Spector (2001) and Colquitt (2001) found that employees' perceptions of procedural fairness positively affect job performance. Lim and Loosemore (2017) found that a strong

perception of organisational fairness supports employees' Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB).

2.4 The Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

Based on the existing literature and interview results, a theoretical framework and related hypotheses are proposed.

Figure 5 Theoretical Framework

2.4.1 The Positive Relationship between Responsibility and Knowledge Sharing Intention

Dutiful employees are reliable and honest (Hough 1992). As a result, they are less likely to act selfishly and are motivated to contribute to the organisation (Moon et al. 2008).

Achievement strivers help only when they see helping as part of their role, while dutiful individuals broaden their perceptions of helping responsibilities. A sense of responsibility drives employees to act for the organisation's benefit without focusing

on personal costs. Duty contributes to building trust, expanding helping role perceptions, and encouraging helping behaviours (Marinova et al. 2013).

Individuals act based on their evaluation of personal consequences. The value of concern for others is thought to come from a process in which individuals accept social information without carefully weighing its personal cost. They are motivated to take actions that support the welfare of others and the organisation, even when such actions may lead to negative feedback that threatens their ego or self-perception. In contrast, individuals low in concern for others tend to reject feedback that does not lead to personally valued outcomes (Korsgaard et al. 1997).

Tangirala et al. (2013) pointed out that the behaviour of speaking up for employees “has contrasting relationships with two traits: duty orientation, referring to employees’ dispositional sense of moral and ethical obligation at the workplace, and achievement orientation,” which reflects “their ingrained personal ambition to get ahead professionally.” Dutiful individuals tend not to focus on how their actions affect their personal interests. As a result, they may engage in behaviours that benefit others, such as knowledge sharing, even when such behaviours involve personal cost or risk. Compared with employees driven by personal ambition (achievement orientation), those motivated by a sense of responsibility based on quality and morality (responsibility orientation) are more likely to act for the benefit of the larger group and speak their minds at work. This is because employees with high dutifulness orientation focus on fulfilling their moral obligations to the organisation (Costa and McCrae 1992). Dutifulness is associated with an escalation of an individual’s commitment to the organization. The focus of responsible people is not on self-risk (Moon 2001).

Grant and Wrzesniewski (2010) confirmed that responsibility is other-directed and linked to feelings of guilt or gratitude. They found that others’ satisfaction depends on

how well individuals fulfill their obligations, which may inspire a stronger sense of responsibility. Employees view others as allies, which highlights mutual interests and their ability to work together. “Duty strengthened the link between core self-evaluations and the objective productivity of call center employees, and this moderating effect was mediated by anticipated guilt and gratitude.”

Conscientious employees tend to be supportive because they genuinely care about the well-being of others and possess a strong normative sense of responsibility toward others (Moon et al. 2008). As a result, they regard knowledge sharing as a way to act beyond personal self-interest and to contribute to the collective good. Vuori and Okkonen’s (2012) research shows that the primary intention for sharing knowledge through internal social media platforms within an organisation is to help the organisation achieve its goals and support colleagues. In contrast, economic rewards and personal career development are seen as the least motivating factors. This clearly reflects an altruistic motive.

To sum up, knowledge sharing is a typical form of altruistic behaviour, and dutifulness is one of its main driving forces. Based on this, the following hypotheses are proposed. To strengthen team cohesion and improve market competitiveness, organisations actively promote knowledge sharing behaviour. Previous research suggests that responsibility is a key factor that drives knowledge sharing. This sense of responsibility generates the intention to share knowledge, which in turn results in actual knowledge sharing behaviour.

The internalization of a sense of responsibility into employees’ “sense of duty” toward knowledge sharing (the normative belief in TRA) directly enhances behavioural intentions and promotes organisational citizenship behaviour. Research has shown that when knowledge sharing is central to one’s professional identity (e.g., “sharing knowledge is part of being a professional”), this sense of responsibility is

further transformed into intrinsic intention, which strengthens behavioural execution. Responsible personality traits, job skill requirements, and knowledge sharing self-efficacy all have significant positive effects on knowledge sharing behaviour. Moreover, job skill requirements and knowledge sharing self-efficacy jointly moderate the relationship between responsible personality and knowledge sharing behaviour (Hao, Qi. et al. 2019). This study places responsibility within the framework of temporary team research and develops related hypotheses accordingly.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the temporary team members' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.4.2 The Negative Relationship between Achievement Orientation and Knowledge Sharing Intention

Individuals who strive for achievement are generally less willing to share knowledge than those driven by a sense of duty, as they tend to prioritize their personal interests over the collective good. They often believe that sharing knowledge may reduce their competitive edge. Achievement Orientation reflects a self-focused mindset, where individuals continuously push themselves to improve and perform at their best. This orientation is associated with competitiveness and a strong emphasis on personal performance, which can also contribute to leadership emergence. Additionally, achievement striving intensifies an individual's desire to compete and surpass others (Marinova et al. 2013).

At the core of achievement striving lies, the desire to win in interpersonal relationships (Smither and Houston 1992). Individuals who pursue achievement tend to focus more on their own performance and less on the well-being and interests of others. When they are driven by the need to compete and surpass others, they often believe that success can only be achieved when others fail, leading to an excessive

emphasis on workplace competition (Ng and Lucianetti 2016). Research shows that “subconscious achievement goals enhance task performance, while subconscious underachievement goals can lead to goal abandonment.” In contrast, “the effect of difficult conscious goals depends on resource allocation and the timing of goal pursuit” (Sitzmann and Bell 2017). Individuals who strive for personal achievement may also fear losing their knowledge advantage, and uncertainty about the potential benefits of knowledge sharing can further discourage them from contributing.

The other-centered trait of duty is positively associated with taking charge, while the self-centered trait of achievement striving shows a negative relationship with taking charge. Pursuing personal achievement is often linked to a decline in commitment. When individuals focused on personal achievement perceive that sharing knowledge may cause them to lose their status or allow others to surpass them, they are likely to become unwilling to share their knowledge (Moon et al. 2008).

Thus, consistent with their self-focused mindset, individuals with high achievement striving tend to act in their own best interest rather than share knowledge or speak up for the benefit of others and the organisation. In contrast to a dutifulness orientation, an achievement orientation is negatively associated with the conceptualization of voice roles (Tangirala et al. 2013).

However, not all scholars view achievement orientation as negatively related to knowledge sharing. Participants with low achievement orientation engaged in social loafing, but only when they expected their coworkers to exert high effort. However, when they expected their colleagues to exert little effort, they would maintain their own effort level, which might be a phenomenon of social compensation. In contrast, participants with high achievement orientation did not show social loafing, regardless of expected coworker effort. As a result, they may underestimate the benefits of sharing knowledge (Hart et al. 2004).

Some Chinese researchers suggest that there is an indirect positive pathway. Specifically, through institutional design—such as linking promotion opportunities with knowledge contribution—achievement orientation can be transformed into sharing intention via external reward expectations (attitudes in TPB), which in turn indirectly promotes knowledge-sharing behaviour (Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022). In addition, research indicates that prestige-driven competition can enhance individual innovation performance by encouraging knowledge-sharing behaviour. Zhang, Chunmei. (2020) argued that under China’s collectivist culture, achievement orientation is more likely to be transformed into sharing behaviour through social identity, emphasizing the moderating role of subjective norms. Based on these contrasting perspectives, the researcher tentatively proposes the following hypothesis.

It is essential to stress that the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing (KS) from a theoretical point of view looks quite contentious. The existing literature demonstrates that studies conducted in the West and competitive business environment associated with it found that AO is negatively correlated with KS due to the fact that this is a self-oriented characteristic that tends to inhibit knowledge sharing since there is a fear of losing one's competitive edge (Moon et al. 2008; Chae et al. 2019). On the other hand, studies conducted in Chinese organisations revealed either positive relationships or mediation between AO and KS due to the fact that in such environments, the success of a person can be linked to group success and can manifest itself through cooperation (Zhang, Chunmei. 2020; Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022). It is also important to mention that Chae et al. (2019) studied South Korea, a country that belongs to East Asia but exhibits characteristics that look like Western achievements (competitive and market driven environment), while China tends to value relations and groups more than achievement per se.

However, the aforementioned conflict between the predominately Western-oriented negative perception and the Chinese findings showing possible positive outcomes is worthy of further examination. This implies that the connection between AO and knowledge sharing could be much more situation-specific than what has been known before. The below hypothesis is formulated in light of such considerations.

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between the temporary team members' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.4.3 The Positive Relationship between Knowledge Sharing Intention and Knowledge Sharing

In the early stages, academic research on knowledge management mainly focused on knowledge information systems. However, this narrow perspective was later considered problematic. For example, Swan et al. (1999) provided empirical evidence showing the difficulties many technicians faced when applying knowledge management methods. The IT-driven approach often failed because it overlooked human-related factors in knowledge sharing. As a response, two major paradigms emerged: the technology-centered paradigm and the human-centered paradigm. The technology-centered paradigm emphasizes interaction, learning, and communication, with key contributors including Nonaka (1994), Senge (1998), and Hendriks (1999). In contrast, the human-centered paradigm focuses on market dynamics, power relations, and psychosocial factors in knowledge sharing. Its representative scholars include Sundaresan and Zuopeng (2004), Hansen and Avital (2005), and Bock et al. (2005). Regarding psychosocial factors, some researchers have highlighted the significance of organisational culture (Petrash 1996), knowledge-sharing attitudes (Rajan, Lank, and Chapple 1998, pp.35-42), and the willingness of enterprises (Ruggles 1998) in improving the effectiveness of knowledge management.

Based on Theory of Rational Behaviour (Ajzen and Fishbein 1975) and its extension Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991), an individual's Behavioural Attitude (BA) is an important predecessor of Behavioural Intention (BI). Then, BI, Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC), and Subjective Norm (SN) become the immediate predecessors of actual Behaviour. In such a system, BI plays a mediator role. Behavioural Attitude (BA) is an individual's feeling of liking or not liking a specific behaviour. An individual assesses such beliefs by how helpful they perceive the knowledge sharing to be. The literature on knowledge sharing supports such theoretical foundations. When individuals perceive knowledge sharing as helpful, they perform such behaviours more often (Bock et al. 2005; Lin 2007).

With the development of the theory, some scholars have explored how social influence affects intentional behaviour. Moan and Rise (2006) examined factors such as Past Behaviour (PB), moral norms, self-identity, group identification, group norms, and action planning to improve the prediction of behavioural intentions. A key assumption underlying this theory is that individuals are rational and consider the meaning and consequences of their actions by integrating various forms of information before deciding to act.

Intentions for knowledge sharing—such as internal satisfaction, a sense of responsibility, and expectations of external rewards—shape an individual's positive attitude toward sharing behaviour and further enhance behavioural intentions. As the core driving force behind behavioural intention, knowledge-sharing intention is translated into actual behaviour through the interaction of attitudes and social norms.

As mentioned earlier, Moon et al. (2008) argued that dutifulness and achievement striving represent orientations toward others and oneself, respectively, and are positively and negatively related to conscientiousness and responsibility in the workplace. Several studies (Chae et al. 2019) have clearly distinguished between

dutifulness and achievement striving. This distinction aligns with Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), which suggests that behavioural intention is primarily influenced by conscientiousness and altruism. However, in Chae et al.'s (2019) study, key mediating variables such as knowledge-sharing intention and sharing intention were not examined. Therefore, the relationship between dutifulness, achievement striving, and knowledge-sharing behaviour remains unclear and requires further investigation.

To sum up, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) and Knowledge Sharing (KS).

Hypothesis 3a: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).

Hypothesis 3b: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).

2.4.4 The Moderating Relationship between Familiarity and Knowledge Sharing

Regarding the influence of team member familiarity on knowledge sharing, the following studies and scholars provide theoretical support:

Reagans and McEvily (2003) found that the intensity of social networks among team members—including social cohesion and tie strength—significantly influences the efficiency of knowledge transfer. High tie strength is associated with members to share tacit knowledge more frequently and engage in deeper communication.

Similarly, Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), drawing on social capital theory, argued that

network ties and interaction, as elements of structural social capital, facilitates shared understanding and the development of group norms, thereby improving both the frequency and quality of knowledge exchange. Levin and Cross (2004) further demonstrated that trust mediates the relationship between strong ties and knowledge sharing. In teams with strong ties, trust is more easily established, which in turn supports more effective knowledge integration. Although the above-mentioned literature did not directly use the term “familiarity”, the concepts such as “social cohesion”, “tie strength”, “network ties”, and “interaction” it employed are inherently part of the meaning of “familiarity”. This is helpful for this study to put forward relevant hypotheses about familiarity.

According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), individuals are influenced by their environment and social relationships, which shape their subjective norms. Prior studies have shown that a high level of team-member exchange fosters employees’ engagement in organisational citizenship behaviours (Kamdar and Dyne 2007). Research by Bakker et al. (2006) and Sawng, Kim, and Han (2006) indicates that the longer a team has been established, the stronger its cohesion tends to be, which in turn promotes employees’ knowledge-sharing behaviours. De Long and Fahey (2000) found that mutual trust among employees significantly affects the flow of knowledge within an organisation. Similarly, Swan et al. (1999) argued that interpersonal interaction strengthens employees’ sense of team identity and facilitates knowledge sharing. Cabrera et al. (2006) also identified peer support as one of the key factors influencing knowledge sharing behaviour.

However, not all studies on familiarity and knowledge sharing have reached consistent conclusions. Hansen (1999) proposed the theory of weak-tie advantage, suggesting that while strong ties—characterized by high familiarity—facilitate the in-depth sharing of complex knowledge due to reduced communication barriers through

trust, weak ties—characterized by low familiarity—can also introduce novel information. In temporary cabin work teams, fluctuations in member familiarity are more pronounced than in other groups, as these teams typically have shorter durations of collaboration and interaction. This raises important questions: Does low familiarity promote the sharing of new information? Or does high familiarity more effectively reduce communication barriers and increase both the frequency and depth of knowledge sharing?

Overall, strong team-member exchange relationships enhance mutual trust, increase communication and interaction, and reduce concerns related to knowledge sharing. As a result, individuals gain a sense of psychological safety and support, making them more willing to share knowledge.

Here, the hypothesis was put forward:

Hypothesis 4: Familiarity (FA) positively moderates the relationship between responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.4.5 The Moderating Relationship between Risk Perception and Knowledge Sharing

As mentioned earlier, employees may perceive five types of risks associated with knowledge sharing. The first is the risk of losing one's advantage within the organisation. Hansen and Avital (2005) noted that knowledge is a valuable resource that enhances work efficiency and generates economic benefits. However, once knowledge is disseminated, individuals may lose their exclusive control and face the risk of its uncontrolled spread toward other members, diminishing their competitive edge. The second is the risk of no return. Knowledge sharing is often viewed as a social exchange behaviour governed by the principle of reciprocity, yet whether the

recipient reciprocates depends entirely on their own awareness and sincerity. The third involves potential misuse. Knowledge owners may worry that their contributions will be used inappropriately, harming their reputation or interests within the organisation (Andrews and DeLahaye 2000; Rigge 2005). If the recipients lack competence, misuse becomes more likely, although selecting capable recipients can help mitigate this risk. Some participants also expressed concerns about being misunderstood. The fourth risk is the exposure of personal weaknesses, which may lead to ridicule or criticism from colleagues and reduce one's willingness to share. The fifth risk concerns the lack of recognition. DePaulo and Fisher (1980) suggested that receiving help carries a psychological cost, and providers of knowledge may feel unacknowledged. In cultures that value modesty, such as those in Eastern societies, openly sharing knowledge may even attract criticism. As a result of these perceived risks, employees may adopt knowledge-hiding strategies to protect their interests.

Obviously, when considering the costs and potential negative consequences of knowledge sharing, employees' intention to share can be significantly affected, ultimately influencing their decision-making. If knowledge owners perceive that sharing knowledge will reduce their competitive advantage or jeopardize their status and promotion opportunities within the organisation, their subjective expectation of loss increases. To minimize such perceived loss, they may choose to withhold knowledge.

Hypothesis 5: Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.4.6 The Moderating Relationship between Organisational Fairness Atmosphere and Knowledge Sharing

Greenberg (1987) proposed the Organisational Justice Theory (OJT), which examines how individuals perceive fairness within their organisations. According to this theory, organisational justice includes three main dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. Colquitt (2001) further divided interactional justice into two components: informational justice and interpersonal justice. Cohen-Charash and Spector (2001), as well as Colquitt (2001), found that employees' perceptions of procedural justice have a positive effect on job performance. Lim and Loosemore (2017) found that when employees perceive a high level of organisational justice, they are more likely to engage in Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB). This outcome is easy to understand.

In the relationship between achievement intention and knowledge sharing intention, process variables may play a moderating role. Research has shown that perceived fairness is an important factor influencing employees' decisions about whether to share knowledge. Among the four types of fairness, informational fairness, interpersonal fairness, distributive fairness, and procedural fairness, procedural fairness is the most widely discussed, as it focuses on the process. The second most emphasized is distributive fairness, which focuses on outcomes.

Schepers and Van Den Berg (2007) found that procedural fairness has a positive effect on employees' perceptions of knowledge sharing. Lin (2007) pointed out that both distributive fairness and procedural fairness can influence individual knowledge sharing behaviour.

Organisational atmosphere fairness refers to employees' subjective perception of fairness within the organisation. It influences their work performance, organisational citizenship behaviour, and sense of identity. De Cremer (2005) indicated that perceived procedural fairness can promote employee cooperation, as it helps facilitate the self-other merging process. Tyler and Blader (2003) proposed the Group

Engagement Model, which suggests that procedural fairness enhances employees' pride and identity by conveying information related to identity recognition, thereby encouraging extra-role behaviour. Based on these studies, it can be concluded that a fair organisational atmosphere affects employees' trust in, recognition of, and support for the organisation, and determines how willing they are to perform behaviours expected by the organisation. If employees perceive the organisation as unfair, the environment as unsafe, or leadership as unjust, they may feel concerned about their surroundings and hesitate to share knowledge.

Although Organisational Justice Theory (OJT) offers important insights into the role of perceptions of justice in promoting citizenship behavior, an alternative theoretical viewpoint is presented by Situational Strength Theory (SST) (Mischel 1968; Meyer et al. 2009). The theory suggests that powerful situations, which feature explicit norms, consistent expectations, and predictable outcomes, reduce the likelihood of the manifestation of dispositional differences, including personality traits. In less powerful situations, the effect of personal predispositions on behavior would be more pronounced. Translating the SST into the domain of organisational fairness suggests that a powerful perception of fairness can be interpreted as a powerful situation: under conditions of transparent evaluations and equal distribution of benefits, individuals' actions will be determined by established rules rather than personal characteristics. In less powerful perceptions of organisational justice, personality characteristics, like AO, will have a more significant impact on behavior.

Hypothesis 6: Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.4.7 The Moderating Relationship between Interaction Quality in Pre-flight Preparation and Knowledge Sharing

Does the interaction quality of pre-flight preparation influence employees' knowledge-sharing during the formal duty stage? In this narrow and specialized field, gaps still exist in the current research literature. However, the effects of similar “ice-breaking activities” on teamwork can be indirectly supported by the following research findings.

Some scholars have examined interpersonal interaction patterns during the early stages of team formation from the perspective of team dynamics. For example, Team Development Stage Model (Forming–Storming–Norming–Performing–Adjourning) emphasizes that building trust is a fundamental prerequisite for effective team collaboration (Tuckman and Jensen 1977). Hogg and Terry (2000) studied the application of Social Identity Theory in teams and observed that shared experience improves members' feelings of belongingness to the team, and that these feelings expedite cooperation. Edmondson (1999) averred that psychological safety is the foundation of team cooperation and knowledge sharing and emphasized initial faith in the team as playing a pivotal role. Moreland and Levine (2002) studied how interactive activities in the course of the socialization of the team shape the building of role identity and collaboration norms. Dutton, Dukerich, and Harquail (1994) theorized that collective rituals, symbols, and ceremonies enhance members' organizational identification and willingness to collaborate by shaping a shared team image. Kozlowski and Bell (2003) systematically reviewed the interaction mechanisms in the early stages of team development, including the roles of fostering a supportive climate, sharing mental models and enhancing team cohesion in reducing members' sense of alienation and promoting the formation of common goals.

The above-mentioned research has demonstrated the positive effects of ice-breaking activities on knowledge sharing through mechanisms such as psychological safety, trust building, and the development of team norms. Pre-flight preparation is a required duty stage, as mandated by regulations, and is included in the crew's official duty time. Its primary tasks include assigning flight responsibilities, dividing roles, clarifying collaboration procedures such as air defense coordination, and developing contingency plans for potential operational difficulties. Although pre-flight preparation is a formal procedure, it shares characteristics with team ice-breaking activities by promoting mutual understanding and the rapid development of collaborative trust. Authorities and organisations often emphasize the completeness of pre-flight preparation steps and the inspection of individual task execution. However, the quality of interpersonal interaction during this stage is often overlooked. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 7: The interaction quality of pre-flight preparation positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

2.5 Summary of this Chapter

This chapter discussed the main variables involved in this study. First, the definitions of key concepts such as knowledge sharing were reviewed, and the specific definitions adopted in this study were clarified, particularly those referring to the broad understanding of knowledge and knowledge sharing. Second, the core variables and corresponding measurement methods were outlined. Scales that are widely used, highly reliable, and aligned with China's national context were considered. Third, relevant literature was reviewed and summarized. For the dependent variable (knowledge sharing behaviour), its antecedents were analyzed, with a focus on theories such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), personality trait theory, the

Situation Strength Theory (SST), and trait activation theory. Finally, it presents 7 research hypotheses for this study.

As for the definition of knowledge sharing, this study follows the definition proposed by Wang and Noe (2010), which refers to the exchange of work-related information, ideas, suggestions, and skills in a way that collaboratively improves the team's work capability.

Existing literature has examined the influence of technical, organisational, team, and personal factors on knowledge sharing. There is also increasing evidence that knowledge sharing intention is closely related to employees' sense of achievement. However, few studies have focused on temporary teams, where team composition frequently changes. Compared with previous studies, this research introduces new moderating variables related to temporary teams, aiming to fill an existing gap.

Current research on employee knowledge sharing can be divided into two levels: the organisational level and the individual level. In terms of research paradigms, it is generally classified into the technology-centered paradigm and the human-centered paradigm. The human-centered paradigm includes three main perspectives: the market perspective, the power perspective, and the social psychological perspective.

This research focuses on knowledge sharing among members of temporary cabin teams. Primarily it is an individual-level study, but also controls for the impact of factors at the team and organisational levels. Based on trait theory and trait activation theory, the present study investigates the effect of individual conscientiousness traits for the case of temporary teams and how team-level factors such as familiarity and organisational-level factors such as organisational fairness climate and other pertinent attributes shape it. The relevant research methods, findings, improved practices, conclusions and discussions will be presented in the following chapters.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction to Research Methods

The literature review in the previous chapter highlighted the critical role of knowledge sharing in the survival and development of organisations, as well as in their participation in market competition. For temporary teams, however, this presents unique challenges. Therefore, this research is considered innovative, as it focuses on cabin temporary teams characterized by non-knowledge-based work, extremely short life cycles, and highly homogeneous knowledge—areas that have received little attention in previous studies. This study emphasizes key variables such as team member familiarity and the quality of interaction during the pre-flight preparation.

In this chapter, the research methods are discussed in detail, and the basic logic of the research design is explained. Section 3.2 reviews the research philosophy and paradigm adopted in this study. Section 3.3 outlines the criteria and methods used for recruiting participants. Section 3.4 introduces the technical details of data collection through semi-structured interviews and online questionnaires. Section 3.5 describes the implementation of the pilot study. Section 3.6 provides a detailed explanation of the criteria used to ensure the rigor of this research. Section 3.7 explains how the study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards. The challenges encountered during the main research process are discussed in Section 3.8. Section 3.9 presents the methods of data collection. Section 3.10 outlines the procedures and details of data processing. Section 3.11 introduces the methods used for data analysis. Finally, Section 3.12 summarizes the research methods employed in this study.

Before the full-scale research was conducted, a pilot study was carried out with ethical approval (GUEP 2024 15531 14212). This pilot study served to review, test, and refine the research methods and protocols.

Given the practical issues that the cabin work teams encounter in airlines, the current research relies on prior studies in the area of knowledge management and temporary teams in order to explain its research approach. However, most of the previous research efforts have concentrated on temporary teams in engineering and construction projects (Anumba et al. 2005, p.1), temporary teams in the movie and television industry with high technical specialisation (Bechky 2006), temporary teams for the purposes of new product development (Edmondson and Nembhard 2009), or relatively stable temporary teams in the sphere of healthcare (Ahmadpour et al. 2023). Meanwhile, there have been fewer attempts at investigating temporary teams such as cabin crews that function for a brief period of time, possess little mutual acquaintance, and have the same professional skills.

3.2 Research Philosophy and Paradigm

The research paradigm is manifested in four philosophical dimensions: ontology, epistemology, methodology, and axiology (Grix 2002; Saunders et al. 2016). Ontology is “concerned with the nature of social reality” and “make claims about what kinds of social phenomena do or can exist, the conditions of their existence, and the ways in which they are related” (Blaikie 2010, p. 92). Epistemology, one of the core branches of philosophy, is concerned with the theory of knowledge, especially regarding its methods, validation, and “what kinds of knowledge are possible – how we can know these things – and with criteria for deciding when knowledge is both adequate and legitimate” (Blaikie 2010, p. 92). In short, it involves claims about “how what is assumed to exist can be known.”

There are four commonly recognized research paradigms: positivism (also known as “naive realism”), post-positivism (sometimes specifically referring to its important branch “critical realism”), constructivism (also known as “interpretivism”), and pragmatism (Hallebone and Priest 2008). Objectivism asserts that “social phenomena and their meanings exist independently of social actors.” In contrast, constructivism holds that “social phenomena and their meanings are constantly accomplished by social actors.” This implies that “social phenomena and categories are not only produced through social interaction, but that they are in a state of constant revision” (Bryman 2016, p. 29).

Positivists approach facts through the processes of hypothesis formulation, derivation, experimentation, data analysis, induction, and the generalization of phenomena. The underlying logic is that knowing enables prediction, and prediction enables control. Broadly speaking, positivism “is an epistemological position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond.” Positivism typically employs quantitative methods and aims to verify or refute hypotheses and propositions. A large amount of data is required to ensure that the research results are statistically significant. In addition, the adoption of positivism provides researchers with credibility through the use of statistical techniques (Guba and Lincoln 1994).

Post-positivism is a critical inheritance and revision of classical positivism. It retains the core belief that there exists an objective reality, but acknowledges that as human researchers, we cannot fully and objectively understand this reality. Blaike (2010, p.101) noted, “reality consists not only of events that are experienced but also of events that occur whether experienced or not, and of the structures and mechanisms that produce these events.” He also believed that, “inaccessible mechanisms require the building of hypothetical models of them and a search for evidence of their existence.” In the post-positivist paradigm, qualitative research no longer aims at

subjective “meaning”, but rather seeks to describe and explain the objectively existing reality more comprehensively, deeply, and rigorously.

The researcher believes that the world exists objectively. Behaviours such as knowledge sharing, organisational atmosphere, and employee familiarity are observable phenomena. In order to understand and identify the rules that govern this process, researchers should rely on observation and measurement. Knowledge sharing behaviour is a type of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), and like natural phenomena, it follows objective patterns that are not influenced by human will or interpretation.

The empirical approach primarily involves formulating a series of hypotheses and testing the relationships between variables. This study adopts a post-positivist empirical method grounded in critical and modified objectivist ontology and employs quantitative research techniques. It examines the main factors influencing knowledge-sharing behaviour, explores the mediating role of sharing intention, and investigates the moderating effects of perceived risk, familiarity, interaction quality, and organisational fairness atmosphere. A set of standardized research procedures and operational techniques was applied throughout the project. These included the selection of participants, control of irrelevant variables, development and use of survey or measurement tools, statistical analysis of data, and interpretation of the results.

The researcher adheres to a critical and hypothetical conception of knowledge and maintain value neutrality. This research was grounded in the actual conditions of enterprises. To gain a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of the knowledge-sharing practices and challenges faced by temporary teams, the use of questionnaires with pre-set items alone was not sufficient. Therefore, interviews were conducted to obtain richer, more personalized, and context-specific data.

3.3 Research Participants

Respondents were selected from Cabin Service and Security Departments of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd. Purposeful sampling method was used where respondents were selected from various technical ranks (junior, intermediate, and senior), as well as various roles such as frontline crew members, supervisors, and instructors. The reason for using such sampling method is not representativeness but rather having a wide array of views and opinions. Besides, respondents were also diverse in terms of age, level of education, and service tenure.

Limitations of this sampling technique must be discussed. It is important to note that sampling was conducted from one organisation only, making it difficult to generalise the results to other organisations, including those operating in other sectors apart from aviation. Moreover, the voluntary nature of participation might lead to the occurrence of self-selection bias where participants who had strong opinions on knowledge sharing would feel inclined to participate. These limitations will be discussed in Section 6.4. This sampling method enabled the elimination of bias and provided insights into employees' intentions and perceptions at all organisational levels.

The sample consisted of all cabin crew staff employed by Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd. within the time frame of the study (April-May 2025). As stated in the company's reports, there were roughly 1,200 people who were cabin crew staff, out of which 658 people returned valid questionnaires. While this can be considered an encouraging response rate (roughly 55%), it does not necessarily mean that the results obtained in the survey are generalizable to the larger group of cabin crew staff in China's aviation industry.

To recruit participants, the researcher used two methods.

The first method relied on the researcher's professional network within the company. Participants were recruited through contacts that the researcher had established during his work in the organisation. This network included a broad range of aviation personnel who were invited to join the study. They were contacted by email, phone, and face-to-face communication, and were informed about the purpose and procedures of the research.

After the initial contact, the researcher provided detailed information to the potential participants. This document contained details about the research, its objectives, and what their participation would involve. By leveraging established relationships, the researcher aimed to recruit a diverse group of participants. The topic was not considered sensitive by the company, and the researcher obtained permission from the organisation.

A stratified sampling method was employed in the process. In order to ensure that there was a representation of diversity based on the technical and organizational hierarchy, the participants were specifically chosen according to their technical level and whether they were in supervisory positions or not. The purposeful selection of respondents is aimed at reflecting the diversity among the cabin crew members.

The researcher conducted semi-structured face-to-face interviews with 17 participants. All of them shared their personal views on knowledge sharing and their experiences of daily work. Stratified sampling was adopted to ensure representativeness. During the questionnaire survey stage, because of its large scale, an online method was used to improve efficiency. In total, 658 participants provided valid and matchable responses. Finally, in the improvement practice stage, the researchers conducted a questionnaire survey among 56 new employees again to verify the effectiveness of the improved knowledge sharing program.

3.4 Research Design

This study involved participation from enterprise workers who grouped themselves into temporary cabin crews. The selection criteria were set up to ensure the inclusion of pilots of various skills and familiarity. The sample used ensured that it covered the whole population of cabin crew members by having people at varying technical levels (junior, intermediate, and senior), as well as of various roles (frontline crew, supervisor, and instructors).

3.4.1 The Adoption of Mixed Research Methods

Table 9 Overview of Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods with Justifications and Supporting Literature

Dimension	Qualitative Analysis	Quantitative Analysis	Mixed Methods
Core purpose	To explore perceptions, experiences, and context-specific meanings of knowledge sharing among temporary cabin crews.	To test hypothesized relationships between personality, situational factors, and knowledge-sharing intention.	To integrate contextual depth and statistical generalizability for a more comprehensive explanation.
Key procedures	Semi-structured interviews → Transcription → Open / axial coding → Thematic analysis → Triangulation	Questionnaire design → Large-sample data collection → Reliability & validity tests → Hierarchical regression → Moderation analysis	Sequential explanatory design: qualitative first to identify themes, then quantitative to test generalizability; joint display for integration.
Supporting literature for	Corbin and Strauss (2015); Braun and	Hair et al. (2010); Tabachnick and Fidell	Creswell and Clark (2011); Teddlie and

Dimension	Qualitative Analysis	Quantitative Analysis	Mixed Methods
methods	Clarke (2006); Miles et al. (2020); Creswell and Poth (2018)	(2013); Cohen et al. (2003); Aiken and West (1991)	Tashakkori (2009); Ivankova et al. (2006); Sale et al. (2002)
Critical reflections & value	Strength: rich insider understanding; captures tacit knowledge and context. Limitation: hard to generalize.	Strength: high replicability and generalizability; enables hypothesis testing. Limitation: less sensitive to context.	Strength: offsets individual weaknesses of mono-methods. Limitation: time-consuming and methodologically demanding.
Justification for choice	Suitable for exploratory research on understudied temporary teams in aviation.	Suitable for testing established theoretical models with large samples.	Necessary for a holistic understanding of knowledge-sharing mechanisms in complex operational settings.

In the field of knowledge sharing, survey research has been widely applied. For instance, as discussed in the literature review of this dissertation, McLure Wasko and Faraj (2000) collected responses from 342 participants to open-ended questions about why individuals participate and help others in online communities. Vuori and Okkonen (2012) examined the intentions, barriers, and differences between general knowledge-sharing incentives and employees' use of internal social media through three survey questions, using descriptive statistics. Bakker et al. (2006) conducted a survey to investigate whether trust could explain knowledge-sharing relationships in new product development projects or whether other factors played a stronger role. Their study covered 23 teams and 91 members, and the findings showed that team member identity had the greatest impact on the density of knowledge-sharing relationships.

This dissertation was oriented toward improving practice and therefore sought to start from real problems and address them systematically. A purely quantitative analysis to verify relationships among variables would not have been sufficient to support a practical improvement plan. For this reason, qualitative research was incorporated to capture details expressed in the richer and more vivid language of respondents, enabling the design of a more systematic and comprehensive solution. Consequently, this study adopted a mixed-methods approach that combined qualitative and quantitative techniques. In the first stage of the research, interviews were conducted with cabin crew members and aviation security officers, since intention and willingness to share knowledge originate from individual cognition. Using coding analysis, the respondents' views on knowledge-sharing behaviours and influencing factors in temporary teams were refined and then compared with existing research results. Through this process, the meanings expressed by respondents were identified, differences from fixed teams were recognized, key variables were discovered, and logical relationships were constructed. These findings were then combined with results from prior studies to guide empirical research. The decision to conduct interviews was based on the complexity of respondents' thoughts, consciousness, and motives, which required comprehensive and multi-angle exploration.

In the literature reviewed in Chapter Two, quantitative methods using standardized scales to collect data and test hypotheses were commonly applied to studies of knowledge sharing at both organisational and individual levels. For example, Gong et al. (2012) matched 190 employee–manager pairs from a chain store, together with 375 additional employees, and showed that proactive employees engaged in more information exchange, thereby strengthening trust relationships with supervisors and colleagues. Hendriks (1999) confirmed that “information and communication technology (ICT) promotes knowledge sharing by reducing temporal and spatial barriers among knowledge workers and improving access to relevant knowledge.” Peng and Pierce (2015) conducted a regression analysis of time-series survey data

from 158 Chinese participants to test their hypothesized relationships. Their results indicated that work-based psychological ownership mediated the link between experienced job control and organisation-based psychological ownership. Moon et al. (2008) found that the other-oriented trait of “responsibility” was positively correlated with proactive behaviour, whereas the self-oriented trait of “achievement striving” was negatively correlated with proactive behaviour. Similarly, dutifulness and achievement striving were distinguished from one another by Chae et al. (2019) and conceptualized to have positive and negative associations with knowledge sharing behaviour, respectively. Overall, testing relationships among variables on a sample of the population has widely been utilized in literature and similarly used in the current work.

During the second stage, a quantitative research methodology was applied to test the hypotheses. Based on preliminary literature and interview findings, hypotheses were generated and tested for validity. The empirical analysis involved hypothesizing a limited number and testing relationships between inter-variables. Adoption of pre-existing scales for fixed teams would have excluded some key information and provided limited aid for hypothesizing. To address this, observations were also conducted, which enriched the study, generated richer data, and supported the subsequent hypotheses. Data for hypothesis testing were obtained from questionnaire items as well as observations, such as the quality of interaction during pre-flight preparations.

Regarding the timing and location of interviews and questionnaires, participants were allowed to choose a preferred setting where they felt comfortable and safe, such as a café, an unoccupied conference room, or a private space outside of working hours. Interviews and questionnaires were usually conducted after flights to help employees review the duty process. Through a series of measures, the researcher ensured the smooth implementation of the mixed-methods approach. This approach provided new

perspectives and valuable data, allowing for a more comprehensive and multi-angle understanding of the research topic.

3.4.2 Qualitative Research: Interview

Semi-structured interviewing was selected as the principal qualitative approach due to its adaptability in addressing emerging themes while retaining standardization throughout the study (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009, pp. 123-126). Semi-structured interviews are also ideal when exploring subjective interpretations of workplace events and phenomena (King and Horrocks, 2010, pp. 1-5).

Interviews that can be described as semi-structured were done with 17 cabin crew members comprising cabin attendants and aviation security officers, who had different levels of technical expertise and experience working as flight attendants. Preliminary statistical analysis was used to bring together the views of the interviewees about the issue of knowledge sharing. At the stage when ways of enhancing knowledge sharing among employees were being investigated, follow-up interviews were done.

The data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis based on the method described by Braun and Clarke (2006). The methodology consists of six steps: familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing, defining, and writing up the results. NVivo 14 software was used to assist in the process of coding and developing themes; this software is often used in qualitative studies in business due to its capability of handling rich text data (Bazeley and Jackson 2013).

The interviews were semi-structured, which allowed the researcher some flexibility in guiding the discussion. Through these interviews, the influencing factors of knowledge-sharing intention were preliminarily examined. The research conducted

interviews with 17 employees of a mid-sized airline who worked in the cabin, in order to explore their concerns and perspectives. The participants represented different organisational levels. Many participants initially had a narrow understanding of knowledge, often limiting it to textbook concepts or examination points. As a result, knowledge sharing was sometimes misunderstood as the simple communication of such points. The researcher spent time explaining that knowledge also included rules, experiences, tips for accomplishing tasks, long-formed judgments, and operational principles. Through these interviews, the researcher gained a clearer understanding of the interviewees' intentions and ideas.

Through the interview method, the extent to which familiarity and different skill levels shaped the intention and behaviour of knowledge sharing was preliminarily examined. This process aimed to understand changes in employees' willingness to share knowledge and to identify the reasons behind such changes. The researcher asked participants to describe their perceptions and intentions at different levels of familiarity and skill, which could not have been easily captured through questionnaires alone. The researcher chose NVivo 14 for qualitative analysis. The respondents' statements were coded and analyzed systematically.

The reason qualitative research was adopted in this study was that it provided access to the meanings conveyed in respondents' discourse, revealed their genuine thoughts, and helped deepen the researcher's understanding of the variables while contributing to the development of a theoretical framework. If the study had relied only on empirical methods and converted the feelings, intentions, and attitudes of the respondents into variables on a scale, much information would have been lost. In particular, since this study focused on cabin work teams with their own distinct characteristics, it was necessary to identify differences from other types of teams, such as fixed teams, engineering and technical temporary teams, and temporary teams with longer life cycles. This process was useful for discovering and extracting new

variables. Therefore, through interviews, the study aimed to explore respondents' true thoughts and meanings in depth and to uncover subtle clues and patterns that might otherwise have been overlooked. This helped generate and refine hypotheses and also supported the identification and resolution of practical problems related to knowledge sharing. Subsequently, the questionnaire survey was used to identify and test the relationships among the variables.

Conducting qualitative research aimed to provide a deeper understanding of employees' knowledge-sharing behaviours, intentions, and influencing factors, while also obtaining richer background information and more profound insights. This study conducted interviews with 17 cabin crew members, including cabin attendants and aviation security officers from different technical grades and positions, in order to identify preliminary characteristics and patterns. This composition was consistent with the actual personnel structure in the flight production process. The researcher considered that theoretical saturation had been reached.

Table 10 Sample Composition

Gender And Rank	Junior	Intermediate	Senior	Chief Flight Attendant or Instructor	Leadership Position	Total
Male	0	2	2	3	1	8
Female	3	2	1	1	2	9
Total	3	4	3	4	3	17

During the interviews, since the participants were not knowledge-intensive employees and might not have been fully aware of existing knowledge-sharing practices, an introduction to knowledge sharing was given to facilitate open discussion. To minimize bias, leading questions were avoided, but prompts were used when necessary to encourage elaboration. The open-ended questions covered: 1) personal details (such as work experience, flight hours, and technical grade); 2) self-identified

factors influencing knowledge sharing; and 3) additional sharing factors prompted by the researcher to supplement responses.

Participants were recruited through formal channels using consent forms and information sheets. To ensure research credibility, cross-validation was applied, and follow-up clarifications were conducted during the coding process. Furthermore, during the practical stage of improving employees' knowledge sharing, additional interviews were conducted, supplemented by quantitative scoring from the respondents. These measures aimed to assess employees' satisfaction with the improvements, as well as the extent of change in their willingness and intention to share knowledge. The results were expected to provide a basis for further research and practice in the future.

More advanced qualitative and preference-elicitation approaches, such as vignettes and questions framed around the average employee, are recognised as sophisticated methods in contemporary research. These designs can help reduce response bias and elicit more context-dependent views. Although they offer finer-grained insights, the present study employed a well-established semi-structured interview design. This choice enabled in-depth, open-ended exploration of participants' real-world experiences while remaining feasible within the operational constraints of the research setting. Future research could integrate these more nuanced methods to further strengthen the elicitation of preferences and behavioural judgments.

3.4.3 Quantitative Research: Questionnaire and Observation

The empirical method was primarily applied to test the relationships among variables. Numerous established scales were available in the existing literature, covering knowledge sharing, team atmosphere, communication intensity, status competition,

threat perception, knowledge-sharing ability, and related constructs. These scales only required minor adaptation to fit the research context.

According to Hendriks (1999), knowledge-sharing actions can be divided into applying knowledge and co-creating knowledge. Depending on an enterprise's specific situation, explicit knowledge sharing may include work reports, manuals, and official documents. In the service industry, however, skills, experience, and judgment are of particular importance. This type of tacit knowledge is shared, exchanged, and enhanced through practice, especially during actual flight operations. Tacit knowledge sharing can also take the form of providing methodologies, models, tips, experience, know-how, know-whom, or expertise gained through education or training. This study referred to related literature, such as the knowledge-sharing scale developed by Bock (2005).

As the research was conducted in a specific enterprise, control variables such as team atmosphere, organisational values, and technical limitations that shaped knowledge sharing were included. According to Mohammed and Nadkarni (2011), gender and education level may affect employees' work attitudes and behaviours. Therefore, gender and education level were also taken as control variables in this study. In addition, the degree of familiarity and the quality of pre-flight coordination were emphasized. For the data collected from questionnaires and observations, the researcher conducted regression analysis using SPSS to examine the relationships among variables. To prevent data contamination, the questionnaire data of participants who had undergone interviews were removed from the database and were not included in the analysis and modeling. In total, 658 valid questionnaires were collected.

To capture real-time interaction and communication among temporary cabin crew teams, non-participant observation was adopted. The enterprise's pre-flight

preparation videos, which are primarily used to ensure the implementation of regulations, standards, and work quality, were retrieved for research purposes with the company's consent. A total of 200 morning departure flights from both the airline's headquarters and outstation base over a 15-day period were reviewed (15 flight videos were missing due to system issues), covering approximately 1,200 instances of crew pre-flight preparation. Audio and video data from the flight preparation rooms were collected via the pre-flight preparation monitoring system to observe interaction and communication among temporary team members, which were then coded and converted into research variables for analysis.

Quantitative data collected through questionnaires were utilized in analyzing item scores, creating statistical models, establishing correlations among variables, and testing the hypotheses proposed. A post-flight questionnaire study involving 1,200 people yielded 920 valid responses. The results obtained were then filtered through data matching and validation procedures in order to retain reliable and valid data sets amounting to 658 respondents (see Section 3.7).

The study used cross-sectional data, which are snapshots of relationships. While cross-sectional studies are adequate for examining associations among variables, they cannot provide information about cause-and-effect relationships. In fact, the significant positive correlation found between years of service and responsibility, explained in section 4.2.2, may be due to either the influence of years of service on responsibility or because more responsible workers tend to stay in the profession longer, as is often the case with reverse causality. If longitudinal data, which measure changes over time, were to be included, it would have been easy to determine the chronological order and thus distinguish the independent and dependent variables. This is one of the major limitations of this study (Angrist and Pischke 2009, pp.221-243).

3.5 Pilot Study

The pilot study was conducted to ensure the applicability of the research method.

Through the trial study, the following aspects were assessed:

- (a) The interviewees' understanding of the interview questions, that is, whether the questions were appropriate, understandable, and presented in a clear and consistent manner.
- (b) The validity of the interview questions, specifically whether the main research questions were effectively and accurately addressed.
- (c) The feasibility of conducting interviews using digital audio recordings and the accuracy of text transcription.
- (d) In addition to verifying the feasibility of the study, the pilot also helped the researcher enhance research skills and, to some extent, reduce potential bias and preconceived notions.

This pilot study was conducted in August 2024, and all offline on-site procedures were adopted:

- (a) Participants were authorized to arrange the interview time and location, choosing places where they felt most comfortable and confident.
- (b) Harmonious relationships were established with the participants, fostering a relaxed atmosphere and encouraging them to express themselves more freely in face-to-face interviews. This also helped reduce the researcher's anxiety.
- (c) During the interviews, the researcher listened carefully, noted important facts and information, avoided correcting participants' thoughts and feelings, shared personal ideas when appropriate, and raised guiding questions.
- (d) Reflection on the process generated new insights.

(e) Because the interviews were conducted in Chinese, the issue of scale translation was also considered.

A one-year interval between the pilot study and the formal research helped prevent bias and data contamination.

3.6 Criteria for Ensuring Research Rigour

Lincoln and Guba (1985) regarded trustworthiness as an important criterion for ensuring the rigor of research. Trustworthiness includes key dimensions such as validity and reliability.

As part of quantitative management research, measuring the reliability and validity of the scales being used is a fundamental step before conducting any test of hypotheses (Hair et al. 2010, pp.125-150; Nunnally and Bernstein 1994, pp.108-112). The former involves the degree to which the different items that have been created to measure the same variable consistently generate the same responses. On the other hand, the latter relates to the ability of the scale to measure what it is supposed to measure. Failure to determine the aforementioned qualities can render any conclusions about the relationship among the variables irrelevant. In this particular research, the reliability test conducted was Cronbach's α , where an α level of 0.70 or more is considered acceptable (Nunnally and Bernstein 1994, pp.108-112).

3.6.1 Validity

To ensure validity, this study emphasized coherence and repeatability of the research results in the following ways:

(a) Research participants were recruited using stratified sampling.

(b) Detailed on-site research agreements were established, and pilot studies were conducted.

(c) The interview questions were reviewed by an expert.

(d) Participants took part anonymously.

The convergent validity of the data was assessed by calculating the Corrected Item–Total Correlation Coefficient (CITC) for each measurement item, and all CITC values were above 0.5. Discriminant validity was examined through exploratory factor analysis. The main indicators used were KMO (greater than 0.7) and Bartlett’s test of sphericity, for which the significance value was required to be statistically significant.

3.6.2 Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of the measurement and data. Using the same measurement tool on the same object should yield consistent results (Shook et al. 2004). In Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), Cronbach’s α coefficient is commonly used to assess the internal consistency of questionnaire items. Since the data in this study were derived from the Likert scale, the reliability of the sample data was evaluated using Cronbach’s α coefficient. According to the evaluation criteria in the existing literature, a value of 0.5 was adopted as the acceptable threshold (Fornell and Larcker 1981).

3.7 Research Ethics

This study addressed ethical issues throughout both the pilot stage and the main research stage, following the guidelines of the University of Stirling and the GDPR. Prior to conducting field investigations, ethical approval was reviewed and granted by the General University Ethics Panel (GUEP). The researcher discussed with the supervisor the potential participants and data collection procedures to ensure that their

work was relevant to a data-driven approach and likely to provide rich and insightful data. Potential participants were then contacted informally.

Regarding the potential ethical risks involved in this project and the steps taken to mitigate them: As the researcher was a member of the management team of the enterprise under study, conducting this research might have caused suspicion or unease among participants and affected the authenticity of their statements. At the same time, the personal privacy of participants was fully protected, including their names, and care was taken to avoid the leakage or public disclosure of any relevant information. Measures were also taken to prevent others from inferring the identities of specific participants from the paper. The participants' right to take part voluntarily or to withdraw at any stage was guaranteed. Written approval was obtained for audio recordings. In addition, the safety of the researcher was also protected. The following steps were adopted to mitigate these risks.

Prior to undertaking research in the workplace, the researcher obtained permission from the senior member of staff. Participants were recruited from the enterprise through recruitment notices. The empirical research activities were conducted within the selected enterprises. A *Participant Information Sheet* and a *Participant Consent Form* were provided, emphasizing that participation in the research was voluntary and had no impact on work relations, performance evaluations, career advancement, or other employment-related decisions.

As a member of the management team, the researcher ensured that employees were free to decline participation. Employees were assured that the aim of the research was to seek truth rather than to obtain agreeable responses, and participants were encouraged to speak freely. If necessary, a screen was erected between the researcher and the participants. The researcher explained the purpose of the study, emphasized that there were no right or wrong answers, and reminded participants that the

interview would be recorded only with their consent. All interview materials were kept confidential.

Issue of Privacy: Some participants might have been apprehensive about potential violations of their privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity. To address these concerns, the researcher ensured compliance with GDPR guidelines to protect participants' privacy. Privacy was ensured by way of the consent form, and the provided data were utilized strictly for the purpose of research. The researcher also adopted more steps toward maintaining the privacy of participants. For instance, for the case of snowball sampling, participants were requested to share the contact information of the researcher by way of the *Participant Information Sheet* with colleagues who may become potential participants. In order to maintain privacy for such company-based research, various steps were adopted.

The information sheet was given to potential participants by colleagues who were interviewees. In case a colleague was interested in participating in the study, he or she would know how to locate the researcher. When they asked interview participants for information on colleagues participating, the researcher answered diligently that no such information was permitted to be shared. This process kept everyone from discovering who participated in the study and consequently kept every participant's confidentiality secure.

The questionnaire was developed in such a manner that irrelevant personal details, like names, private interests, or marital status, and any other detail involving immediate identification of participants, like specific job roles, were not used. The names of the participants and job roles were not shown, and codes or pen names were used instead of real names so that the participants stayed undisclosed. The identities of participants were kept confidential and not released to other participants in the course of the research, and details that would specifically reveal participants due to

the work they do were not included in published research, providing an additional layer of protection for privacy. Participants were provided codes so responses couldn't be linked to them, and signed permission for audio taping was obtained.

In order to ensure that the process of research did not involuntarily upset participants or place them under undue stress, a pilot study was conducted. The pilot study tried the questions and the process in order to determine the amount of time and to create a comfortable and supportive environment for the delivery of participants' narratives. To ensure that interviews were conducted in a safe environment, they were conducted in places familiar to participants, such as cafés or vacant conference rooms. The place was left to participants' discretion anywhere they felt safe and comfortable, and the date and time were set accordingly. Additionally, to ensure participants' well-being a further measure, they were provided with a safe word. The deployment of the word at any point of the interview would allow participants to suspend discussion, revoke their participation, or withdraw. By including these provisions, the use of which was entirely at participants' own discretion, the researcher hoped to produce a sensitive and respectful environment of consideration, mindful of the sensitive topic and aware of its probable emotional resonance. The right to withdraw from the project at any point was not merely restricted pre-participation but remained open to participants following participation in research activities. The enterprise was afforded the same assurance.

Safety of the Researcher: Ensuring the researcher's safety was essential. Although the subject of this study was neither highly sensitive nor overly personal, it did not rule out the possibility of individual sensitivity or emotional distress. The research process could also have led to emotional exhaustion or introduced bias on the part of the researcher. These risks were identified and mitigated, and the researcher strived to maintain the objectivity of the study.

Data were stored only on the researcher's personal laptop computer. The laptop was password-protected at both startup and within the project folder, and the password was not disclosed to others. There was no conflict of interest throughout the research. The company supported this doctoral project but did not provide funding, and it did not interfere with the research process or results. The study was considered to fall within the scope of academic research, and the rights of the researcher were protected. The company believed that this research could contribute to improving management and increasing employee satisfaction in the future. The research was based on the researcher's work but involved no conflict of interest. The potential risks described above were assessed as neither serious nor highly probable, and the overall assessment result was considered acceptable.

3.8 Challenges While Conducting the Study

The main challenge was the large scale of the respondent group. In the pilot study, due to its limited size, data collection was conducted entirely offline. However, the main study was much larger and covered the flight operation phase, involving more than 1,000 participants. Therefore, data collection in the main study was carried out through a combination of offline reminders and online completion. This created numerous difficulties in collecting data, matching personnel with flight numbers, and organizing the dataset. Based on the preliminary research findings, the questionnaire items were adjusted appropriately to facilitate better understanding.

The second difficulty was gaining the trust of respondents in order to obtain genuine data. During the interview stage, the researcher first contacted respondents through personal connections. Some participants contacted other potential participants on behalf of the researcher, while others recommended their colleagues. The researcher then followed up with these individuals by phone. In addition to these participants, the researcher also recruited respondents through publicly available staff information,

which included details such as department, name, and email address. The researcher then contacted them directly. Throughout the main research, ethics remained a priority. The researcher sought participants' permission and obtained their informed consent before conducting the study. Participants also retained the right to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason. During the questionnaire survey stage, the majority of respondents agreed to participate and completed the questionnaires.

3.9 Data Collection Methods

The data used in this research were collected by the researcher. The study controlled the surveyed subjects from four aspects. First, regarding industry limitations, airlines are labor-intensive enterprises within the traditional transportation sector. According to industry practice and the recommended human-machine ratio by the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC), the standard is 100:1. Labor costs accounted for a large proportion of company expenses, and to ensure safety and service quality, personnel were required to receive professional training and obtain qualifications. Second, at the enterprise and departmental level, employees of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd. were selected as the research subjects. The cabin work team came from the cabin service department and the security department, where their workspaces were the same and the nature of their work was similar. Third, in terms of education level, cabin crew and aviation security officers generally held junior college degrees, with a smaller number holding bachelor's degrees; therefore, the research subjects were not considered knowledge workers. Fourth, years of service were also taken into account.

The questionnaires employed in this research comprised several scales for each construct (refer to Appendix B). There were two questionnaires: Questionnaire 1 covered personal characteristics (Responsibility, Achievement Orientation, Risk

Perception, and Organisational Fairness Atmosphere), and Questionnaire 2 assessed Knowledge Sharing Intention and Knowledge Sharing Behaviour, which were answered after the flight.

Ordering of questions. The scales in Questionnaire 1 were arranged in the following sequence: Achievement Orientation, Responsibility, Knowledge Sharing Intention, Organisational Fairness Climate, and Risk Perception. The sequencing was not randomized. It is conceivable that by placing the achievement orientation scale and the responsibility scale early in the questionnaire, these scales may have inadvertently prompted participants to be more concerned with their individual motivations before responding to questions regarding organizational fairness or risk perception.

Nonetheless, since the concepts examined in the questionnaire are conceptually different (individual-level vs organization-level factors) and because the independent and dependent variables were separately measured using two different questionnaires (Questionnaire 1 and Questionnaire 2), there is a relatively low likelihood of common method variance due to question sequencing (Podsakoff et al. 2003). In addition, the acceptable results generated by the CFA analyses demonstrated that the impact of question sequencing on construct measurement was minimal.

In Questionnaire 2 (post-flight), items measuring Knowledge Sharing Intention were presented before items measuring Knowledge Sharing Behaviour. Similarly, items for each construct were grouped on the same page to minimise sequencing interference. This ordering was intentional, reflecting the theoretical assumption that intention precedes behaviour (Ajzen 1991). However, it is possible that asking about intentions first may have influenced subsequent reports of behaviour. Future research could improve upon this design by randomising the order of items or using counterbalancing techniques across participants (Tourangeau et al. 2000, pp.197-229).

Randomising the order of questionnaire items would have been a valuable design feature. It would have allowed the researcher to test whether responses were sensitive to item placement, for instance, whether asking about risk perception before or after responsibility changed the observed relationship between these variables.

Randomisation is particularly useful when constructs are conceptually related, as it helps to rule out the possibility that observed associations are artefacts of question order (Tourangeau et al. 2000, p35.). In this study, the fixed ordering was a limitation imposed by practical constraints (the questionnaires were administered via a digital platform that did not support randomisation). Future studies should consider implementing randomisation to strengthen the robustness of findings.

While more sophisticated methods, such as vignette-based experiments (Aguinis and Bradley 2014) or conjoint analysis (Hainmueller et al. 2014) are available for eliciting preferences and mitigating social desirability bias, the current study employed conventional Likert scales due to practical constraints (e.g., questionnaire length, respondent fatigue in a post-flight setting). Future research may adopt these advanced techniques to complement the findings presented here.

3.9.1 Data Collection Channels

This study mainly acquired data through observation, statistics, questionnaires, and interviews.

The first method was literature research. The researcher reviewed research achievements in the field of knowledge sharing in both international and Chinese contexts, identified theoretical gaps, proposed initial hypotheses, and built a theoretical framework.

The second method was observation. The researcher formulated a data collection plan based on the daily flight production plan of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd. The video monitoring system in the flight preparation room was used to record the pre-flight preparation status of each flight crew. The interactions, postures, and expressions of the crew were analyzed, and the quality of pre-flight preparations was graded and quantified. Video surveillance sites were classified as workplaces. Employees were required to accept surveillance as part of their duties, and they were informed in advance. In addition, the acquisition of research data was approved by the enterprise.

The third method was statistical analysis. The historical records of how often crew members were paired with each other, as documented in the Flight Operation Control System (FOC), were used to establish a model and assign values to their familiarity. The technical grade information of the crew members was directly retrieved from the FOC. The technical grade represented a comprehensive assessment made by the company, based on the duration of an employee's flight experience as well as their knowledge and skill level.

The fourth method was the questionnaire survey. Crew members' dutifulness, achievement striving, perceived organisational support, perceived fairness in the organisational atmosphere, and knowledge-sharing behaviour were measured using established scales. Questionnaires on knowledge-sharing intention, knowledge-sharing behaviour, perceived organisational support, and perceived fairness in the organisational atmosphere were distributed and collected after the completion of each flight mission. Data on dutifulness and achievement orientation were collected only once for each respondent. In addition, unique identifiers combining flight date, flight number, and crew member names were incorporated into the questionnaire forms to enable matching between pre-flight observation data and post-flight responses.

The fifth method was interview analysis, which was carried out in two stages. In the first stage, during theoretical construction, interviews were conducted with cabin staff, including flight attendants and aviation security officers, to support discourse analysis. In the second stage, during the improvement of enterprise practices, interviews were used to assess and understand the effects of enhancing knowledge sharing within temporary teams.

3.9.2 Source of the Scales

All measures used in the study had previously been developed based on existing tools which possessed sound psychometric properties. Measures were chosen based on two criteria. The first one involved use of scales which had been validated for organizational use or which had been back-translated in accordance with standardized procedures (Brislin 1986). Second, all the measures used had reliability greater than 0.70 measured as Cronbach's alpha (Nunnally and Bernstein 1994, pp.248-292).

RS and AO were quantified using the measures that had been developed by Chae et al. (2019). The differentiation between duty-oriented and achievement-oriented conscientiousness is crucial for investigating the hypotheses put forward in this study. KSI was quantified using the instrument devised by Bock et al. (2005) while KS was measured using the tool validated by Collins et al. (2006).

(a) Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO) in this study were measured using the *Dutifulness and Achievement Striving Scales* designed by Chae et al. (2019).

(b) Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) comes from the *Intention to Share Knowledge* of Bock (2005), National University of Singapore.

(c) Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS) comes from the scale of *Employee Knowledge Sharing Behaviour* by Collins (2006) et al., Cornell University.

(d) Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) was measured using scales adapted from Liao and Rupp (2005), Bock (2005), and Colquitt (2001). Three aspects were considered: procedural fairness, distributive fairness, and interactional fairness (Moorman, 1991). Four items were selected.

(e) Risk Perception (RP) scale in this study was modified from the *Perceived Cost of Sharing Knowledge* scale designed by Casimir et al. (2012), University of Newcastle. See Appendix B for details.

3.10 Data Processing

Based on the daily flight schedule, the researcher selected times that were convenient for cabin crew members to complete the questionnaire. To ensure data quality, questionnaires were not distributed after long or fatiguing flights or after flights completed late at night. Each cabin crew member on a daily flight was assigned a number. The coding rule combined the date, flight number, and crew members' names, for example: 20250415+GY7001.

The pre-flight preparation videos of the daily morning outbound flights at both the headquarters base and the external station base were combined with the post-flight questionnaires to collect data.

3.10.1 Data on the Quality of Interaction During the Pre-Flight Preparation

The researcher used Python to analyze the interactive emotions, interaction density, and information entropy captured in the pre-flight preparation videos and the corresponding spoken texts.

The pre-flight preparation interaction analysis adopted automatic text analysis methods. Transcriptions of speech content were done based on the videotapes of 200

pre-flight meetings. Three measures used for evaluating the quality of interactions include information entropy, interaction density, and interactive emotions.

Emotion interaction was evaluated through an emotion classifier that was pretrained via the Chinese sentiment analysis model using the BERT framework (Devlin et al. 2019). The specific model used for this purpose was from the Beijing Institute of Artificial Intelligence (Jiang 2023), which has been pretrained with a vast database of conversations in Chinese language and has an accuracy level of above 85%.

Sentiment analysis via automated tools is more reliable compared to manual methods due to its high degree of consistency and scalability (Grimmer and Stewart 2013).

Entropy was used as an indicator of lexical diversity, showing the sophistication of the communication process (Shannon 1948). A higher score for entropy means high diversity of the language, which is indicative of deep information exchange (Tausczik and Pennebaker 2010). Interaction density was defined as the number of utterances made during briefings, which is a commonly accepted behavioral measure of communication intensity in teams (Sacks et al. 1974).

3.10.1.1 Information Entropy

The measure of information entropy was employed in the evaluation of linguistic diversity within the pre-flight briefings. Information entropy is rooted in information theory (Shannon 1948) and has been widely used in organisational communication studies to represent the complexity and richness of communication among teams (Hickman et al. 2022). Entropy is higher when there is more linguistic diversity in a text, which means that more extensive exchanges have occurred (Pennebaker et al. 2003). The calculation of entropy for each pre-flight briefing was conducted in the current study.

An alternate method might involve the use of manual coding for the communication itself (such as task versus social communications). The drawback of manual coding is that it is time consuming and subject to rater bias (Grimmer and Stewart 2013).

Entropy analysis provides an automated means of calculating lexical richness, despite the fact that it does not capture semantics.

It was used as an indicator to measure the complexity of language expression.

Calculation Logic: Information Entropy was used as a statistical indicator to measure the diversity of text information. After tokenizing the text and removing stop words, the frequency of each word was calculated, and the overall level of language uncertainty was determined from the probability distribution. A higher entropy value indicated more dispersed word usage and therefore greater information complexity and expression diversity.

The formula for calculating information entropy was as follows:

$$H(X) = -\sum p(x) \cdot \log_2(p(x))$$

Here, $H(X)$ represented the information entropy of dataset X , and $p(x)$ represents the probability of a certain category x occurring in the dataset.

Theoretical Connotation: Information Entropy reflected the “content richness” and “complexity of expression” in language usage. In an interactive context, it was used to indicate whether a speech contained diverse information, whether it demonstrated strong logical coherence and content intensity, and it also reflected the cognitive depth of an individual’s expression.

3.10.1.2 Interactive Emotion

Sentiment analysis was applied to assess the emotionality of the language used during the pre-flight briefings. Sentiment analysis was performed using a Chinese pre-trained

sentiment classification model using BERT (Devlin et al. 2019). In particular, the sentiment classification model from the Beijing Institute of Artificial Intelligence (Jiang 2023) was used, which has been trained on a massive Chinese corpus of spoken conversations. Each utterance was assigned a label as positive, neutral, or negative with a corresponding probability score.

An automated sentiment analysis method was chosen over a manually coded one due to its increased reliability and scalability (Grimmer and Stewart 2013). However, it is crucial to keep in mind that sentiment analysis measures the expressed tone of emotion and not the emotion itself. Furthermore, the machine learning model has been trained on general Chinese language data and may lack some nuance of language used in aviation. In future studies, researchers may wish to further refine the sentiment analysis model using aviation-related texts.

It was used as an indicator to measure pragmatic emotional tendencies.

Computational Logic: Each round of speech was regarded as the basic unit. Using a pre-trained Chinese sentiment analysis model, the emotional attributes (such as positive or negative) of each speech were identified, and the intensity of these emotions was quantified. On this basis, the average positive emotional intensity, the average negative emotional intensity, and a comprehensive emotional tendency score were calculated.

Theoretical Underpinnings: Interactive Emotion reflected the emotional tone and attitudinal tendency in the communication process. High positive emotions usually indicated collaboration, identification, and support, whereas negative emotions could have implied disagreement, criticism, or tense situations. The comprehensive score generally reflected the degree of friendliness or conflict in the conversational atmosphere.

3.10.1.3 Interaction Density

The density of interactions was defined by counting the total number of speech turns for each pre-flight brief. This measure describes the frequency of communication encounters and has been applied to studies of team communication as an index of the density of interactions (Woolley et al. 2010). Speech turns were determined by changes of speakers within the transcripts.

A different way could be through the measurement of total time spent talking or coding for different kinds of interactions, such as asking questions vs. making statements. The reason for preferring the measure based on the number of turns was that it is simple and reliable.

It was a structural indicator that measured the degree of active communication.

Calculation Logic: Each speech was counted as one interaction round for statistical purposes. The total number of speech rounds in a text was calculated as a quantitative indicator to measure interaction density. Speech segments were usually identified based on discourse markers in the text structure, such as the word “speaker” or names that begin with specific letters.

Theoretical Underpinnings: Interaction Density reflected the level of activity and the rhythm of interaction in group communication. A greater number of interaction rounds indicated more frequent communication and more thorough interaction, suggesting a more active flow of information and a more responsive mechanism within the group. This indicator could represent group interaction characteristics in contexts such as meetings, collaborative discussions, and negotiation dialogues.

3.10.2 Limitations of Automated Text Analysis

The interaction quality factors consisting of information entropy, interactive emotion, and interaction density were computed per pre-flight briefings and then combined with the survey data based on flight numbers and dates. The interaction quality factors were included as moderators in the regressions presented in Section 4.3.2 (Path 2, Models 2 to 4). In particular, each factor served as a moderator (AO x interaction quality) to examine Hypothesis 7, suggesting that the quality of pre-flight preparations will strengthen the positive effect of AO on KSI.

The following limitations in relation to the automated text analysis techniques used in this study need to be recognized. First, the sentiment analysis algorithm is based on training data in the general Chinese language, which means that it might fail to identify domain-specific terms that might be used during communications in the aviation field. Second, the calculation of information entropy is an indicator of lexical diversity in the conversation but not of the accuracy or relevance of the information being communicated. Third, interaction density (turns) reflects the number of exchanges during the conversation but does not distinguish task-related from social communications. This needs to be considered when analyzing the insignificant results in Section 4.3.2.

3.10.3 Degree of Familiarity Value

This measure has been devised by adopting a weighted summation model that incorporates the prior collaborations both at the dyad as well as the group levels. This model draws its rationale from social network theory, which states that interaction between several actors leads to familiarity of the entire group rather than being limited to the sum total of the relationships between two people (Reagans and

McEvily 2003). The weights chosen ($\omega_2 < \omega_3 < \omega_4 < \omega_5$) are theoretically determined rather than empirically estimated.

However, certain limitations should not be overlooked when considering the proposed measure. Other methods, for example, those employing the number of collaborations without giving any weightings, or even applying measures like network density, would perhaps lead to somewhat different conclusions. The weighted measure has been used to incorporate various levels of team knowledge, although the weights involved are subjective in nature.

3.10.3.1 Quantitative Value

In this project, the “familiarity” variable was represented by the “number of collaborations”. The frequency of collaboration among personnel within a specific group of crew members over a defined period was recorded, including two-person, three-person, and four-person collaborations. The number of times that crew members in a particular cabin collaborated to execute flights within one year was also included. A familiarity score was calculated by summing the collaboration frequencies using weighted ratios. A higher score indicated greater familiarity among the cabin crew members.

Quantitative calculation: After the indicators were quantified, the familiarity scores of the crew members were calculated using a weighted summation method. Suppose the weights of the indicators $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n$ are $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n$, then the crew members' familiarity score $F = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \omega_i$.

Model Validation: Multiple groups of crew members were randomly selected as samples. The constructed model was applied to calculate their familiarity scores,

which were then compared with observed collaboration performance and the degree of close interpersonal relationships among the crew members.

Parameter Adjustment: Based on the verification results, parameters such as indicator weights and quantification methods in the model were adjusted and optimized to improve its accuracy and reliability. For example, if it was found that a greater number of crew members having worked together had a stronger impact on the familiarity score, the weight of this indicator was accordingly increased.

The following is an example of a model that incorporates multi-member collaboration into the familiarity calculation, along with the corresponding weight settings. These settings can be adjusted based on specific scenarios. Suppose the number of crew members is n (e.g., $n=5$), and the following factors are considered when calculating team familiarity. For example, if it is found that the number of crew members who have previously worked together significantly affects the familiarity score, the weight assigned to this indicator should be increased accordingly.

The cooperation situation between two individuals:

Define C_{2ij} as the number of times Member i and Member j ($i \neq j$) have cooperated.

The weight of the cooperation between the two individuals is set as ω_2 .

The contribution of familiarity of 2 persons is: $\sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} C_{2ij} \times \omega_2$

The cooperation situation among three individuals:

Define C_{3ijk} as the number of times Member i , Member j and Member k ($i \neq j \neq k$) have cooperated.

The weight of the cooperation between the three individuals is set as ω_3 .

The contribution of familiarity of 3 persons is: $\sum_{1 \leq i < j < k \leq n} C_{3ijk} \times \omega_3$

By following this pattern, the contribution of familiarity of 4 persons is:

$\sum_{1 \leq i < j < k < l \leq n} C_{4ijkl} \times \omega_4$

The contribution of familiarity of 5 persons is: $\sum_{1 \leq i < j < k < l < m \leq n} C_{5ijklm} \times \omega_5$

Based on all the above factors, the calculation formula for crew familiarity is as follows:

$$F = \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} C_{2ij} \times \omega_2 + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k \leq n} C_{3ijk} \times \omega_3 + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k < l \leq n} C_{4ijkl} \times \omega_4 + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k < l < m \leq n} C_{5ijklm} \times \omega_5$$

Weight assignment:

Generally speaking, the more people involved in the cooperation, the higher the overall familiarity among the crew members. Therefore, the weights can be set in an increasing order based on the number of participants, that is, $\omega_2 < \omega_3 < \omega_4 < \omega_5$. For example, suppose $\omega_2 = 0.1$, $\omega_3 = 0.2$, $\omega_4 = 0.3$, $\omega_5 = 0.4$. Setting the weights in this way means that the more people are involved in the cooperation, the greater the positive effect on the overall familiarity of the temporary team. The weights can also be adjusted according to the actual situation of the crew members, such as the nature of their tasks and the mobility of the members, to more accurately reflect the familiarity level among the crew.

3.10.3.2 Normalization Processing

The familiarity scores of the crew members were normalized. Normalization can accelerate the convergence of the optimization algorithm, as it brings the values of different feature dimensions to a similar scale, thereby improving the algorithm's efficiency in processing the data.

The minimum-maximum normalization (Min-Max Scaling) method was adopted.

This method scales all features in the original data to the range [0, 1], using the following formula:

$$F_{\text{norm}} = \frac{F - F_{\min}}{F_{\max} - F_{\min}}$$

3.10.3.3 Data set Processing

This study used a dataset containing nearly 75,000 data points collected between January 1, 2022, and May 2, 2025. During this period of approximately three and a half years, the number of crew members per flight was generally between 5 and 18, as shown in Figure 21. In the initial stage, the data were cleaned and preprocessed. Noisy data were removed, and only records involving security and cabin crew members were retained. Invalid flight records were also excluded. Figure 6 presents the flight statistics during the study period, showing the distribution of crew numbers per flight.

Figure 6 Flight Statistics from 2022 to 2025

Step 2: Based on the full dataset of 75,000 flight records, a subset of 857 flights from April 18, 2025, to May 2, 2025, was selected. The familiarity scores of the crew members for these 857 flights were calculated and then normalized. The results are presented in Figure 7.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
flight_id	flight_date	flight	depart	arrival	ac_type	ac_reg	name_json	userid_arr	name_arr	flight_c	route	source	机组编号	分数
21919B49D5E84	2025-04-18	GY7283	KWE	NGB	A320	B-329J	[{"userid": "16016024.16111.GYBWB022.GYKCB0", "name": "张森南, 邓国浪"}]				贵阳-宁波 FOC		74126	0.252
2087FCFA765F5	2025-04-18	GY7117	HYN	TFU	A320	B-327Q	[{"userid": "12912956.12977.16048.16143.GYK", "name": "赖红宇, 邹静"}]				台州-成都 FOC		74127	0.1232
2087FCFA78035	2025-04-18	GY7118	TFU	HYN	A320	B-321V	[{"userid": "12812881.16014.16019.16070.GYK", "name": "穆嘉子, 曹芸菲"}]				成都天府-FOC		74128	0.1850
2087FCFA7DCT5	2025-04-18	GY7253	YBP	ZUH	E190	B-3285	[{"userid": "16116172.GYBWB069.GYBWB084.GYK", "name": "杨东豪, 钟杰"}]				宜宾-珠海 FOC		74129	0.1087
2087FCFA7EB75	2025-04-18	GY7254	ZUH	YBP	E190	B-3285	[{"userid": "16116172.GYBWB069.GYBWB084.GYK", "name": "杨东豪, 钟杰"}]				珠海-宜宾 FOC		74130	0.1087
2087FCFA80DB5	2025-04-18	GY7282	ACX	KWE	E190	B-3320	[{"userid": "12712782.16029.GYBWB013.GYKCB0", "name": "胡茗捷, 雷沐翰"}]				兴义-贵阳 FOC		74131	0.1593
208902DC3C315	2025-04-18	GY7259	NGB	CKG	A320	B-32JF	[{"userid": "12912943.16017.16137.16163.GYK", "name": "马向前, 代亚灵"}]				宁波-重庆 FOC		74132	0.1208
208902DC3D215	2025-04-18	GY7260	CKG	NGB	A320	B-32JF	[{"userid": "12912943.16017.16137.16163.GYK", "name": "马向前, 代亚灵"}]				重庆-宁波 FOC		74133	0.1208
208943F269EF0	2025-04-18	GY7146	CZX	KWE	E190	B-3116	[{"userid": "12712782.16029.GYBWB061.GYKCB0", "name": "胡茗捷, 雷沐翰"}]				常州-贵阳 FOC		74134	0.1136
208943F26D530	2025-04-18	GY7247	KWE	YIW	A320	B-30DY	[{"userid": "12812885.12955.GYBWB037.GYKCB0", "name": "谢志瀚, 张良超"}]				贵阳-义乌 FOC		74135	0.3142
208943F26EF70	2025-04-18	GY7248	YIW	KWE	A320	B-329J	[{"userid": "12912988.16022.16130.GYBWB077", "name": "赵应芳, 罗国彬"}]				义乌-贵阳 FOC		74136	0.2326
2089A179F5E02	2025-04-18	GY7111	KWE	HGH	A320	B-326E	[{"userid": "12812870.16009.16016.16135.GYB", "name": "刘梅, 唐湘"}]				贵阳-杭州 FOC		74137	0.1404
2089A179FF4B0	2025-04-18	GY7112	HGH	KWE	A320	B-326E	[{"userid": "12812870.16009.16016.16135.GYB", "name": "刘梅, 唐湘"}]				杭州-贵阳 FOC		74138	0.1404
2089A17A03B02	2025-04-18	GY7113	KWE	HYN	A320	B-327Q	[{"userid": "12912956.12977.16048.16143.GYK", "name": "赖红宇, 邹静"}]				贵阳-台州 FOC		74139	0.1232
2089A17A03A30	2025-04-18	GY7185	YBP	FOC	E190	B-3285	[{"userid": "16016068.16086.GYKCB019.GYKCB0", "name": "王宇2, 何昕烽"}]				宜宾-贵阳 FOC		74140	0.1885
2089A17A05A02	2025-04-18	GY7231	YBP	TNA	E190	B-3241	[{"userid": "12812860.16054.16167.GYBWB072", "name": "胡瑞浩, 王青彩"}]				宜宾-济南 FOC		74141	0.1463
2089A17A074F0	2025-04-18	GY7232	TNA	YBP	E190	B-3241	[{"userid": "12812860.16054.16167.GYBWB072", "name": "胡瑞浩, 王青彩"}]				济南-宜宾 FOC		74142	0.1463
2089B7B3C09F2	2025-04-18	GY7108	FOC	YIC	E190	B-3285	[{"userid": "16016068.16086.GYKCB019.GYKCB0", "name": "王宇2, 何昕烽"}]				福州-宜春 FOC		74143	0.1885
2089B7B3C0A12	2025-04-18	GY7108	YIC	KWE	E190	B-3285	[{"userid": "16016068.16086.GYKCB019.GYKCB0", "name": "王宇2, 何昕烽"}]				宜春-贵阳 FOC		74144	0.1885
2089B7B3C10F2	2025-04-18	GY7207	ACX	LLB	E190	B-3242	[{"userid": "12712794.16173.GYBWB042.GYBWB0", "name": "张常彬, 郑嘉晨"}]				兴义-荔波 FOC		74145	0.2601
2089B7B3C1112	2025-04-18	GY7207	LLB	TEN	E190	B-3242	[{"userid": "12712794.16173.GYBWB042.GYBWB0", "name": "张常彬, 郑嘉晨"}]				荔波-铜仁 FOC		74146	0.2601
2089B5C9BA04	2025-04-18	GY7105	KWE	SYX	A320	B-320T	[{"userid": "12712756.12870.16009.16016.161", "name": "高子池, 刘梅"}]				贵阳-三亚 FOC		74147	0.1824
2089B5C9BB444	2025-04-18	GY7106	SYX	KWE	A320	B-327Q	[{"userid": "12712769.12873.12878.16018.GYK", "name": "刘兆远, 冉海"}]				三亚-贵阳 FOC		74148	0.1457
2089B5C9BC0C4	2025-04-18	GY7208	TEN	LLB	E190	B-3242	[{"userid": "12712794.16173.GYBWB042.GYBWB0", "name": "张常彬, 郑嘉晨"}]				铜仁-荔波 FOC		74149	0.2601
2089B5C9BC0C4	2025-04-18	GY7208	LLB	ACX	E190	B-3242	[{"userid": "12712794.16173.GYBWB042.GYBWB0", "name": "张常彬, 郑嘉晨"}]				荔波-兴义 FOC		74150	0.2601
2089CE2F302B4	2025-04-18	GY7121	KWE	HIA	A320	B-321V	[{"userid": "16016069.16139.GYKCB098.GYKCB2", "name": "于佳禾, 罗娅兰"}]				贵阳-淮安 FOC		74151	0.1359
2089CE2F302F4	2025-04-18	GY7121	HIA	TSN	A320	B-321V	[{"userid": "16016069.16139.GYKCB098.GYKCB2", "name": "于佳禾, 罗娅兰"}]				淮安-天津 FOC		74152	0.1359
2089CE2F320D4	2025-04-18	GY7122	TSN	HIA	A320	B-321V	[{"userid": "16016069.16139.GYKCB098.GYKCB2", "name": "于佳禾, 罗娅兰"}]				天津-淮安 FOC		74153	0.1359
2089CE2F320F4	2025-04-18	GY7122	HIA	KWE	A320	B-321V	[{"userid": "16016069.16139.GYKCB098.GYKCB2", "name": "于佳禾, 罗娅兰"}]				淮安-贵阳 FOC		74154	0.1359
2089CE2F3700	2025-04-18	GY7131	KWE	ACX	E190	B-3242	[{"userid": "12812848.12850.12985.GYKCB162", "name": "胡凌熙, 钟奇缘"}]				贵阳-兴义 FOC		74155	0.1818
2089CE2F36A54	2025-04-18	GY7205	TFU	DYG	A320	B-326Z	[{"userid": "12712759.12947.12985.GYKCB146", "name": "陈波, 孙高艾妮"}]				成都天府-FOC		74156	0.3095
2089CE2F36A74	2025-04-18	GY7205	DYG	HIA	A320	B-326Z	[{"userid": "12712759.12947.12985.GYKCB146", "name": "陈波, 孙高艾妮"}]				张家界-界 FOC		74157	0.3095

Figure 7 Crew Familiarity Score

Step 3: Visualization and Analysis of Results:

As shown in Figure 23, the familiarity scores were mostly concentrated between 0.1 and 0.6, indicating that the level of coordination among crew members was relatively low. This outcome reflects characteristics inherent to the aviation industry. For example, during crew scheduling, efforts are made to reduce the frequency of repeated collaborations among personnel to prevent the formation of close-knit subgroups, which could negatively affect overall team dynamics.

To enhance the interpretability of the results, the familiarity scores were transformed using a square root function. The processed data are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Familiarity Distribution and Kernel Density Estimation (After Processing)

Note: Kernel density estimation using Gaussian kernel with bandwidth selected by Silverman's rule of thumb.

3.10.3.4 Critical Discussion of the Familiarity Measure

This familiarity index has been created through a weighted summation method taking into consideration the prior collaborations both at the dyad level and at the level of teams. The weights for this ($\omega_2 < \omega_3 < \omega_4 < \omega_5$) were chosen due to theoretical considerations that teams having experienced collaboration with more people have a higher effect on their overall familiarity as compared to those with lower numbers – a theory-driven choice and not one based on estimation of results. This approach was chosen to capture the multi-level nature of team familiarity, which prior research has suggested may be more than the sum of pairwise ties (Reagans and McEvily 2003).

Alternative approaches. A number of other options could have been considered for measuring familiarity. One of these options was simply using dyadic familiarity based on the actual number of prior collaborations, without weighting according to the group's size. This method would have been much easier to implement and would not

have required any arbitrary weightings. Another option that could have been implemented would be network density measures – in particular, the ratio of actual vs. possible connections within a team (Wasserman and Faust 1994, pp. 100-104, 170-173). Finally, one could consider treating familiarity as a categorical construct, where familiarity levels such as “never flown together,” “flown together 1-5 times” and “flown together 6 or more times” would apply.

Rationale for the current approach. Two motivations were behind the choice of using the weighted index. First, the airline cabin crew setting was one where group tasks would need coordination of all team members (e.g., during emergencies). The use of the concept of group familiarity was thus theoretically justifiable. Second, the application of the weighted index facilitated testing the possibility that familiarity could function on a group level rather than a dyadic level alone. It should be noted, however, that there is no empirical basis for such an assumption of relative weight.

Potential limitations. It is worth noting that the weighted index can be considered “over-engineered” in that it takes several elements into account at once, thereby concealing some information that might otherwise have been captured had different or less sophisticated measurements been used, or had different types of familiarity included in the regression model (e.g., dyadic familiarity and group-level familiarity). In addition, the lack of significant associations found in Section 4.3.2 in Table 14 and Model 2 might simply be an artifact of the selected measurement, not a lack of association itself.

Implications for interpretation. However, because of the insignificance of the results, together with the possible flaws of the measure used, it is important to interpret the results concerning the effects of familiarity cautiously. The insignificance of the results does not imply that there is no relationship between knowledge sharing and interpersonal familiarity among temporary teams, but rather

could be due to the measure used or due to the nature of the field of civil aviation itself (as discussed in Section 6.2).

3.11 Data Analysis Techniques

This study aimed to explore the relationship between temporary team members' sense of responsibility, team characteristics, and individual intention and behaviour related to knowledge sharing.

The pilot study followed procedures and methods similar to those of the formal study and produced satisfactory results in August 2024. Its primary purpose was to evaluate the effectiveness of the semi-structured interview format and the appropriateness of the interview question list, assess the reliability and validity of the data, and conduct a preliminary test of the research hypotheses using the scale data. At this stage, particular attention was given to ensuring that the interview questions were easy to understand so that participants could provide in-depth and meaningful responses. Additionally, the applicability and validity of the scale, the accuracy of its Chinese–English translation, and participants' comprehension of the questionnaire items were preliminarily evaluated.

The survey was conducted in the context of daily operations in 2025. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 17 participants, and questionnaires were distributed to 1,200 individuals.

The interview questions explored whether variations in mutual familiarity, perceived organisational support, perceived fairness within the organisational environment, and technical competence had a significant impact on business communication and knowledge sharing. Specifically, the questions examined whether these factors enhanced participants' sense of responsibility and achievement, or reduced

communication-related risks such as misunderstanding, lack of cooperation, or interpersonal tension. The interview data were analyzed using NVivo to identify key themes and patterns.

The empirical method was primarily used to develop hypotheses and examine the relationships among variables, with adjustments made based on the specific research context. Tacit and explicit knowledge were analyzed separately. As the study was conducted in a specific enterprise, control factors such as team environment, organisational culture, and technical constraints of knowledge transfer were considered. Observation and questionnaire data were analyzed in SPSS using regression analysis for analyzing the correlation and influence of such factors.

The participants provided informed consent in person prior to joining in the study. The participants were made aware that participation was voluntary and at any given time they were free to drop from the study without explanation and without suffering any negative consequences. The study remained strictly ethical and the privacy and confidentiality of every participant were ensured. The participants received an information sheet and a consent form outlining the purpose of the study, procedures, and confidentiality measures prior to interview and questionnaire distribution. Participants were not required to answer any questions they were uncomfortable with, and care was taken to ensure that no psychological or professional harm occurred. The research did not disclose participants' personal information or opinions, nor did it investigate any proprietary business information. The initial theoretical framework guiding the qualitative phase is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Initial Theoretical Framework

According to the convention in management studies (Becker 2005), regression models considered demographic factors (gender, age, and education) as control variables. It should be noted that these control variables, especially education, may themselves correlate with knowledge-sharing behavior. From the econometrics perspective, such control variables can be called “bad controls” when they become the outcomes of independent variables (Angrist and Pischke 2009, pp.64-68). As a way of addressing the issue, the analyses were repeated without using control variables, and there was no essential difference in the findings. Still, the use of education as a control variable calls for some reservation.

3.12 Summary of This Chapter

This chapter provided a detailed overview of the methodological components applied in the research process. It covered the research paradigm, research strategies, pilot study, encountered challenges, data collection methods, data analysis techniques, strategies for ensuring research rigor, and ethical considerations.

The following chapters will present the research findings and improved practices, discussion, and future directions.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1 Preface to This Chapter

The cabin temporary team is different from fixed teams and long-term temporary teams, such as film crews and technical breakthrough teams. Its characteristics—temporariness, homogeneity of members' technical backgrounds, hierarchical technical levels, and a short life cycle—are more pronounced. Meanwhile, unlike medical surgical teams (Ahmadpour et al. 2023), they have a lower degree of mutual familiarity and are not knowledge-based personnel.

The characteristics of the cabin temporary team are directly reflected in the following aspects. First, the level of familiarity among team members varies; some have worked together before, while others have not. Second, the members' technical proficiency differs. The team includes leaders with higher technical skills, along with other members holding junior, intermediate, or senior technical titles. These are explicit and observable features. In addition, there are implicit factors such as perceived organisational support and the sense of fairness within the team. These are subjective experiences with complex internal mechanisms. Clearly, individual perceptions—including judgment, intuition, and emotional response—play a critical role in shaping members' motives, attitudes, and intentions. Therefore, this study considers not only explicit factors such as technical grades and the degree of mutual familiarity, but also individual perception factors such as the perceived fairness of the team environment.

In the first stage of the interviews, respondents reported that their main motivations for knowledge sharing included self-initiative, achieving collective success, helping others, and meeting work-related requirements. These intentions are closely aligned with responsibility-related theories of knowledge sharing and personality traits. Some

participants also indicated a positive correlation between mutual familiarity and knowledge-sharing intention. They generally believed that individuals with similar technical levels communicate more effectively and are less likely to withhold information. Due to long-term exposure to regulatory management practices in the industry, respondents commonly viewed pre-flight preparation as a critical phase. Some also saw it as an opportunity to improve mutual understanding and build collaborative trust. The insights obtained from these interviews offer meaningful guidance for the researcher.

Combined with relevant literature, the following hypotheses regarding the influencing factors of knowledge sharing in temporary teams are initially proposed and tested.

How does the level of Familiarity (FA) affect the Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour (KS) of temporary team members?

How do social interaction and openness during the pre-flight preparation stage affect the knowledge-Sharing Behaviour (KS) of temporary team members?

How does the Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) affect the knowledge-sharing Behaviour (KS) of temporary team members?

How does Risk Perception (RP) affect the Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour (KS) of temporary team members?

4.2 The Qualitative Analysis Finding

Following qualitative methods, 17 flight attendants and security officers were interviewed. NVivo analysis produced 25 initial codes, which were consolidated into five categories: pre-flight preparation, on-duty sharing, intentions, situational factors, and team structure. Demographic data included participants' experience, profession, grade, and gender. Theoretical saturation was considered reached when no new themes or insights emerged from the data.

4.2.1 Overall Analysis of The Interview

Table 11 Code List

Level 3 Code	Level 2 Code	Level 1 Code
1 pre-flight stage	1-1 program collaboration	
	1-2 work reminder	
	1-3 ice-breaking ceremony	
	1-4 greetings	
	1-5 interaction	
	1-6 membership information	
2 knowledge sharing on duty	2-1 sharing methods	
	2-10 review and analysis	
	2-2 flight information	
	2-3 collaboration onboard	
	2-4 regulations and standards	
	2-5 work trend	
	2-6 skill demonstration	
	2-7 experience	
	2-8 emergency disposal	
2-9 case discuss		
3 knowledge sharing intention	3-1 job demand	
	3-2 push oneself	
	3-3 achievability	
	3-4 expected feedback	
	3-5 satisfaction	
	3-6 altruism	
4 situational factors	4-1 risk perception	4-1-1 worries about mistakes and misunderstandings
		4-1-2 worried about potential impact
		4-1-3 no worry
		4-1-4 unable to empathize
	4-2 unfavorable feedback	
	4-3 team atmosphere	
	4-4 work and time pressure	
	4-5-member familiarity level	
5 team structure factors	5-1 technical grade factor	5-1-1 technical level difference
		5-1-2 same technical level
	5-2 mood	5-2-1 mood does not affect

Level 3 Code	Level 2 Code	Level 1 Code
		5-2-2 mood affects work
		5-2-3 mood partly affects work
	5-3 member's personality	
	5-4 leading role of chief	

Regarding the definition of knowledge, the respondents—particularly those with higher technical grades and leadership roles—demonstrated a relatively clear understanding. Interviewee No. 16 (the chief cabin attendant) noted that knowledge can be divided into two categories: one is written or theoretical knowledge used for understanding and learning; the other is practical experience transformed into written form. This reflects his awareness of the distinction between explicit and tacit knowledge. He also emphasized the importance of transforming knowledge into skills and refining tacit knowledge into explicit forms. Interviewee No. 15 (a department manager) highlighted that summarizing industry cases and experiences serves as an important source of new knowledge. Interviewee No. 12, a senior instructor for aviation security officers, believed that knowledge could be transformed into fundamental qualities and abilities. Overall, the respondents held a broad definition of knowledge and generally believed that anything applicable to their work could be regarded as knowledge. According to word frequency analysis, the most frequently mentioned words included “flight,” “knowledge,” “communication,” “content,” “events,” “need,” “information,” “procedures” ... The word cloud is shown in figure 10.

Figure 11 A Tree Diagram About “Experience”

With “manual” as the keyword, the tree diagram is shown. With “manual” as the keyword, the tree diagram is shown in Figure 12. Respondents considered manuals to be a form of explicit knowledge, serving as a systematic and theoretical summary. Due to long-term acceptance of industry regulations and the concept of being a “manual-based” employee, all respondents clearly stated that when standards or procedures are unclear, they do not rely on memory or recitation but instead consult the manual. When team members have differing views, decisions are also made in accordance with the manual’s provisions.

Figure 12 The Tree Diagram about the Manual

4.2.2 The Association Between Intention and Knowledge Sharing

In terms of intentions to share knowledge, respondents commonly mentioned factors such as a feeling of obligation, personal accomplishment, work necessities, and the desire to assist others. This implies that in the case of the studied cabin crew, the willingness to engage in knowledge sharing can stem from various motives encompassing basic work duties and self-fulfilment. However, because of the limited number of respondents ($n = 17$), these results cannot be considered as conclusive, but should rather be seen as indicative of the studied individuals' opinions. Among the respondents, self-motivation and a sense of responsibility were the strongest drivers, while pure work demands and altruism were mentioned less frequently. Most of those who emphasized responsibility held relatively high technical ranks and had extensive experience. Respondent No. 12, an instructor of aviation security officers—the highest technical grade in the field, qualifying one to train others—stated:

"During the process of teaching students, no matter whether they can master what I teach or not, when they actually use it, I feel the power of knowledge dissemination."

This clearly reflects a sense of achievement. Interviewee No. 5 also stated,

"There is a sense of achievement when teaching students."

This relationship is clearer when the number of years of experience is taken into account. It seems that the sense of responsibility grows with the number of years of experience. However, such an observation cannot make it clear which of the following causes leads to the result: either the increased number of years of experience generates a greater sense of responsibility, or only those who possess greater responsibility tend to stay in the field for longer periods of time (Angrist and Pischke 2009, pp.227-243). This may be linked to the long-term cultural influence of aviation enterprises, which prioritize safety and emphasize precision in work. Over time, employees tend to align the interests of the enterprise with their own. Several respondents also mentioned self-discipline and internal intention. As Respondent No. 14 stated:

"Test whether you have mastered the knowledge firmly."

This correlation will be further examined through questionnaires in the quantitative analysis.

Figure 13 Knowledge Sharing Intention and Years of Working Experience

Figure 14 The Intention and Technical Level of Knowledge Sharing

4.2.3 The Association Between Risk Perception and Knowledge Sharing

Respondents mainly expressed concerns about being misunderstood, affecting others' interests, and the pressure from work tasks. Unlike R&D teams in high-tech industries, cabin staff occupy labor-intensive rather than knowledge-intensive roles. Therefore, the risk of losing individual knowledge and skills within the organisation (Hansen and Avital 2005) was not mentioned.

One common concern is the fear of making mistakes, which is more prominent among personnel with lower technical levels. For example, Respondent No. 13, who holds an intermediate technical level, said:

"I'm worried that the knowledge I share is inaccurate and may lead others astray."

"Because the trainees are taught by instructors. If there is a conflict between the knowledge points, I teach and those taught by the instructor, the trainees won't know which one is correct, which will cause confusion."

Respondent No. 15, who holds a senior position and has more work experience, was concerned about the lack of uniform teaching standards. In contrast, those with fewer years of experience were mainly worried about making mistakes in the knowledge they share. This suggests that as work experience increases, the number of people who express no concern about the risks of knowledge sharing also increases, which is understandable.

The second concern is that shared knowledge might be misused, potentially harming the reputation of the sharer or others within the organisation. This finding is supported by existing research (Riege 2005). Many respondents mentioned that when they shared real cases or events involving specific individuals, they were worried about leaving a negative impression and lowering those individuals' social evaluation. As the civil aviation industry has shifted its focus to prevention, every effort must be made to avoid accidents. Strict investigations are now required for pre-accident symptoms, unsafe incidents, and deviations. These investigations systematically analyze the causes, especially those involving human error, and impose serious consequences on those responsible, including fines, administrative penalties, technical downgrades, and flight suspensions. For the individuals involved, this is considered shameful. Therefore, sharing such knowledge may affect interpersonal relationships. Respondent No. 7 said:

"I'm worried that I might make mistakes, the knowledge I share might not be accurate, and might lead others astray."

Respondent No. 13 stated:

"I'm afraid that the viewpoints I express will touch upon other's sensitive points."

Respondent No. 5 added:

"If the remarks are inappropriate, or if you don't know much about others, perhaps what you said has stimulated them."

The third concern is work pressure. Work pressure affects knowledge sharing. One interviewee stated:

"When I'm busy, I simply don't have time for anything else."

Heavy flight tasks make employees feel tired, and knowledge sharing becomes a luxury. According to the coding results, which reflect the frequency of mentions, this type of impact does not show a clear pattern.

Regarding the factors influencing knowledge sharing, all respondents believed that familiarity among team members had a significant impact on knowledge sharing during duty, which aligns with common sense. Employees with less seniority tend to talk this more, which may be related to their familiarity with the enterprise and colleagues. Some interviewees mentioned that in master-apprentice relationships, the closeness is much stronger than among regular flight attendants. There is more communication, more operation demonstrations, and more theoretical knowledge shared. This is also part of their job responsibilities. As Instructor No. 11 stated, when teaching trainees, she would first demonstrate the operation. She lets the trainee watch the demonstration to see if he can observe it correctly. If the observation is not effective, she then explains it again. This is clearly a teaching behaviour. Instructor No. 5 also said:

"When teaching trainees, communication is ongoing at all times."

The impact of familiarity on the intention to share knowledge is an empirical hypothesis.

4.2.4 The Association Between Job Gradients and Knowledge Sharing

Research (Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022) indicates that employees with higher formal status are more likely to engage in prestige-based status competition and demonstrate more knowledge-sharing behaviours. The interview results in this study confirm that individuals with higher technical levels are more willing to actively share knowledge with those at lower technical levels.

Interviewee No. 8, who has a medium to low technical level, stated:

“The chief flight attendant will share some of his previous experiences with us.”

“How should we act to better resolve conflicts?”

“For instance, when encountering such a situation, he will share his experience from his perspective with you.”

Interviewee No. 11 is an instructor. When teaching, she conducts case analyses for the chief flight attendant. Interviewee No. 12, an aviation security instructor,

“Provide some normative suggestions to the flight attendants from the perspective of an aviation security instructor.”

Regarding job gradients, respondents with medium or lower technical levels generally indicated that communication is smoother among employees of similar technical levels. When there is a large gap in technical levels, it creates certain barriers to knowledge sharing. This is especially true when a lower-level employee interacts with someone at a higher level who also holds positions such as inspector or leader. Cabin inspectors have the authority to impose measures such as grounding or demotion on flight attendants who fail an inspection. In such cases, flight attendants with lower technical levels may avoid technical exchanges or hesitate to seek advice. They might also show behaviours such as avoidance or fear of being questioned. For example, Respondent No. 13, who holds a lower technical level, said:

“I’m afraid of saying the wrong thing, not expressing accurately enough, causing misunderstandings, and leaving a bad impression.”

“If I make a mistake, others will still have complaints about me and think I’m not professional.”

Interviewee No. 6 stated:

“Those with lower technical levels should be more casual in communication, or those at the same level as oneself should basically speak normally, just like among friends.”

Respondent No. 7 also feared exposing shortcomings and said:

“When I encounter those with higher technical levels than me, it’s usually them who ask questions. I won’t take the initiative to share with them because I’m afraid of making a mistake.”

The impact of technical grades on the Intention for knowledge sharing remains a hypothesis that requires further investigation.

From the perspective of knowledge sharing content, it includes both replicative and exploratory knowledge sharing. Replicative knowledge sharing often occurs among personnel at the same technical level. In this case, the knowledge provider simply passes on existing knowledge—such as manuals, systems, and regulations—to the recipient. During this process, the core content of the knowledge remains unchanged, and no new knowledge or concepts are generated. In contrast, exploratory knowledge sharing involves both parties processing the original knowledge and creating new ideas based on it. This type of sharing is often reflected in event handling and service skills. It usually involves tacit knowledge, and knowledge providers tend to adopt an exploratory approach. In-flight sharing frequently takes the form of discussions, which cover topics such as 2–6 *skill demonstrations*, 2–7 *experience*, 2–8 *emergency disposal*, and 2–9 *case discussion*. Figure 15 illustrates the relationship between technical level and the content of knowledge sharing reported by participants.

Figure 15 The Content and Technical Level of Knowledge Sharing

Interviews revealed that employees with fewer years of experience tend to have a stronger desire for knowledge and are eager to exchange job-related information, regulations, standards, and skills. However, they mainly rely on the active sharing initiated by employees with higher technical levels. Communication among those with lower technical grades is limited. This lack of communication is caused by three main factors. First, they may have an insufficient understanding of the tasks involved. Second, they may wish to hide their lack of knowledge or feel embarrassed. Third, the organisational atmosphere may discourage open exchange.

In interviews, senior employees were more likely to impart knowledge to those with less experience. Employees with lower technical levels preferred to communicate on equal terms with colleagues of similar technical levels. The content of their chats

involves several key areas: company policies (including bonus systems, route networks, and base support conditions); operational matters such as experience sharing, flight coordination, and key passenger concerns (e.g., identifying abnormal behavior); internal topics like departmental hot topics; as well as lifestyle interests such as improving physical fitness. These findings suggest that job gradients affect communication behaviour. Interviewee No. 3, who is at the primary technical level, stated:

“The prerequisite for knowledge sharing is that the other party’s technical level is lower than mine. If the technical level is higher than mine and the flight experience is longer than mine, it is impossible to carry out. She will think that I am educating and directing her.”

Interviewee No. 13, who holds an intermediate technical level, said:

“If they are at the same level or have a similar level, communication will be a bit more relaxed, and they will be more proactive.”

The impact of technical grades on knowledge sharing will be empirically demonstrated in the following sections.

Employees with more experience more frequently mentioned contextualized knowledge, such as handling special situations and discussing case studies, during communication and knowledge sharing. One possible explanation relates to cognitive differences. Less experienced employees may not yet recognize the importance or practical value of this type of exploratory knowledge. It also appears that new employees are less frequently mentioned in workplace communication, and their intention to learn and share is relatively weak. This is a phenomenon that deserves attention. New employees should be encouraged to study diligently and actively seek advice from veteran colleagues. Meanwhile, experienced employees should set a good example, maintain a respectful and open attitude, and engage more in experience sharing and open dialogue with both junior and senior staff.

The frequency and depth of communication among employees are shaped mainly by factors such as working area and physical space, including position in the front or rear cabin; differences in age and family status; the degree of familiarity, such as the number of cooperative flights or whether there is a master-apprentice relationship; similar technical levels; personal extroversion; and emotional state. Pre-flight preparations, as well as the chief flight attendant's ability to motivate the team—including their personal appeal, impact, and approachability—also contribute positively to team communication.

4.2.5 The Association Between Ice-Breaking and Knowledge Sharing

The degree of understanding regarding the ice-breaking effect of pre-voyage preparations varies among respondents, but most acknowledged its positive role. Due to the characteristics of the industry and the nature of the work, most respondents recognized the importance of pre-flight preparation in supporting procedural collaboration and task allocation. About half of the respondents, including those with less experience, observed the ice-breaking effect. As Interviewee No. 13 stated:

"Communicating more can liven up the atmosphere, making everyone feel less tense and depressed at work. Then, throughout the entire flight, everyone will appear particularly relaxed and happy."

Respondent No. 7 said:

"Some interaction during the pre-flight preparation stage is helpful for communication during the flight execution process."

The main reason, according to one respondent, is that a more harmonious atmosphere during in-flight work can reduce the pressure on everyone. He also noted:

"The pre-flight preparation meeting is an ice-breaking session. If a harmonious atmosphere is created, we will interact more and communicate more smoothly when we board the plane."

The knowledge sharing project diagram related to the duty process is shown below. It includes both population characteristics and specialties. For both cabin crew and aviation security officers, knowledge sharing involves not only explicit knowledge—such as regulations, standards, and company updates—but also tacit knowledge, including skill demonstrations and case discussions. The type of work experience that lies between these two forms of knowledge is the most frequently discussed.

As a temporary team, the crew carries out a special routine before each flight—pre-flight preparation. All respondents agreed that this stage is directly related to the quality of flight execution. During pre-flight preparation, crew members complete all required steps in accordance with established procedures and checklists. This stage is also a key focus of inspections by supervisory authorities and is considered a mandatory task. From the perspective of first-level coding, respondents most frequently mentioned “*1-1program collaboration*” during the pre-flight preparation stage. This reflects the requirements of the civil aviation industry, which emphasizes strict adherence to regulations, standards, and working procedures. The chief flight attendant and other temporary team leaders place strong emphasis on following procedures. In contrast, fewer respondents mentioned the ritualistic aspects of pre-flight preparation, such as ice-breaking and small talk. Although some acknowledged the presence of behaviours like small talk and “*1-4greeting*”, they had not yet elevated these to the level of building rapid trust or facilitating team collaboration. Their understanding of this dimension remains limited. The role of this sense of ritual will be further examined in the following sections.

Figure 16 Technical Level and Pre-Flight Preparation Communication

From the perspective of first-level coding, respondents who recognized the value of pre-flight preparation in "*1-3 ice-breaking ceremony*", "*1-5 interaction*" and "*1-4 greeting*" were mainly those with higher technical levels. These individuals focused on the actual quality of preparation, rather than merely completing the procedures. In contrast, respondents with lower technical levels largely overlooked these aspects. They rarely mentioned "*1-5 interaction*" and showed limited awareness of the importance of teamwork.

4.2.6 The Association Between Emotions and Knowledge Sharing

Regarding emotional experiences, demographic characteristics such as gender and technical grade show little observable association. Instead, emotional patterns are

more closely tied to individual personality traits. In addition, respondents with less flight experience tend to be more affected emotionally. As flight experience increases, the emotional impact becomes weaker and its duration shorter. Many respondents reported that they gradually developed the ability to self-regulate, which they viewed as a basic professional quality required in this field. Figure 17 shows the perceived impact of mood on work, broken down by technical level.

Figure 17 The Association between Mood and Technical Level

Based on the interview results, the influencing factors of knowledge sharing within temporary teams can be reasonably inferred to include familiarity among members, differences in technical or job grades, and the level of interaction during pre-flight preparations. Among these, familiarity and the quality of pre-flight preparation

interaction—both of which are distinctive characteristics of temporary civil aviation crews—are quantitatively analyzed and tested in the following sections.

However, it is important to note that caution must be exercised when interpreting the results of the qualitative analysis conducted for this study. First, only 17 participants were interviewed, all from one organization. Second, the analysis conducted was exploratory in nature. The results of the thematic analysis conducted should not be generalized to other groups of airline cabin crew. This is because the analysis conducted was done to gain insights on the topic being investigated and to serve as a basis for formulating hypotheses. It is also important to note that the language used in this section such as "the participants reported" or "the responses revealed" implies an exploratory analysis.

4.3 The Quantitative Analysis Finding

4.3.1 The Overall Situation of Quantitative Analysis

Based on the daily flight schedule, questionnaires were distributed at times that were convenient for cabin crew to respond. To ensure data quality, questionnaires were not distributed for fatigued flights or for flights that concluded at night. Each daily flight crew was assigned a unique identifier. The rule for numbering combined the flight date, flight number, and crew member names. For example: 20250415+GY7001.

Data were collected by combining pre-flight preparation videos of the morning outbound flights at both the headquarters base and the external station base with post-flight questionnaires.

Figure 18 Path 1 and Path 2

In the previous chapters, the following seven hypotheses were proposed.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the temporary team members' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between the temporary team members' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) and Knowledge Sharing (KS).

Hypothesis 3a: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their knowledge sharing Behaviour (KS).

Hypothesis 3b: Knowledge sharing intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).

Hypothesis 4: Familiarity (FA) positively moderates the relationship between responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Hypothesis 5: Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderate the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Hypothesis 6: The Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Hypothesis 7: The interaction quality of pre-flight preparation positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Based on the results of the questionnaire survey, the reliability analysis of the relevant measurement items is presented as follows.

Table 12 The Reliability of Each Variable

Variables and Indicators	Cronbach α	Q1 CITC	Q2 CITC	Q3 CITC	Q4 CITC
Responsibility	0.980	0.966	0.955	0.946	0.924
Achievement Orientation	0.970	0.932	0.927	0.952	0.892
Risk Perception	0.977	0.920	0.960	0.969	---
Organisational Fair Atmosphere	0.932	0.858	0.893	0.837	---
Knowledge Sharing Intention	0.973	0.936	0.932	0.955	---
Knowledge Sharing Behaviour	0.979	0.943	0.961	0.963	0.921

Cronbach's α if Item Deleted 0.986, delete

Cronbach's α if Item Deleted 0.980, delete

4.3.1.1 Reliability and Validity Assessment

Before examining the hypothesized relationships, the psychometric properties of the measures scales were examined. This process was necessary in order to check for reliability and validity, whereby the items measuring each of the constructs of AO,

RS, OF, RP, KSI, and KS are reliable and measure distinct constructs (Hair et al. 2010, pp.120-140).

EFA was done first as a means of analyzing the underlying structure of factors among the variables without assuming any prespecified structure. EFA is advised whenever scales are to be adapted to different cultures or occupations, since it aids in determining if there are similar groupings within the items as identified during the process of development of the scale (Fabrigar et al. 1999). KMO and Bartlett's test were used as a measure of sampling adequacy for factor analysis of the data (Tabachnick and Fidell 2013, p.600-630).

After conducting EFA, CFA was undertaken to determine whether the proposed six-factor solution (AO, RS, OF, RP, KSI, and KS) would be considered to represent adequate fit to the data. As opposed to EFA, which is exploratory, CFA involves testing of a measurement model that is theoretically pre-specified (Byrne 2016, pp.69-113). The aim of the CFA procedure is not the 'fit' of data in the form of maximising variance explained, but determining whether the observed data are a good match to the measurement model specified. Model fit was examined through CFI, TLI, RMSEA, and SRMR criteria, according to common conventions (Hu and Bentler 1999, p.27).

In this study, EFA technique was applied to investigate the factor structure of scales (cross industry validity), whereas, in case of CFA, the factor model was tested on the basis of theoretical hypothesis (Anderson and Gerbing 1988). From the findings of the study, it can be observed that six-factor model shows a good fit with the data (RMSEA = 0.094, CFI = 0.957).

4.3.1.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted to assess the construct validity of the relevant measurement items. The analysis yielded a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value of 0.908, indicating excellent sampling adequacy. Bartlett's test of sphericity produced a chi-square value of 21,079 with 171 degrees of freedom (Sig = 0.000, *i.e.*, $p < 0.001$), confirming that the data were suitable for factor analysis.

All common factor variances exceeded 0.6, indicating that the factors could be effectively extracted. A total of six factors were identified, which together explained 94.466% of the total variance. These results indicate a high level of construct validity. Based on the strong reliability and validity of the data, regression analysis was subsequently conducted on the relevant variables.

4.3.1.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Once it had been established that the model had a satisfactory fit, the relationships among constructs postulated under the hypotheses were tested using ordinary least squares regression analysis. Regression analysis, as opposed to CFA, forms the main hypothesis testing process. What CFA does is provide a foundation for the regression process by ensuring that the constructs employed in the regression analysis are reliable and valid. This two-stage process, first establishing construct validity before testing relationships, is common practice in management studies (Anderson and Gerbing 1988).

4.3.2 Regression Analysis

The hypotheses were analyzed through OLS regression. The standard errors were obtained through robust standard errors (Huber-White standard errors), which are used in cases where there is heteroscedasticity in the data (White 1980). The

regressions were conducted in SPSS software, and the results are presented in Tables 14-16.

Path 1: Responsibility - Knowledge Sharing Intention - Knowledge Sharing Behaviour.

Moderating effects: Risk perception showed a significant moderating effect, while familiarity did not have a significant impact.

Path 2: Achievement Orientation - Knowledge Sharing Intention - Knowledge Sharing Behaviour.

Moderating effects: Organisational Fairness Atmosphere significantly moderated this relationship, whereas interaction quality—including information entropy, emotion, and interaction density—did not exhibit a significant moderating effect.

Table 13 Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlation Analysis

Variable	Mean	Sd	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.Gende r	1.480	0.500								
2.Age	26.13 0	3.414	- 0.209*							
3.Educ ation	2.350	0.509	0.212*	0.073						
4.AO	6.125	1.074	- 0.176*	- 0.039	- 0.061					
5.RS	6.250	0.987	- 0.207*	0.012	- 0.101	0.860	**			
6.OF	5.896	1.367	- 0.092*	- 0.067	- 0.059	0.437	0.444	**	**	
7.RP	3.718	2.258	-0.061	- 0.066	- 0.021	0.035	- 0.032	0.179	**	
8.KSI	6.467	0.874	-0.058	- 0.046	0.051	0.301	0.309	0.388	0.017	**
9.KS	6.440	0.899	-0.057	- 0.040	0.025	0.311	0.310	0.368	0.006	0.919
						**	**	**	**	**

N=658, **p<0.05

AO: Achievement Orientation

RS: Responsibility

OF: Organisational Fairness Atmosphere

RP: Risk Perception

KSI: Intention for Knowledge Sharing

KS: Knowledge Sharing Behaviour

FA: Familiarity

From table 12, the descriptive statistics of the sample indicate a higher proportion of female respondents, which aligns with the occupational characteristics of the industry. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to examine the bivariate relationships between variables.

The average age is concentrated around 26 years, with a relatively small standard deviation. Among cabin crew and aviation security officers, older employees are more likely to transition to ground-based administrative roles, shift to other careers, or leave the industry altogether. Therefore, the average age of 26 is consistent with the demographic profile of employees in the new company. The average educational level of respondents is at the junior college level. The mean scores for “Achievement Orientation” (AO) and “Responsibility” (RS) are both relatively high, reflecting the industry’s emphasis on safety, service quality, work ethic, and professional values. In contrast, the score for “Risk Perception” (RP) is relatively low, which may be attributed to the non-knowledge-intensive nature of the industry and the lack of strong direct competition among employees. Scores for both “Knowledge Sharing Intention” (KSI) and “Knowledge Sharing Behaviour” (KS) are also relatively high, which corresponds with the collaborative and team-oriented nature of the work.

From the perspective of sample correlation, the correlation coefficient between “Knowledge Sharing Behaviour” (KS) and “Knowledge Sharing Intention” (KSI) reached 0.919, indicating a very strong positive relationship. This finding strongly supports the hypothesized path from knowledge sharing intention to knowledge sharing behaviour. In addition, “Knowledge Sharing Behaviour” (KS) showed a significant correlation with “Achievement Orientation,” (AO) with a coefficient of 0.311; with “Responsibility,” (RS) the coefficient was 0.310; and with “Organisational Fairness Atmosphere,” (OF) the coefficient reached 0.368. These results provide further support for Hypotheses 1 and 2. However, the moderating effect of “Organisational Fairness Atmosphere” (OF) requires further examination through regression analysis.

In addition, knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) is significantly correlated with Achievement Orientation (AO), Responsibility (RS), and Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF). Their correlation coefficients are 0.301, 0.309, and 0.388 respectively. These results provide partial support for Hypotheses 1 and 2. The moderating effect of Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) still needs further analysis.

The correlation coefficient between Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) and Responsibility (RS) is 0.444. Responsibility (RS) is strongly correlated with Achievement Orientation (AO), with a correlation coefficient of 0.860. Risk Perception (RP) also shows a certain relationship with Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF), and the correlation coefficient is 0.179.

The control variables, including age, education level, and gender, show no significant relationship with Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) or Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS). In the following section, regression analysis will be used to test each of the proposed hypotheses individually.

Table 14 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variable	χ^2	df	RMSEA	CFI	TLI	SRMR
Original model (AO, RS, OF, RP, KSI, KS)	1189.397	174.000	0.094	0.957	0.948	0.036
Five-factor model (AO+RS, OF, RP, KSI, KS)	2182.105	179.000	0.131	0.916	0.901	0.044
Four-factor model (AO+RS+OF, RP, KSI, KS)	3232.392	183.000	0.159	0.872	0.853	0.073
Three-factor model (AO+RS+OF+RP, KSI, KS)	6503.129	186.000	0.227	0.734	0.700	0.129
Two-factor model (AO+RS+OF+RP+KSI, KS)	10255.748	188.000	0.285	0.576	0.527	0.236
Single-factor model (AO+RS+OF+RP+KSI+KS)	14346.449	189.000	0.338	0.404	0.338	0.268

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; KS=Knowledge Sharing; RP=Risk Perception; OF=Organisational Fairness Atmosphere

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was adopted to evaluate data quality of the research sample and examine the correspondence between variables and items. In the original six-factor model, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is 0.094, which is within the acceptable range. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) reaches 0.957, exceeding the 0.95 threshold and indicating good model fit. The Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is 0.948, also above 0.9, suggesting good fit. The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is 0.036, well below 0.1, further supporting model acceptability. Overall, the original six-factor model demonstrates better explanatory power than the models with merged factors.

Table 15 Path 1 Regression

	KSI		KS	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Gender	-0.015 (0.070)	-0.047 (0.070)	-0.017 (0.040)	0.006 (0.017)
Age	-0.015 (0.010)	-0.014 (0.010)	-0.052 (0.038)	0.005 (0.016)
Education	0.182 (0.066)	0.160 (0.066)	0.064 (0.038)	-0.020 (0.016)
RS	0.290*** (0.034)	0.271*** (0.033)	0.318*** (0.039)	0.028 (0.017)
RP	0.034* (0.016)			
RS × RP	-0.148*** (0.043)			
FA		-0.318 (0.283)		
RS × FA		-0.038 (0.033)		
KSI				0.912*** (0.016)
Constant Term	4.530*** (0.412)	4.962*** (0.409)	-1.989*** (0.243)	-0.174*** (0.106)
F	14.467***	12.725***	18.553***	710.457***
R ²	0.118	0.105	0.319	0.919

Note: N = 658; ***indicates p<0.01, **indicates p<0.05, *indicates p<0.1, *Standard errors in parentheses.*

AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; KS=Knowledge Sharing; RP=Risk Perception; OF=Organisational Fairness Atmosphere

Model 1 uses Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) as the dependent variable and includes three control variables: gender, age, and educational attainment. The independent variable Risk Perception (RP) is also introduced. The results show that these control variables do not have a significant effect on Knowledge Sharing

Intention (KSI). Model 1 is overall significant, with an F-value of 14.467 and $p < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 is 0.118. The regression coefficient of Risk Perception (RP) is 0.034, which is marginally significant at the 0.1 level. The regression coefficient of the interaction term between Responsibility (RS) and Risk Perception (RP) is -0.148, indicating that Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates Path 1.

As seen from Model 2, the moderating influence of Familiarity (FA) on the association between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) was insignificant ($\beta = -0.038$, $p > 0.05$). It should be mentioned that the index used in this research to measure the level of familiarity, a weighted sum of previous interactions, implies certain weighting considerations which are not supported by empirical evidence (see 3.10.2.3 for an analysis). Other indices of familiarity could give a different outcome.

Model 2 includes the independent variable team Familiarity (FA). The regression results show that Model 2 remains statistically significant overall, with an F-value of 12.725 and $p < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 is 0.105, which is slightly lower than that of Model 1. The p-value for team Familiarity (FA) is not statistically significant, indicating that it has no significant effect on Path 2.

Model 3 demonstrated a positive effect of the independent variable “Responsibility” (RS) on the dependent variable “Knowledge Sharing Behaviour” (KS), which was overall significant. The F value was 18.553, and $P < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 was 0.319. The regression coefficient of “Responsibility” was 0.318, and $P < 0.01$. Model 3 shows a positive effect of the independent variable Responsibility (RS) on the dependent variable Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS). The model is statistically significant overall, with an F-value of 18.553 and $p < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 is 0.319. The regression coefficient for Responsibility (RS) is 0.318, and $p < 0.01$.

Model 4 examined the mediating role of Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). The model is statistically significant overall, with an F-value of 710.457 and $p < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 is 0.919. The regression coefficient for Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) is 0.912, and $p < 0.01$.

Table 16 Path 2 Regression

	KSI			Model 4	KS	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3		Model 5	Model 6
Gender	-0.015 (0.070)	-0.083 (0.070)	-0.085 (0.070)	-0.090 (0.070)	-0.064 (0.072)	0.012 (0.029)
Age	-0.065 (0.038)	-0.013 (0.038)	-0.013 (0.038)	-0.013 (0.038)	-0.011 (0.010)	0.002 (0.004)
Education	0.105 (0.038)	0.131 (0.038)	0.127 (0.038)	0.129 (0.038)	0.083 (0.068)	-0.037 (0.028)
AO	0.339*** (0.038)	0.209 (0.038)	0.206 (0.038)	0.204 (0.038)	0.229*** (0.309)	0.034 (0.013)
OF	0.092* (0.042)					
AO × OF	-0.177*** (0.051)					
Information Entropy		-0.003 (0.069)				
AO × Information Entropy		-0.015 (0.033)				
Interactive Emotions			0.075 (0.358)			
AO × Interactive Emotions			0.029 (0.032)			
Interactive Density				0.002 (0.002)		
AO × Interactive Density				-0.019 (0.036)		
KSI						0.936*** (0.017)
Constant Term	4.397*** (0.381)	5.367*** (0.380)	5.444*** (1.064)	5.313*** (0.382)	5.230*** (0.015)	0.206*** (0.015)

	KSI			Model 4	KS	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3		Model 5	Model 6
F	29.275***	9.520	9.635	9.835	18.192***	713.850***
R ²	0.212	0.072	0.082	0.083	0.100	0.846

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; KS=Knowledge Sharing; RP=Risk Perception; OF=Organisational Fairness Atmosphere

In Path 2, Model 1 examined the positive relationship between the independent variable Achievement Orientation (AO) and the dependent variable Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). The independent variable Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) was also included. The three control variables—gender, age, and educational background—were not significant. Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) had a positive moderating effect, with a regression coefficient of 0.092 and $p < 0.1$. The interaction effect of Achievement Orientation (AO) and Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) had a regression coefficient of -0.177 and $p < 0.01$.

Models 2, 3, and 4 respectively examined interaction information entropy, interaction emotion, and interaction density, and tested their moderating effects on the positive relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). All results were statistically insignificant.

Model 5 examined the positive predictive association of the independent variable Achievement Orientation (AO) on the dependent variable Knowledge Sharing Behaviours (KS). The model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 18.192 and $p < 0.01$. The regression coefficient for Achievement Orientation was 0.229, and $p < 0.01$.

Model 6 examined the mediating role of Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). The model was statistically significant, with an F-value of 713.850 and $p < 0.01$. The explanatory power R^2 was 0.846. The regression coefficient for Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) was 0.936, and $p < 0.01$.

Figure 19 Moderating Interaction Effect of Risk Perception on Path 1

*Note: Lines represent predicted values at low (mean – 1 SD) and high (mean + 1 SD) levels of Risk Perception (RP). The figure does not display confidence intervals; the significance of the interaction effect is reported in Table 14 ($\beta = -0.148$, $p < 0.01$).

*

RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; RP=Risk Perception

In Path 1, Risk Perception (RP) and Responsibility (RS) show an interaction effect. As RS increases, the intention for knowledge sharing (KSI) also increases. Under low RP conditions, the rate of increase in KSI is faster. Conversely, under high RP conditions, the rate of increase is slower. Therefore, RP negatively moderates the positive relationship between RS and KSI.

Figure 20 Moderating Effect of Organisational Fairness Atmosphere in Path 2

*Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention;
OF=Organisational Fairness Atmosphere*

In Path 2, Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) and Achievement Orientation (AO) show an interaction effect. The stronger the AO, the stronger the Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). When the Organizational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) is relatively low, the growth rate of the Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) is faster; conversely, when the Organizational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) is relatively high, the growth rate is slower. Therefore, OF negatively moderates the positive relationship between AO and KSI.

From the perspective of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), a high Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) is a strong context where rules, standards, and reward mechanisms are guaranteed by the organisation and are predictable for employees. Behaviours such as knowledge sharing are considered extra-role behaviours. In a strong context, employees do not need to engage in strong extra-role efforts to prove their value or secure resources. The abilities and contributions of

achievement-oriented individuals can be recognized through institutionalized and fair evaluation mechanisms. Therefore, their intention to demonstrate performance through knowledge sharing is significantly reduced. Conversely, in a low fairness atmosphere, a weak context, organisational systems lack sufficient signaling power. Employees need to rely more on proactive behaviours to shape their image and obtain positive evaluations. To increase the visibility of their abilities, achievement-oriented individuals are more likely to use knowledge sharing as an additional channel for performance demonstration, thereby strengthening the positive relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

The tests for the significance of the moderated mediation effects (Hypotheses 3a, 3b, 4, 5, 6, and 7) were conducted using the bootstrapping technique where 5,000 samples were taken (Preacher and Hayes 2008). This technique is non-parametric and does not make any assumptions about the sampling distribution. It is also advised to conduct the bootstrapping test when assessing indirect effects in mediation analysis (Hayes 2019, p.128). The moderated mediation effect findings have been presented in Table 16 below, showing the conditional indirect effects of (RS and AO on KS via KSI at low, medium, and high levels of the moderators.

The adjusted mediation bootstrap test was conducted with Bootstrap N = 658,5000 times.

Table 17 Bootstrapped Conditional Indirect Effects

Effect	Regulation	Effect Value	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Limit	Upper Limit
RS→KSI→KS	Low	0.459	0.299	0.603
	Medium	0.296	0.212	0.379
	High	0.068	0.070	0.215
AO→KSI→KS	Low	0.184	0.064	0.299
	Medium	0.088	0.031	0.147
	High	0.030	0.038	0.107

*Note: Bootstrap N = 658, 5,000 resamples. Low, medium, and high values refer to one standard deviation below the mean, the mean, and one standard deviation above the mean, respectively. *

AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; KS=Knowledge Sharing

Conclusion:

For path 1, the regression analysis results indicate that Responsibility (RS) has a significant indirect effect on Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS), and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) serves as a complete mediator between the two. Specifically, Responsibility (RS) is significantly and positively associated with Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) ($\beta = 0.290$, $p < 0.001$), and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) strongly and positively predicts Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS) ($\beta = 0.912$, $p < 0.001$). After controlling for Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI), the direct effect of Responsibility (RS) on Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS) becomes non-significant ($\beta = 0.028$, $p > 0.05$), supporting the hypothesis of complete mediation.

Furthermore, Risk Perception (RP) has a significant moderating effect on the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). The interaction term between Responsibility (RS) and Risk Perception (RP) is significantly negative ($\beta = -0.148$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that when Risk Perception (RP) is higher, the positive impact of Responsibility (RS) on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) becomes weaker. In contrast, the moderating effect of team Familiarity (FA) is not significant ($\beta = -0.038$, $p > 0.05$), providing no support for its role as a moderating variable.

For path 2, the regression results show that Achievement Orientation (AO) significantly and positively predicts Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) ($\beta = 0.339$, $p < 0.001$), and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) strongly and positively predicts the

Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS) ($\beta = 0.936, p < 0.001$). After controlling for intention, the direct effect of Achievement Orientation (AO) on the behaviour becomes non-significant ($\beta = 0.034, p > 0.05$), indicating that intention plays a complete mediating role in the relationship between the two.

Furthermore, the results of the moderation effect test revealed that the Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) significantly negatively moderated the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) ($\beta = -0.177, p < 0.01$). Specifically, when the Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) was weaker, the driving effect of Achievement Orientation (AO) on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) was stronger; whereas in a higher Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF), this effect was weakened. In addition, the marginal moderating effect of interaction density was not significant ($\beta = -0.019, p \approx 0.5$). Likewise, the other moderating variables, including interaction information volume and interaction emotion, did not show significant effects.

Table 18 Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypotheses	Test Result
Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the temporary team members' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Supported
Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between the temporary team members' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Not Supported (Significant, but in opposite directions)
Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) and Knowledge Sharing (KS).	Supported
Hypothesis 3a: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).	Supported
Hypothesis 3b: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).	Supported

Hypotheses	Test Result
Hypothesis 4: Familiarity (FA) positively moderates the relationship between responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Not Supported
Hypothesis 5: Risk Perception (RP) has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Supported
Hypothesis 6: The Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Not Supported
Hypothesis 7: The interaction quality of pre-flight preparation positively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).	Not Supported

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; KS=Knowledge Sharing; RP=Risk Perception; OF=Organisational Fairness Atmosphere

However, one should make clear that the conducted CFA is not considered to be hypothesis testing. This procedure only validates the scale measure. Testing of hypotheses formulated in Chapter 2 was carried out using regressions reported below. The separation of these two approaches to research was based on the methodology suggested by Anderson and Gerbing (1988).

4.4 Summary of this chapter

By using data modeling and analysis, the following conclusions were made:

- (a) There is a positive relationship between the temporary team members' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).
- (b) There is a positive relationship between the temporary team members' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).
- (c) There is a positive relationship between Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) and Knowledge Sharing (KS).

i. Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Achievement Orientation (AO) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).

ii. Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) mediates the relationship between employees' Responsibility (RS) and their Knowledge Sharing Behaviour (KS).

(d) This study found no evidence that Familiarity (FA) and the quality of interaction during pre-flight preparation affect Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

(f) Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

(e) Organisational Fairness Environment (OF) negatively moderates the relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

The findings of this study clearly show that knowledge sharing among cabin crew temporary teams has both characteristics of fixed teams and industry-specific features. In conclusion, the characteristics of temporary cabin teams have a significant impact on the knowledge sharing behaviour of their members. By enhancing employees' self-intention for knowledge sharing, strengthening their pursuit of achievement, increasing their sense of responsibility, reducing their risk perception, and mitigating the negative effects of team characteristics, employees' knowledge sharing behaviour can be promoted. Furthermore, even a temporary team depends on the policy and cultural support of the enterprise and its departments. When employees perceive that the organisation supports and encourages behaviours such as sharing theoretical knowledge, technical exchanges, and case studies, their intention is enhanced, and they become more willing to engage in these behaviours.

This chapter presents the findings from both qualitative and quantitative analyses and addresses the four research questions raised in this study. The following chapters will be devoted to the organisational practice, discussion, conclusions, and directions for future research.

CHAPTER 5: ORGANISATIONAL PRACTICE FOR KNOWLEDGE SHARING

5.1 Implications for Practice Improvement from Research Findings

Based on the results of the regression analysis presented earlier, Responsibility (RS), Achievement Orientation (AO), and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) are all positively correlated, with regression coefficients of 0.290 and 0.339, respectively. This suggests that a 1% increase in the scores of Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO) among temporary team members corresponds to a 0.29% and 0.339% increase in Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI), respectively. These findings indicate that RS and AO are key drivers for enhancing KSI. The regression coefficient for the interaction term between Responsibility (RS) and Risk Perception (RP) is -0.148 (RS×RP), suggesting that Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). In other words, when perceived risk increases, the positive effect of Responsibility (RS) on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI) significantly weakens.

Qualitative research also offers insights and inspiration for improving employees' knowledge sharing. Organisations can address employees' concerns by enhancing learning and cognitive understanding. It is important to strengthen employees' awareness of knowledge and its value, especially by increasing recognition of tacit knowledge. Targeted training programs, such as including department managers in the sessions, can help reduce employees' anxiety about differences in job and technical levels and eliminate communication barriers. Employees should be encouraged to take on the role of knowledge sharers, and a dedicated award for knowledge sharing can be added to the department's annual recognition system.

These research findings provide the following management insights: First, strengthen employees' sense of Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO). This includes integrating relevant assessments during the personnel selection stage and implementing targeted improvements in training programs. Second, reduce the negative impact of Risk Perception (RP) by minimizing potential career risks for employees who share sensitive knowledge. Third, enhance the capabilities of both knowledge sharers and recipients throughout the knowledge-sharing process. Based on these insights, the researcher has developed an improvement plan, and achieved some positive outcomes.

Fortunately, when the topic of this research was determined, the cabin Crew Resource Management (CRM) project of Colorful Guizhou Airlines had just been initiated. The researcher was concurrently serving as the General Manager of the Cabin Service Department at that time and thus was deeply involved in the course development. In particular, the communication section, which was originally planned for 1 class hour, was expanded to 3 class hours, bringing the total class hours to 30. This led to greater emphasis on the responsibility and awareness of knowledge sharing, and classroom cooperative sharing games were designed. With the personal experiences shared by department managers, the concerns of employees regarding the technical hierarchy and misunderstandings were significantly alleviated. As shown in Picture 2, senior managers participated in training sessions to address employees' concerns about knowledge sharing.

Picture 2 Managers Eliminated Employees' Concerns About Sharing Knowledge
Senior managers sharing personal experiences during CRM training to reduce perceived risks associated with knowledge sharing (Mechanism 2). Location: Colorful Guizhou Airlines Training Center, Guiyang, Date: March 2025, Photo by: Geng Qingshuang

5.2 Key Intervention Components and Mechanisms

Using the results obtained from the empirical analysis contained in Chapter 4, three intervention strategies were developed to improve knowledge sharing within the temporary cabin teams. These strategies address one predictor each and are actualized through practical training procedures and management strategies.

Mechanism 1: Activating Responsibility and Achievement Orientation

Based on the empirical results, it can be observed that both RS and AO are positively related to Knowledge Sharing Intentions (KSI) ($\beta = 0.290$; $\beta = 0.339$), with $p < 0.01$

for each. Two main approaches were implemented in the program aimed at motivating employees in terms of using such factors as responsibility and achievement orientation. Firstly, the length of Crew Resource Management training increased from 27 to 30 hours with an addition of 3 hours being devoted to the discussion of modules relating to the topic of communication and knowledge sharing. Modules were designed in a way that required participants to discuss actual cases of successful knowledge sharing in which their seniors talked about their experience in this matter. Secondly, achievement orientation was used as one of the motivation strategies through the implementation of the system of 'knowledge contribution points'.

Mechanism 2: Reducing Risk Perception

In the regression analysis, RP was found to negatively moderate the relationship between RS and KSI ($\beta = -0.148$, $p < 0.01$). In order to address this barrier, two methods were applied. Firstly, a learning environment free of punitive measures was fostered through managers' direct communication that any mistakes made in the course of learning will not lead to sanctions. Secondly, the pre-flight procedure was altered by focusing on psychological safety, where chief flight attendants were instructed to begin their briefings by saying "all your questions and comments are appreciated" and "we learn from each other here". The intention behind these messages is to lessen the social costs associated with knowledge sharing, especially among newer employees who were most concerned about being criticised.

Mechanism 3: Strengthening Team Interaction

Even though there was no statistical support in the quantitative study for moderating the paths based on FA and interaction prior to the flight, the qualitative data revealed that the pilots considered these moderators as having meaning in their experience. As

a result, the treatment plan included structured icebreakers during the pre-flight preparation process, involving simple introductions as well as sharing an operating hint from past flights. Although the icebreakers were insignificant in the regression analysis, they were still included because they were highly regarded by practitioners and contributed to the creation of a cooperative environment.

Temporary team building is not limited to the period before flight execution. During the recruitment of new employees, greater emphasis is placed on a sense of responsibility, pursuit of personal achievement, and teamwork. These qualities are important not only for effective knowledge sharing but also for meeting the requirements of cabin safety, air defense security, and service quality. Team collaboration requires close coordination, strong communication skills, and the ability to work well with others. These aspects were somewhat overlooked in the past.

In daily training, the concept of teamwork should be deeply embedded in employees' minds. The flight operation model, task division, and team training of the crew are all important drivers of temporary team building. Purposeful and intensive training—aimed at overcoming barriers such as unfamiliarity among members and differences in technical levels—can improve the quality of pre-flight preparation, particularly the quality of interaction. This contributes to the development of collaborative and cooperative abilities among team members.

The variability of temporary team members is a defining feature of commercial flights. When scheduling shifts, priority should be given to factors such as flight characteristics, crew qualifications and capabilities, and duty time limitations to ensure job competence and operational safety. Crew members have only a limited amount of time to become familiar with each other. The requirement for rapid team formation is to achieve a coordinated and cooperative state within 20 minutes. This

process must be supported by contextual elements, including regulations and standards, corporate culture, and collaborative resource management.

Based on the research findings in Chapter 4, and with support from the enterprise, the researcher designed and issued guidelines to improve the quality of pre-flight preparation, in alignment with the Crew Resource Management (CRM) plan.

According to these guidelines, in addition to completing the required checklist items, pre-flight preparation should place greater emphasis on mutual communication and the rapid establishment of trust. Subsequently, overall staff awareness was enhanced through department-led training sessions. This initiative strengthens knowledge-sharing behaviour among temporary team members through daily training, cultural development, behavioural reinforcement, and other supportive measures.

5.2.1 Attitude Shaping

Apart from the above-mentioned strategies, other cultural measures were undertaken to supplement the intervention. They are as follows: (a) Training for all members of the organisation regarding the importance of sharing information; (b) Inclusion of standards of knowledge contributions within the appraisal process of departments; and (c) Creating a culture where employees are allowed to learn from mistakes without punishment. While these are not the key drivers of the intervention, they created a conducive atmosphere for behavioural change.

Popularization training on knowledge, knowledge sharing, and organisational knowledge construction was carried out across the company, embedding the concept of knowledge sharing deeply in employees' minds. Misunderstandings about learning—such as viewing it only as a classroom activity—were addressed. Employees were encouraged to understand that learning is a tool for better job performance and to integrate work with study. Emphasis was placed on problem-

solving, continuous improvement, innovation, and the exchange of knowledge and experience in daily work. As cabin crew members had already implemented Crew Resource Management (CRM), aviation security officers were also included in cabin teams and received CRM training simultaneously. Knowledge sharing was integrated throughout the process to improve employees' mental models.

The unwillingness to communicate was addressed. Some individuals with lower technical levels were hesitant to participate in knowledge exchange due to fears of exposing their limitations, concerns about job hierarchy, or factors such as fatigue.

According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), attitude can predict behaviour. Situational factors were created to minimize external influences and to promote positive knowledge-sharing behaviours supported by positive attitudes. A non-punitive corporate culture was established to strengthen employees' sense of organisational support. Through education and training, employees were guided to recognize the importance of knowledge sharing and to develop a positive attitude toward it. The stronger the attitude, the more likely it was to predict behaviour. Likewise, the more significant the attitude change achieved through training and education, the greater the likelihood that employees would display the desired behaviours. Through these efforts, employees' sense of responsibility was activated, thereby improving their attitude toward knowledge sharing. Picture 3 shows a knowledge sharing training session at Colorful Guizhou Airlines.

Picture 3 The Knowledge Sharing Training Site of Colorful Guizhou Airlines
Interactive training session designed to activate responsibility and achievement orientation among cabin crew (Mechanism 1). Location: Colorful Guizhou Airlines Training Center, Guiyang, Date: April 2025, Photo by:Gengqingshuang

5.2.2 Capacity Building for Knowledge Sharing

According to the perspectives of Hendriks (1999) and Zhang, Kejun. et al. (2009), participants in knowledge sharing can be categorized as knowledge senders and receivers. A lack of knowledge-sharing capacity is mainly observed among receivers. When the ability to absorb knowledge is weak, even if the sender is willing to share, knowledge sharing is unlikely to yield effective outcomes, and the knowledge is less likely to be transformed into action.

Szulanski (1996) pointed out that, knowledge transfer barriers include the recipient's limited absorption capacity, unclear causal relationships, and a difficult relationship between the knowledge source and the recipient.

During the learning process, it is important to avoid remaining at the initial stage of rote memorization. Some civil aviation employees tend to focus on reciting manuals

and regulations without truly understanding them. The second level is comprehension. At this stage, trainees improve their learning ability, become more motivated to learn, and shift their attitude from “I have to learn” to “I want to learn.” They learn to interpret and express the acquired content in their own words, explain concepts, and illustrate what they have learned. They also begin to make inferences. The third level is operational application, which involves applying the acquired knowledge in practice. The fourth level is knowledge transfer and integration, where learners draw inferences by analogy and fully internalize the knowledge.

According to the Dunning-Kruger Effect proposed by Kruger and Dunning (1999), “the learning process consists of four stages: unconscious incompetence, conscious incompetence, conscious competence, and unconscious competence.” As skill-based operations, many abilities fall into the category of unconscious competence, that is, “I don't know that I know”. Much knowledge and many skills become integrated into the individual and form muscle memory. Once familiar, individuals no longer think about the specific steps of an operation.. It is essential to help team members recognize their knowledge and skill gaps so that they can adopt a humble attitude toward learning. Practice, hands-on operations, teaching, and discussion are all forms of active learning, which are generally more effective than passive methods such as lectures and reading. During the review process, with guidance from instructors, trainees complete the cycle of reviewing, drawing conclusions, and gaining experience.

The ability to learn knowledge and skills in context was enhanced. The first level of situational awareness is perception, which involves searching for and acquiring data. The second level is understanding, which entails extracting empirical knowledge from real-world observations and memory to form a clear understanding. The third level is prediction, which involves forward-looking thinking and the ability to update mental models, allowing individuals to anticipate the development of events and future conditions. At this level, information is transformed into knowledge. Enhancing

cognitive abilities of workers increases the application of psychological resources and improves the construction of mental models. Workers become able to effectively detect and efficiently collect information in the performance of tasks, and sense and make informed decisions.

A significant portion of knowledge in the domain is tacit and must be transferred through practice. For example, Threat and Error Management (TEM) is considered an integral component of fundamental airmanship. TEM encompasses training ideologies, flight briefing, Quick Reference Handbook (QRH), Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), and human factors that influence operational performance.

Employees were trained to become knowledge sharers and to understand how to share knowledge effectively. For example, they learned to convey information clearly and concisely, and to confirm whether the recipient had correctly understood the message. In training reviews, if trainees were guided to recognize the importance of pre-flight preparation, then the related procedures and tasks needed to be clarified, and the division of labor clearly defined. As a result, trainees were more likely to take pre-flight preparation seriously in future operations.

During flight duty, instrumental communication and social communication are closely connected. In the working environment, crew members share their feelings and emotions, meet psychological needs, and build a foundation for effective task-related communication. Casual conversations and the exchange of personal interests during the cruise phase help create a friendly and relaxed atmosphere. In the process of knowledge exchange, non-verbal communication should also be emphasized. Facial expressions, body movements, gestures, and eye contact should be used effectively.

5.2.3 Cultural Creation and Behavioural Reinforcement

According to Hofstede's (1983) study on national cultures in four dimensions, cultural differences are reflected in "Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, Individualism vs. Collectivism, and Masculinity vs. Femininity." The Power Distance dimension reflects the extent to which organisational members prefer an autocratic superior-subordinate relationship. Uncertainty Avoidance indicates how much members tend to avoid stressful or uncertain situations in workplace interactions. East Asian countries generally exhibit high power distance, placing strong emphasis on superior authority. Subordinates rarely challenge their superiors and often express opinions in an indirect and cautious manner, with one-way communication being more common. As a society with a collectivist tradition, individuals tend to adjust their personal style to maintain team harmony, willingly share knowledge, and demonstrate strong collaboration. In light of these cultural traits, this project not only emphasizes teamwork but also seeks to address employees' concerns and reduce the influence of hierarchical differences.

Organisational culture refers to the set of shared values that all employees embrace and follow, reflected in their working style, team spirit, learning attitude, initiative, and sense of responsibility. A highly adaptive organisational culture is widely recognized by employees, giving them a sense of mission, stimulating enthusiasm and creativity, and improving job satisfaction. It encourages employees to ask questions, supports the exchange of knowledge and skills, eliminates punitive practices, and prevents highly skilled personnel from occupying superior positions.

Based on enterprise practice, Kegan et al. (2016 cited in Officer 2018, pp.1-6) found that some organisations place equal emphasis on personal development and business operations, making the entire organisation function like a school. In such organisations, managers create conditions and guide subordinates to support the development of others, thereby fostering enterprise growth through human development. This approach is known as a Deliberately Developmental Organisation (DDO).

The culture of silence was addressed. Under technical or hierarchical gradients, lower-level personnel often held a sense of deference toward higher-level individuals. As a result, they remained silent when they should have spoken up. A psychologically safe environment was created to support employees in demonstrating learning and teamwork behaviours. Employees were treated with respect, and efforts were made to prevent the emergence of “anxiety zones,” characterized by high demands and low psychological safety, and “comfort zones,” where low demands are coupled with high psychological safety. In particular, under a punitive culture, strict work standards combined with low psychological safety levels posed serious safety risks. Cooperation and learning were actively encouraged, mistakes during the learning process were tolerated, and “learning zones” were intentionally established.

Real-time reviews and post-flight reviews were effectively utilized to strengthen employees’ knowledge-sharing behaviours. Team leaders, such as the chief flight attendant, were expected to conduct timely and concise post-flight reviews. These reviews helped crew members establish a common goal and enhance situational awareness. Experiences and lessons were shared, and employee performance in operational and communication aspects was analyzed, with constructive suggestions provided for improvement. Picture 4 illustrates team collaboration training activities designed to strengthen temporary team cohesion.

Picture 4 Temporary Team Collaboration Spirit Training

Ice-breaking and team-building activities integrated into pre-flight preparation to strengthen team interaction (Mechanism 3). *Location: Colorful Guizhou Airlines Training Center, Guiyang, Date: April 2025, Photo by: Gengqingshuan*

According to Trait Activation Theory (Tett and Guterman 2000), individuals receive internal rewards, such as a sense of achievement, during the process of trait activation, and simultaneously gain external rewards through performance outcomes, such as bonus points and monetary bonuses. Managers who value both types of rewards at the same time can promote desirable work behaviours in subsequent stages, thereby forming an orderly and effective virtuous cycle and further advancing organisational development.

5.3 Effectiveness Test

The effectiveness of the three intervention strategies used in Section 5.2 was tested via an experimental study involving 56 cabin crew members who had just joined the organization. In this study, while the experimental group (n = 28) underwent the

entire 30 hours of training which included all the three interventions, the control group (n = 28) underwent a 27-hour training program which excluded the two modules for communication and knowledge sharing (Section 4.3).

This was a long-term project. To evaluate its effectiveness in a timely manner, newly recruited employees were selected for a control experiment. These employees were required to undergo new employee training and initial training, including Cabin Crew Resource Management (CRM), which created favorable conditions for assessing attitudes and intention toward knowledge sharing. The main methods were as follows: First, a qualitative assessment was conducted. Interviews were conducted again with selected representative employees to better understand the internal reasons behind changes in their willingness and attitudes toward knowledge sharing. Participants were also asked to evaluate the organisational environment to determine whether the sharing culture had been effectively promoted and whether the overall learning atmosphere within the organisation had improved.

The second method was quantitative assessment. Questionnaires were used to measure employee participation indicators, such as Responsibility (RS), Risk Perception (RP), Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). The mean and standard deviation of employees' knowledge sharing responses were analyzed to describe the central tendency and dispersion of the data. Hypothesis testing using t-tests was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences before and after the implementation of the plan.

Third, further improvement suggestions were proposed. Based on the analysis results, plans for optimization were developed, along with recommendations to expand impact, address potential problems, and achieve continuous improvement.

5.3.1 Controlled Experiment Design

Fifty-two newly recruited cabin crew members from the company were randomly divided into two groups according to training requirements.

The experimental group (Group 1, 28 participants) received 30 hours of CRM training after the new employee training, including a 3-hour communication module training on shaping the attitude of knowledge sharing. The control group (Group 2, 28 participants) received 27 hours of CRM training without the communication module after the new employee training. After the control test, the control group also received supplementary 3-hour communication module training.

A 7-point Likert scale (1 = completely inconsistent, 7 = completely consistent) was used to measure four core variables: Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI), Risk Perception (RP), sense of Responsibility (RS), and Achievement Orientation (AO). All items were adapted from validated scales and were consistent with those used in previous sections. Both groups completed a baseline assessment and a post-training retest simultaneously, conducted before and after the training period.

5.3.2 Statistical Analysis Results

Table 19 Comparison Before and After Training

Variable	Experimental Group (Before Training)	Experimental Group (After Training)	Control Group (Before Training)	Control Group (After Training)
KSI	4.61±0.74	5.98±0.45	4.43±0.57	4.80±0.67
RP	2.68±1.40	1.55±0.66	2.66±1.29	2.68±1.08
RS	4.44±0.77	5.88±0.38	4.35±0.67	4.57±0.72
AO	4.39±0.622	6.02±0.52	4.29±0.53	4.51±0,54

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; RP=Risk Perception

Table 20 Independent Samples T-Test: Experimental Group (After Training) Vs
Control Group (After Training)

Variable	T Value	P Value	Cohen's D	Effect Size
KSI	7.67	<.001	17.96	large
RP	-3.02	<.001	-7.06	large
RS	8.47	<.001	19.82	large
AO	10.60	<.001	24.82	large

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; RP=Risk Perception

Table 21 Paired-Samples T-Test: Experimental Group (Before Training) Vs.

Experimental Group (After Training)

Variable	Mean Difference	T Value	P Value
KSI	+1.37	8.36	<.001
RP	-1.15	-3.65	<.001
RS	+1.42	8.88	<.001
AO	+1.64	9.87	<.001

Note: AO=Achievement Orientation; RS=Responsibility; KSI=Knowledge Sharing Intention; RP=Risk Perception

The above statistical data indicate that the training effect is significant. After the experimental group received the training that included the communication module, their intention to share knowledge, sense of responsibility, and achievement orientation were all significantly enhanced, while their risk perception was significantly reduced. The experimental group scored significantly better than the control group on all four variables. The differences before and after the test for all variables were statistically significant. This indicates that the training content, especially the 3-hour communication module training aimed at shaping the attitude towards knowledge sharing, played a crucial role in changing the employees' attitudes.

5.3.3 Practical Effects and Implications

A preliminary conclusion can be drawn:

- (a) CRM training significantly enhanced flight attendants' Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI increased by 29.7%, $p < .001$).
- (b) The enhanced CRM training led to concurrent, significant improvements across multiple psychological factors: the reduction in Risk Perception (RP decreased by 42.2%, $p < .001$) and the enhancement of Responsibility (RS increased by 32.4%) and Achievement Orientation (AO increased by 37.1%).

Practical Implications:

- (a) It is recommended that airlines incorporate the enhanced CRM training into their mandatory training programs.
- (b) Establish a "knowledge contribution points" system and link KSI to the promotion mechanism.
- (c) For individual employees with persistently high RP score (RP exceeding 6), voluntary psychological support or team counseling resources should be provided.
- (d) Develop a scenario simulation system to strengthen risk response training, adopting a hybrid model of theoretical instruction combined with scenario-based simulation.

Research Limitations:

All samples were drawn from a single airline, and cross-company validation is needed to improve generalizability. In addition, the long-term effects require follow-up data tracking for further verification.

However, the substantial positive changes noted in the experimental group, especially the increase in knowledge sharing intention by 29.7% and a decrease in risk perception by 42.2%, serve as initial proof that the intervention methods derived from the empirical study can be implemented in reality.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This chapter presents the research findings based on data collected from Colorful Guizhou Airlines, followed by further discussion and future research directions. It also provides a brief review of the research purpose, research questions, relevant literature, and key findings.

6.1 Overview of Key Findings

The Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO) are positively associated with knowledge sharing, and this association is mediated by Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). Factors such as Familiarity (FA) among temporary team members, the density, emotional tone, and richness of pre-flight interactions do not affect the positive impact of Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO) on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI). Similarly, the Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

6.2 Compare with Existing Literature

The results of the research are in agreement with previous literature on the effect of RS on Knowledge Sharing Intention within the framework of the fixed group. At the same time, the effect of RP as the moderator for the relationship between RS and KSI can be considered similar to other studies (Casimir et al. 2012).

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Concerning the effect of AO, current literature is contradictory in concluding whether it contributes in a positive or a negative way to knowledge sharing (Marinova, Moon, and Kamdar 2013). However, in this paper, it is found that the effect of AO on KSI is positive. As mentioned in Section 2.3.2.1, this discrepancy might result from cultural contingency since previous research has shown that the effect of achievement orientation on knowledge sharing was different across Western cultures (Moon et al. 2008; Chae et al. 2019). For instance, in collectivist cultures like China, an individual achievement is regarded as a part of collective achievement within the organisational context (Hofstede 1983; Cheung et al. 1996). This would explain why individuals who have a strong achievement orientation in China are more willing to share their knowledge in order to contribute to collective achievement and do not consider it to harm their position.

Another surprising outcome was the negative moderating effect of OF. Using the Situational Strength Theory (SST) discussed in Section 2.4.6, this result can be viewed as follows: when there is a very high level of organisational fairness atmosphere, it acts as a 'strong situation' (Mischel 1968; Meyer et al. 2009), where uniform standards limit the manifestation of individuals' idiosyncrasies. Under such conditions, individuals' behavior is largely determined by social standards rather than personal qualities such as need for achievement. In contrast, when organisational fairness atmosphere is low – a weak situation – the individual's personal characteristics play a larger role in his or her conduct. Therefore, the negative moderating effect should not be considered as a proof that fairness negatively affects

anything but simply shows that under a strong atmosphere of fairness, individuals do not require personal characteristics to prove their worth.

Apart from cultural contingency, two other possible reasons are worth mentioning. Firstly, organisational design might be considered. In the aforementioned organisation, the sharing of knowledge is incorporated into the promotion system and yearly evaluation process. It means that the achievement-oriented people in the organisation have an opportunity to advance in their career while proving that they are able to share their knowledge. When the organisational structures incentivise cooperation among people, the achievement-oriented people tend to share rather than hoard their knowledge (Cheng, Dejun. and Wang, Xiaoyu. 2022).

In addition, the influence of self-selection cannot be entirely ignored. The Chinese civil aviation industry has stringent entrance requirements coupled with consistent training throughout one's career; such circumstances might result in self-selection for those whose AO tendencies favor cooperation and safety compliance. As such, if cabin crew are self-selected for their cooperative nature from the start, then any negative relationship between AO and KS might not be significant.

When considered together, these other possibilities for AO's connection to KS—contingency, organizational design, and selection bias—all point to the fact that this connection is not immutable but rather dependent on the surrounding environment within which it is implemented. Accordingly, the current study's result linking AO and KS positively cannot be viewed as refuting past research but instead as supplementing it by delineating the parameters of AO's effect.

However, one must take the lack of significance for the role of the moderating variable FA with caution. It should be remembered that, as mentioned in Section 3.10.2, the way the index of familiarity is created in the present research through the

use of weighted index of prior cooperation may be considered as an example of over engineering due to the use of subjective weights in its calculation. An alternative way to measure familiarity, which includes simple indices of dyadic familiarity and frequency of prior collaborations, can lead to different conclusions. Finally, the environment of aviation implies the existence of certain SOPs, the implementation of which requires certain types of communication, irrespective of interpersonal relationships.

6.3 Contributions and Implication

6.3.1 Contribution to Cross-Cultural and Contingency Theory

This research provides a unique insight into both the cross-cultural and contingency theories in showing that there is no universal link between personality attributes and knowledge sharing behavior, as this link is influenced by culture and context.

First, the discovery that AO promotes the sharing of knowledge in a Chinese organisational environment contradicts the prevailing Western perspective which views AO as an egoistic construct and an impediment to cooperation (Moon et al., 2008; Chae et al., 2019). This study builds upon TAT by demonstrating that the trait can indeed be activated differently based on its definition in various cultures. For instance, within cultural settings where the achievements of individuals cannot be separated from those of a group, achievement orientation becomes an effective way of displaying competence through knowledge sharing.

Second, this study contributes to contingency theory by highlighting the organisational fairness climate as a situational factor influencing the relationship between achievement orientation and behaviour. Based on the SST framework, this research demonstrates that when there is a high organisational fairness climate, it

creates what SST calls a "strong situation," in which the effects of dispositional factors become lessened, while the opposite holds for a low organisational fairness climate. This insight provides further knowledge of organisational justice because, contrary to previous beliefs, it suggests that organisational fairness is not a straightforward facilitator of good behaviour but a more complicated phenomenon.

Third, by placing this study in the context of the civil aviation industry—a field marked by high levels of standardization, transient teamwork, and tasks that do not involve a great deal of knowledge—the scope of knowledge sharing research is broadened in terms of application beyond the realm of technological innovation and R&D, which have predominated knowledge sharing research.

As a whole, these contributions highlight the significance of cultural and contextual contingencies in the study of knowledge sharing. The findings show that future work in the area ought to be directed away from the question "Does variable X lead to behavior Y?" to "Under what circumstances does variable X lead to behavior Y?"

6.3.2 Practical Implications

The main contribution of this study lies in the following:

First, unlike previous studies focusing on temporary teams such as film crews, project teams, and technical task forces, this research examines cabin crews, which are more temporary in nature and have shorter life cycles. It investigates the impact of team structure characteristics and pre-flight “rituals” on Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

Second, previous research on knowledge sharing in temporary teams often treated team characteristics as independent variables. This approach tends to blur the

distinction between situational factors and personality traits, failing to clearly separate independent variables from moderating variables. In contrast, this study identifies responsibility as a primary factor for knowledge sharing and treats team structure characteristics as situational moderating variables, providing a more refined classification of these contextual factors.

Third, the application of information technology and artificial intelligence in organisational behaviour research has helped identify important moderating variables, such as emotion and engagement.

Fourth, this study highlights the role of a sense of ceremony in temporary teams, particularly during pre-flight preparations.

Fifth, the study also discusses situational teaching and knowledge exchange that occur during the flight execution process.

Main practical implications:

First, the findings support the effective implementation of Crew Resource Management (CRM) in civil aviation. Providing recommendations on crew composition helps improve the quality of flight execution. Based on the researcher's practical experience within the airline, incorporating elements that stimulate a sense of responsibility and achievement orientation, while reducing concerns about the risks associated with knowledge sharing, proved effective in enhancing employees' enthusiasm for knowledge sharing during CRM training. These measures are expected to produce even better outcomes in the future.

Second, shift the focus of pre-flight preparation from merely reading checklists and executing work procedures to a more comprehensive approach that emphasizes rapid

trust-building and role engagement. This enhances the overall quality of preparation, including knowledge, skills, and psychological readiness. Although the hypothesis test did not support a significant relationship between the quality of interaction during pre-flight preparation and knowledge sharing during flight duty, many interviewees confirmed the positive effects of such interactions during pre-flight preparation. This is also worthy of further in-depth research in the future.

Third, it contributes to enterprise knowledge development and the establishment of a learning organisation, while enhancing employees' ability to share knowledge. These improvements have further strengthened safety and service quality, enhanced market competitiveness, and better addressed passenger needs. Picture 5 shows an example of knowledge sharing content integrated into the company's teaching materials.

Picture 5 Knowledge-Sharing in the Teaching Materials of Colorful Guizhou Airlines
 Location: Colorful Guizhou Airlines Training Center, Guiyang, Date: May 2025,
 Photo by: Ling Fu

6.4 Research Limitations and Future Research Directions

The limitations of this study include the following:

First, this research focuses on non-knowledge workers in a specific industry context rather than knowledge employees in high-tech enterprises. The generalizability of the findings across different industries remains an area for further exploration.

Second, this study focuses on the characteristics of temporary teams as the core research perspective. As a result, several potentially important factors—such as the behaviour of interim team leaders, organisational cohesion, and the educational background of knowledge recipients—were not included within the scope of the analysis.

Third, the questionnaires were filled out by the employees themselves, possibly leading to common method variance. Cross-sectional research design was used in this case, capturing the correlation between variables at one point in time. While the research design suffices for the correlation test, it does not suffice for making any causation claims. In what direction do the variables affect each other? Does the sense of responsibility lead to knowledge sharing behavior or is it the other way around? Future longitudinal research will be needed to confirm the causal direction through temporally ordered observations (Angrist and Pischke 2009, pp.227-243).

Fourth, the conclusions drawn from this research have been derived using information obtained through one particular organisation. While there was diversity in terms of the technical level of workers as well as different types of roles represented in the sample used for analysis, it is important to point out that the sampling process in this study

was non-random. This means that the results obtained can only reflect the processes within this particular organisation.

Fifth, there might be some possible ordering effects on the questionnaires. In Questionnaire 1, the measures appeared in a predetermined sequence (Achievement Orientation, Responsibility, Knowledge Sharing Intention, Organisational Fairness Atmosphere, and Risk Perception). Perhaps the location of some questions had an effect on answers to other questions. Perhaps respondents answered the questions on achievement orientation and responsibility before those questions on organisational fairness atmosphere in such a way that they were unintentionally primed into a self-oriented perspective toward their working environment. On the other hand, in Questionnaire 2, questions on Knowledge Sharing Intention preceded questions on Knowledge Sharing Behavior. Though this order is theoretically accurate, it can cause consistency bias, whereby respondents feel obligated to answer in a consistent way with what they have already indicated.

However, in order to take care of these concerns, it was decided to separately measure the independent and dependent variables through different questionnaires, that is Questionnaire 1 for independent variables and Questionnaire 2 for the dependent variables. This would avoid common method variance, as suggested by Podsakoff et al. (2003). It can be argued that future research can use randomized item ordering or even longitudinal research design.

The survey method was based on traditional Likert-type scale items. Future studies could further develop this research by using advanced preference elicitation techniques, such as the use of vignettes or reference point questions. Both methods are known to be successful in reducing social desirability bias and capturing conditional preferences (Aguinis and Bradley 2014). This research methodological approach can be applied in behavioral economics and social psychology.

Prospects for future research. The TPB framework could be adopted in future studies to examine the effect of other environmental variables that may trigger the activation of personality characteristics in terms of their influence on knowledge sharing behavior. Besides, the pre-flight interactions, the technicality, mentor and mentee relationships, and leadership styles may also be worth examining.

6.5 Reflection

6.5.1 The Question Answered

This study addresses fundamental questions concerning knowledge sharing within temporary teams and confirms the applicability of relevant theoretical frameworks in the context of the researcher's organisation.

Through interviews, this study gained a general understanding of the views, characteristics, and influencing factors related to knowledge sharing among cabin crew members in the researcher's organisation. The findings were compared with existing literature. As flight experience increases, recognition of the importance of knowledge sharing also grows, and crew members are more likely to incorporate case discussions and post-flight analyses into their routines. Communication barriers are minimal among personnel with similar technical levels. Additionally, mood fluctuations during flights appear to have no clear correlation with technical proficiency. However, excessive procedural requirements during pre-flight preparations may restrict mutual communication, making their impact on knowledge sharing inconclusive. These research findings are believed to offer valuable insights for business practice.

According to the regulations for dispatched flights, cabin crew members must possess different technical grades, making it impractical to enhance knowledge sharing by assigning crew members of the same technical level to fly together. Controllable factors include crew Familiarity (FA), which can be improved gradually through fixed pairings over time. Other factors include Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF), Risk Perception (RP), and the quality of pre-flight preparation interactions. Therefore, in the subsequent questionnaire survey, these influencing relationships were verified through modeling, forming the focus of the analysis.

In the questionnaires and modeling results, a consistent finding with existing literature is that conscientiousness, among employees' personality traits, serves as a key driving force for knowledge sharing. This includes both self-oriented achievement motives and altruistic or duty-based intentions. However, due to concerns about being misunderstood, misused, or facing negative consequences—as well as the time and energy costs involved—temporary team members' risk perception negatively impacts their willingness to share knowledge.

6.5.2 Unexpected Results

Contrary to many previous research findings (Moon et al., 2008; Chae et al., 2019), personal achievement orientation in this organisation shows a positive impact on knowledge sharing. Although this result is unexpected, it aligns with findings from related studies conducted in China, reflecting the significant influence of a collectivist cultural background (Zhang, Chunmei. 2020), where individuals are educated to closely associate personal career development with organisational success. Furthermore, the organisational climate of fairness demonstrates a negative moderating effect on the relationship between achievement orientation and knowledge sharing, which is inconsistent with some existing literature (Lim and Loosemore

2017; Lin 2007). This phenomenon can be interpreted through the lens of Situational Strength Theory (SST).

This study did not demonstrate a direct relationship between the quality of interaction during pre-flight preparations and knowledge sharing behaviour. Similarly, Familiarity (FA) among temporary team members showed no significant impact on knowledge sharing. This may be attributed to the high safety standards of the civil aviation industry, the procedural nature of flight operations, and the emphasis on coordination. Regardless of familiarity or the presence of pre-flight interaction rituals, trust must be established in the workplace, and overall communication remains smooth.

Whereas many have chosen to interpret such results as anomalies invalidating past research, this paper contends that they lie at the heart of the theoretical contributions made. It would be misleading to consider such deviations from the Western-based results on achievement orientation (AO) as an indication that the previous results were wrong; instead, it simply indicates that the connection between AO and knowledge sharing is contingent upon certain contextual factors. Through identifying specific contexts under which a positive relationship is observed, it adds a layer of specificity to the existing theories.

In addition, the negative moderating impact of OF on the link between AO and knowledge sharing, even though not consistent with prior studies which view the concept of fairness as always positive, makes more sense with the use of SST perspective. This result does not imply that the use of fairness may be unproductive. On the contrary, a high level of fairness results in defined behavioural standards in the work place, so people do not have to exhibit individual qualities in order to prove their worth.

What seemed to be a deviation from previous observations, in reality, turned out to be the most important part of the research findings. This is because they force researchers to reconsider some taken-for-granted assumptions concerning the functioning of certain personal characteristics and allow new ways of examining when and where those characteristics are displayed in organizational behavior. In this regard, these surprising results, in turn, enhance the validity of the thesis rather than refute it.

6.6 Conclusion

This research has yielded a range of findings that offer valuable guidance for practical improvement. The qualitative phase revealed that key intentions for employees to share knowledge include a sense of achievement and altruistic thinking. A lower perception of risk is also conducive to knowledge sharing. Differences in technical grades can affect knowledge sharing intention, with employees at the same technical level more likely to share knowledge effectively. As employees gain more experience, the content of knowledge sharing becomes more diverse, covering case reviews, retrospectives, industry trends, and more. However, due to operational requirements for crew composition, temporary team members must hold different technical levels, and their seniority and years of service also vary. As a result, this factor is not considered controllable. In the subsequent quantitative phase, the study focused on more manageable factors such as Responsibility (RS), Achievement Orientation (AO), Risk Perception (RP), Familiarity (FA), and the quality of pre-flight preparation interactions.

The following conclusions were confirmed through quantitative analysis:

- (a) The primary intentions for knowledge sharing among cabin crew members are their sense of Responsibility (RS) and Achievement Orientation (AO).

(b) The structural characteristics of temporary teams serve as important situational factors that can either activate or inhibit members' sense of responsibility.

Specifically, Risk Perception (RP) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Responsibility (RS) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

(c) The perception of an Organisational Fairness Atmosphere (OF) negatively moderates the positive relationship between Achievement Orientation (AO) and Knowledge Sharing Intention (KSI).

(d) Aside from the factor of Familiarity (FA), the quality of interaction during pre-flight preparations does not significantly enhance the team's intention to share knowledge during flight operations.

Therefore, great importance should be attached to fostering employees' achievement orientation and sense of responsibility, while reducing their concerns about knowledge sharing. Controlled experiments have verified that employees' intention to share knowledge was significantly enhanced, producing notable results. These findings not only validate the effectiveness of the intervention measures but also lay a solid foundation for further practical research and broader application.

REFERENCES

Aguinis, H. and Bradley, K.J. (2014) Best Practice Recommendations for Designing and Implementing Experimental Vignette Methodology Studies, *Organizational research methods*, 17(4), pp. 351–371. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428114547952>.

Ahmadpour, L. et al. (2023) Knowledge sharing in temporary teams: Exploring the use of 3D printing in orthopaedic surgery. *Technovation*, 123, pp. 102723-. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2023.102723>.

Aiken, L.S., West, S.G. and Reno, R.R. (1996) *Multiple regression: testing and interpreting interactions*. London: Sage Publications.

Ajzen, I. (1991) The theory of planned behaviour. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), pp. 179–211. Available at:

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T).

Ajzen, I. (2011) The theory of planned behaviour: Reactions and reflections, *Psychology & health*, 26(9), pp. 1113–1127. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1080/08870446.2011.613995>.

Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (1975) A bayesian analysis of attribution processes. *Psychological Bulletin*, 82(2), pp. 261–277. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1037/h0076477>.

Allport, G.W. (1921) Personality and character, *Psychological Bulletin*, 18(9), pp. 441–455. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0066265>.

- Allport, G.W. (1961) An approach to personality. In: *Pattern and growth in personality*. London: Holt, Rinehart and Winston, pp.22-35
- Anderson, J.C. and Gerbing, D.W. (1988) Structural Equation Modeling in Practice: A Review and Recommended Two-Step Approach, *Psychological bulletin*, 103(3), pp. 411–423. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.103.3.411>.
- Andrews, K.M. and Delahaye, B.L. (2000) Influences on knowledge processes in organisational learning: the psychosocial filter. *Journal of Management Studies*, 37(6), pp. 797–810. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6486.00204>.
- Andrews, M.C., Kacmar, K.M. and Harris, K.J. (2009) Got political skill? The impact of justice on the importance of political skill for job performance, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(6), pp. 1427–1437. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017154>.
- Angrist, J.D. and Jörn-Steffen Pischke (2008) *Mostly harmless econometrics: An empiricist's companion*. 1st ed. Princeton, N.J: Princeton University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400829828>.
- Anumba, C.J., Egbu, C.O. and Carrillo, P.M. (2005) *Knowledge management in construction*. 1st ed. Malden, MA: Wiley. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470759554>.
- Argote, L. (2013) *Organizational learning: creating, retaining and transferring knowledge*. 2nd ed. New York: Springer. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5251-5>.
- Argote, L. and Ingram, P. (2000) Knowledge transfer: a basis for competitive advantage in firms. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 82(1), pp. 150–169. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1006/obhd.2000.2893>.

Argote, L., McEvily, B. and Reagans, R. (2003) Introduction to the special issue on managing knowledge in organisations: creating, retaining, and transferring knowledge. *Management Science*, 49(4), pp. v–viii. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.49.4.0.14421>.

Ashton, M.C. (1998) Personality and job performance: the importance of narrow traits: Summary. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 19(3), p. 289.

Babcock, P. (2004) Shedding light on knowledge management. *HR Magazine*, 49(5), pp. 46–.

Bagozzi, R.P. (1992) The self-regulation of attitudes, intentions, and behaviour. *Social psychology quarterly*, 55(2), pp. 178–204. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2786945>.

Bakker, M. et al. (2006) Is trust really social capital? Knowledge sharing in product development projects. *The Learning Organisation*, 13(6), pp. 594–605. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09696470610705479>.

Bamberger, P.A. and Levi, R. (2009) Team-based reward allocation structures and the helping Behaviours of outcome-interdependent team members. *Journal Of Managerial Psychology*, 24(4), pp. 300–327. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940910952705>.

Barrick, M.R. and Mount, M.K. (1993) Autonomy as a moderator of the relationships between the big five personality dimensions and job performance, *Journal of applied psychology*, 78(1), pp. 111–118. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.1.111>.

Barrick, M.R., Mount, M.K. and Li, N. (2013) The theory of purposeful work behaviour: the role of personality, higher-order goals, and job characteristics. *The*

Academy of Management Review, 38(1), pp. 132–153. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2010.0479>.

Bechky, B.A. (2006) Gaffers, gofers, and grips: role-based coordination in temporary organisations, *Organisation Science (Providence, R.I.)*, 17(1), pp. 3–21. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1050.0149>.

Blaikie, N. W. H. (2010) Strategies for answering research questions. In: *Designing social research: the logic of anticipation*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Polity Press.

Bock, G.-W. et al. (2005) Behavioural intention formation in knowledge sharing: examining the roles of extrinsic motivators, social-psychological forces, and organisational climate. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(1), pp. 87–111. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.2307/25148669>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>. Bazeley, P. and Jackson, K. (2013) *Qualitative data analysis with NVIVO*. Second edition. London: SAGE. Angrist,

Brislin, R. (1986) The wording and translation of research instruments, *Field Methods in Cross-Cultural Research*, pp. 137–164.

Bryman, A. (2016) Part one: the research process. In: *Social research methods*. Fifth edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press, p.29

Byrne, B.M. (2016) *Structural Equation Modeling With AMOS: Basic Concepts, Applications, and Programming, Third Edition*. 3rd ed. Oxford: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315757421>.

CAAC. (2011) *航空承运人运行中心 (AOC)政策与标准 [Air carrier operations center (AOC) policies and standards]*. CAAC. Available:
https://www.caac.gov.cn/PHONE/XXGK_17/XXGK/GFXWJ/201511/P020151103346844971519.pdf [Accessed: 10MAY 2025].

CAAC. (2018)*航空安全员合格审定规则(CCAR-69-R1)[Rules for the qualification assessment of aviation security officers]*. CAAC. Available:
https://www.caac.gov.cn/XXGK/XXGK/MHGZ/201809/t20180930_191933.html
[Accessed: 9 MAY 2025].

CAAC. (2020)*客舱乘务员的资格和训练(AC-121-FS-27R3)[The qualifications and training of cabin crew]*. CAAC. Available:
https://www.caac.gov.cn/big5/www.caac.gov.cn/PHONE/XXGK_17/XXGK/GFXWJ/202006/P020200608581952405251.pdf05251.pdf [Accessed: 9 MAY 2025].

CAAC. (2024) *大型飞机公共航空运输承运人运行合格审定规则[Rules for the certification of the operation of public air transport carriers of large aircraft]*.CAAC. Available:
<https://www.caac.gov.cn/XXGK/XXGK/MHGZ/202404/P020240415603456188073.pdf> [Accessed: 2 APR 2025].

CAAC. (2024)*客舱运行管理 AC-121-FS-131R1 [Cabin operation management]*.CAAC. Available:
[caac.gov.cn/XXGK/XXGK/GFXWJ/202412/P020241217627827577058.pdf](https://www.caac.gov.cn/XXGK/XXGK/GFXWJ/202412/P020241217627827577058.pdf)
[Accessed: 5 MAY 2025].

Cabrera, Á. and Cabrera, E.F. (2002) Knowledge-sharing dilemmas. *Organisation Studies*, 23(5), pp. 687–710. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840602235001>.

Cabrera, Á., Collins, W.C. and Salgado, J.F. (2006) Determinants of individual engagement in knowledge sharing. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(2), pp. 245–264. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190500404614>.

Cannon-Bowers, J.A. and Bowers, C. (2011) Team development and functioning, in S. Zedeck (ed.) *APA handbook of industrial and organizational psychology, Vol 1: Building and developing the organization*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association, pp. 597–650. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/12169-019>.

Carter, C. and Scarbrough, H. (2001) Towards a second generation of KM? The people management challenge. *Education & Training (London)*, 43(4/5), pp. 215–224. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM0000000005483>.

Casimir, G. et al. (2012) Knowledge-Sharing: Influences of trust, commitment and cost. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. [Online] 16 (5), 740–753.

Cattell, R.B. and P. Cattell, H.E. (1995) Personality structure and the new fifth edition of the 16PF, *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 55(6), pp. 926–937. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164495055006002>.

Chatterjee, S. et al. (2021) Antecedents and consequences of knowledge hiding: The moderating role of knowledge hidiers and knowledge seekers in organisations, *Journal of Business Research*, 128, pp. 303–313. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.02.033>.

Cheng, Dejun. and Wang Xiaoyu. (2022). 员工地位竞争动机、知识分享行为与创新绩效——基于嵌入性悖论视角 [Employee status competition motivation, knowledge sharing Behaviour and innovation performance: from the perspective of

embeddedness paradox]. *Scientific and Technological Progress and Countermeasures*, 39 (23), pp.119-127

Cheung, F.M. et al. (1996) Development of the Chinese personality assessment inventory. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 27(2), pp. 181–199. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022196272003>.

Chih-Chien, W. (2004) The influence of ethical and self-interest concerns on knowledge sharing intentions among managers: an empirical study. *International Journal of Management*, 21(3), pp. 370-.

Cohen, J. (2003) *Applied Multiple Regression/Correlation Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*. 3rd edition. Edited by P. Cohen and S.G. West. Mahwah, N.J: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203774441>.

Cohen-Charash, Y. and Spector, P.E. (2001) The role of justice in organisations: a meta-analysis. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 86(2), pp. 278–321. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1006/obhd.2001.2958>.

Collins, H.M. (1993) The structure of knowledge. *Social Research*, 60(1), pp. 95–116.

Colorful Guizhou Alines. (2025) *Company profile*. Colorful Guizhou Alines. Available: <https://www.cgzair.com/gydc/dcgs/ggjj.html> [Accessed: 15 Aug 2025].

Colquitt, J.A. (2001) On the dimensionality of organisational justice: a construct validation of a measure. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), pp. 386–400. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.386>.

Colquitt, J.A. et al. (2001) Justice at the millennium: a meta-analytic review of 25 years of organisational justice research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), pp. 425–445. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.425>.

Comte, A., Martineau, H. and Harrison, F. (2000) View of The Hierarchy of The Positive Sciences. In: *The Positive philosophy of Auguste Comte.: Volume 1*. Kitchener, Ont: Batoche, pp.42-55.

Connelly, C.E. et al. (2012) Knowledge hiding in organisations. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 33(1), pp. 64–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.737>.

Corbin, J.M. and Strauss, A.L. (2015) *Basics of qualitative research: techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Fourth edition. London, United Kingdom: SAGE.

Costa, P.T. and McCrae, R.R. (1992) Four ways five factors are basic. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 13(6), pp. 653–665. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(92\)90236-I](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(92)90236-I).

Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2011) *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles: SAGE.

Creswell, J.W. and Poth, C.N. (2019) *Qualitative inquiry & research design: choosing among five approaches*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles, California: SAGE.

Cummings, J.N. (2004) Work groups, structural diversity, and knowledge sharing in a global organisation, *Management Science*, 50(3), pp. 352–364. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1030.0134>.

De Cremer, D., Tyler, T.R. and Ouden, N. den (2005) Managing cooperation via procedural fairness: The mediating influence of self-other merging, *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 26(3), pp. 393–406. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2004.12.004>.

De Hoogh, A.H.B., Den Hartog, D.N. and Koopman, P.L. (2005) Linking the Big Five-Factors of personality to charismatic and transactional leadership; perceived dynamic work environment as a moderator, *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 26(7), pp. 839–865. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.344>.

De Long, D.W. and Fahey, L. (2000) Diagnosing cultural barriers to knowledge management, *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 14(4), pp. 113–127. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/AME.2000.3979820>.

De Vries, R.E., van den Hooff, B. and de Ridder, J.A. (2006) Explaining knowledge sharing: the role of team communication styles, job satisfaction, and performance beliefs. *Communication Research*, 33(2), pp. 115–135. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093650205285366>.

Dean, A. and Kretschmer, M. (2007) Can ideas be capital? factors of production in the postindustrial economy: a review and critique. *The Academy of Management Review*, 32(2), pp. 573–594. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2007.24351866>.

Delanty, G. and Strydom, P. (2003) *Philosophies of social science: the classic and contemporary readings*. Maidenhead, Berkshire: Open University Press, p.6.

DePaulo, B.M. and Fisher, J.D. (1980) The costs of asking for help. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology*, 1(1), pp. 23–35. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1207/s15324834basp0101_3.

Devlin, J. *et al.* (2019) BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding, *arXiv.org* [Preprint].

Dudley, N.M. *et al.* (2006) A meta-analytic investigation of conscientiousness in the prediction of job performance: examining the intercorrelations and the incremental

validity of narrow traits. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91(1), pp. 40–57. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.91.1.40>.

Dunn, W.S. et al. (1995) Relative importance of personality and general mental ability in managers' judgments of applicant qualifications. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 80(4), pp. 500–509. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.80.4.500>.

Dutton, J.E., Dukerich, J.M. and Harquail, C.V. (1994) Organisational images and member identification. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 39(2), pp. 239–263. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2393235>.

Edmondson, A. (1999) Psychological safety and learning behaviour in work teams. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44(2), pp. 350–383. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2666999>.

Edmondson, A.C. and Nembhard, I.M. (2009) Product development and learning in project teams: the challenges are the benefits. *The Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 26(2), pp. 123–138. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5885.2009.00341.x>.

Eisenberger, R. et al. (1986) Perceived organisational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), pp. 500–507. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500>.

Eysenck, H.J. (1970) *The structure of human personality*. 3rd ed. London: Methuen.

FAA. (2023) *Pilot's Handbook of Aeronautical Knowledge*. Oklahoma: Federal Aviation Administration. Available: [w https://www.faa.gov/regulations_policies/handbooks_manuals/aviation/faa-h-8083-25c.pdf](https://www.faa.gov/regulations_policies/handbooks_manuals/aviation/faa-h-8083-25c.pdf) [Accessed: 44 APR 2025].

- Fabrigar, L.R. *et al.* (1999) Evaluating the Use of Exploratory Factor Analysis in Psychological Research, *Psychological methods*, 4(3), pp. 272–299. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.4.3.272>.
- Ferrin, D.L. and Dirks, K.T. (2003) The use of rewards to increase and decrease trust: mediating processes and differential effects. *Organisation Science (Providence, R.I.)*, 14(1), pp. 18–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.14.1.18.12809>.
- Fornell, C. and Larcker, D.F. (1981) Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), pp. 39-. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151312>.
- Forrest, G.M. (1971) Book Review: The Structure of Human Personality. *Research in education (Manchester)*. London, England: SAGE Publications, pp. 95–95. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/003452377100500111>.
- Foss, N.J. (1996) Knowledge-based approaches to the theory of the firm: some critical comments. *Organisation Science (Providence, R.I.)*, 7(5), pp. 470–476. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.7.5.470>.
- Foss, N.J. (2003) Bounded rationality and tacit knowledge in the organisational capabilities approach: an assessment and a re-evaluation, *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 12(2), pp. 185–201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/12.2.185>.
- Foss, N.J., Husted, K. and Michailova, S. (2010) Governing knowledge sharing in organisations: levels of analysis, governance mechanisms, and research directions. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(3), pp. 455–482. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2009.00870.x>.
- Gong, Y. *et al.* (2012) Unfolding the proactive process for creativity: Integration of the employee proactivity, information exchange, and psychological safety

perspectives. *Journal of Management*, 38(5), pp. 1611–1633. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206310380250>.

Goodman, R.A. and Goodman, L.P. (1976) Some management issues in temporary systems: a study of professional development and manpower-the theater case. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 21(3), pp. 494–501. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2391857>.

Gotlieb, J.B., Grewal, D. and Brown, S.W. (1994) Consumer satisfaction and perceived quality: complementary or divergent constructs?, *Journal of applied psychology*, 79(6), pp. 875–885. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.79.6.875>.

Grant, A.M. and Wrzesniewski, A. (2010) I won't let you down... or will I? core self-evaluations, other-orientation, anticipated guilt and gratitude, and job performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(1), pp. 108–121. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017974>.

Grant, R.M. (1996) Toward a knowledge-based theory of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17(S2), pp. 109–122. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250171110>.

Greenberg, J. (1987) A taxonomy of organisational justice theories. *The Academy of Management Review*, 12(1), pp. 9–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/257990>.

Grimmer, J. and Stewart, B.M. (2013) Text as Data: The Promise and Pitfalls of Automatic Content Analysis Methods for Political Texts, *Political analysis*, 21(3), pp. 267–297. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/pan/mps028>.

Grix, J. (2002) Introducing students to the generic terminology of social research. *Politics (Manchester, England)*, 22(3), pp. 175–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9256.00173>.

GUBA E. G (1994) Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of Qualitative Research* [Preprint].

Hainmueller, J., Hangartner, D. and Yamamoto, T. (2014) Do Survey Experiments Capture Real-World Behavior? External Validation of Conjoint and Vignette Analyses with a Natural Experiment. Harvard Dataverse. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7910/dvn/27793>.

Hair, J.F. (2010) *Multivariate data analysis*. 7th ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.

Hakanson, L. (2007) Creating knowledge: the power and logic of articulation, *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 16(1), pp. 51–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dtl033>.

Hakanson, L. (2010) The firm as an epistemic community: the knowledge-based view revisited, *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 19(6), pp. 1801–1828. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dtq052>.

Hallebone, E. and Priest, J. (2009) *Business and management research: paradigms & practices*. 1st edn. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Hansen, M.T. (1999) The search-transfer problem: the role of weak ties in sharing knowledge across organisation subunits. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44(1), pp. 82–111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2667032>.

Hansen, S. and Avital, M. (2005) Share and share alike: the social and technological influences on knowledge sharing behaviour. *Sprouts (Cleveland, Ohio)*, 5(1).

Hao, Qi., Jin, Chang., Wei, Kou. (2019) 虚拟团队成员知识分享行为影响机制：个人与环境交互视角 [The influence mechanism of virtual team members' knowledge-sharing Behaviour: an interaction perspective between individuals and the environment]. Beijing: Zhongguorenmindaxue. Available: <https://www.kjib.org/fileup/HTML/2019-7-138.htm> [Accessed: 12 APR 2025].

Harrison, D.A., Newman, D.A. and Roth, P.L. (2006) How important are job attitudes? meta-analytic comparisons of integrative behavioural outcomes and time sequences. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(2), pp. 305–325. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2006.20786077>.

Hart, J.W. et al. (2004) Achievement motivation, expected coworker performance, and collective task motivation: working hard or hardly working?. *Journal Of Applied Social Psychology*, 34(5), pp. 984–1000. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2004.tb02580.x>.

Hayes, A.F. (2019) *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: a regression-based approach*. Second edition. New York, New York; The Guilford Press.

Helmreich, R.L. and Merritt, A.C. (2001) *Culture at work in aviation and medicine: national, organizational, and professional influences*. 1st ed. Aldershot: Ashgate.

Hendriks, P. (1999) Why share knowledge? the influence of ICT on the motivation for knowledge sharing. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 6(2), pp. 91–100. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1441\(199906\)6:2<91::AID-KPM54>3.0.CO;2-M](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1441(199906)6:2<91::AID-KPM54>3.0.CO;2-M).

Hofstede, G. (1983) National cultures in four dimensions: a research-based theory of cultural differences among nations. *International Studies of Management and*

Organisation, 13(1–2), pp. 46–74. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00208825.1983.11656358>.

Hogan, R., Johnson, J. and Briggs, S. (1997) *Handbook of personality psychology*. 1st ed. Chantilly: Elsevier Science & Technology.

Hogg, M.A. and Terry, D.J. (2000) Social Identity and self-categorization processes in organisational contexts. *The Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), pp. 121–153. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/259266>.

Hough, L.M. (1992) The “Big Five” Personality variables--construct confusion: description versus prediction. *Human Performance*, 5(1–2), pp. 139–155. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08959285.1992.9667929>.

Hough, L.M. and Oswald, F.L. (2005) They’re right, well ... mostly right: research evidence and an agenda to rescue personality testing from 1960s insights. *Human Performance*, 18(4), pp. 373–387. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327043hup1804_4.

Hu, L. and Bentler, P.M. (1999) Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives, *Structural equation modeling*, 6(1), pp. 1–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>.

ICAO. (2020) *Doc10002: cabin crew safety training manual*. 2nd edition. Montreal: International Civil Aviation Organisation.

ICAO. (2024) *safety management manual (doc 9859)*. Montreal: International Civil Aviation Organisation.

Ilgen, D.R. *et al.* (2005) Teams in Organizations: From Input-Process-Output Models to IMO Models, *Annual review of psychology*, 56(1), pp. 517–543. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.56.091103.070250>.

Ipe, M. (2003) Knowledge sharing in organisations: a conceptual framework. *Human Resource Development Review*, 2(4), pp. 337–359. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484303257985>.

Ismail Al-Alawi, A., Yousif Al-Marzooqi, N. and Fraidoon Mohammed, Y. (2007) Organisational culture and knowledge sharing: critical success factors. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 11(2), pp. 22–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270710738898>.

Ivankova, N.V., Creswell, J.W. and Stick, S.L. (2006) Using Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design: From Theory to Practice, *Field methods*, 18(1), pp. 3–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X05282260>.

J.D. and Pischke, J.-S. (2009) *Mostly harmless econometrics: an empiricist's companion*. Princeton, N. J.; Princeton University Press. Available at: <http://www.vlebooks.com/vleweb/product/openreader?id=Stirling&isbn=9781400829828>.

Jiang, Nan. et al. (2023) Full-Body Articulated Human-Object Interaction, arXiv.org [Preprint]. Hickman, L. et al. (2022) Text Preprocessing for Text Mining in Organizational Research: Review and Recommendations, *Organizational research methods*, 25(1), pp. 114–146. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428120971683>.

Judge, T.A. and Zapata, C.P. (2015) The person-situation debate revisited: effect of situation strength and trait activation on the validity of the big five personality traits in predicting job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 58(4), pp. 1149–1179. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2010.0837>.

Judge, T.A. and Zapata, C.P. (2015) The person–situation debate revisited: effect of situation strength and trait activation on the validity of the big five personality traits in

predicting job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 58(4), pp. 1149–1179. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2010.0837>.

Judge, T.A. et al. (2013) Hierarchical representations of the five-factor model of personality in predicting job performance: integrating three organizing frameworks with two theoretical perspectives. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 98(6), pp. 875–925. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033901>.

Kamdar, D. and Dyne, L.V. (2007) The joint effects of personality and workplace social exchange relationships in predicting task performance and citizenship performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(5), pp. 1286–1298. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.5.1286>.

Kim, S. and Lee, H. (2006) The Impact of organisational context and information technology on employee knowledge-sharing capabilities. *Public Administration Review*, 66(3), pp. 370–385. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00595.x>.

King, N. and Horrocks, C. (2010) *Interviews in qualitative research*. London: SAGE.

Korsgaard, M.A., Meglino, B.M. and Lester, S.W. (1997) Beyond helping: do other-oriented values have broader implications in organisations?. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82(1), pp. 160–177. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.82.1.160>.

Kozlowski, S. W. J. and Bell, B. S. (2003). Work groups and teams in organisations. In W. C. Borman, D. R. Ilgen, & R. J. Klimoski (Eds.). *Handbook of psychology (Vol. 12): Industrial and Organisational Psychology*. New York: Wiley, pp. 333-375.

KPMG. (2000) *Knowledge management research report 2000*. KPMG. Available: https://www.providersedge.com/docs/km_articles/KPMG_KM_Research_Report_2000.pdf [Accessed: 2 April 2025].

Kraft, P. et al. (2005) Perceived difficulty in the theory of planned behaviour: Perceived behavioural control or affective attitude? *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 44(3), pp. 479–496. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466604X17533>.

Krauss, S.E. (2005) Research paradigms and meaning making: A primer. *The Qualitative Report*, 10 (4), pp. 758-770.

Kruger, J. and Dunning, D. (1999) Unskilled and unaware of it: how difficulties in recognizing one's own incompetence lead to inflated self-assessments. *Journal Of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77(6), pp. 1121–1134. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.77.6.1121>.

Kvale, S. and Brinkmann, S. (2009) *Interviews: learning the craft of qualitative research interviewing*. Los Angeles: Sage.

Leavy, P. (ed.) (2014) *The Oxford handbook of qualitative research*. New York, New York: Oxford University Press.

Levin, D.Z. and Cross, R. (2004) The strength of weak ties you can trust: the mediating role of trust in effective knowledge transfer. *Management Science*, 50(11), pp. 1477–1490. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1030.0136>.

Levin, D.Z. et al. (2003) Trust and knowledge sharing. In *Creating value with knowledge: insights from the IBM Institute for Business Value*.

Liao, H. and Rupp, D.E. (2005) The impact of justice climate and justice orientation on work outcomes: a cross-level multifoci framework. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(2), pp. 242–256. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.90.2.242>.

Lim, B.T.H. and Loosemore, M. (2017) The effect of inter-organisational justice perceptions on organisational citizenship Behaviours in construction projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(2), pp. 95–106. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2016.10.016>.

Lin, C.-P. (2007a) To share or not to share: modeling knowledge sharing using exchange ideology as a moderator. *Personnel Review*, 36(3), pp. 457–475. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483480710731374>.

Lin, C.-P. (2007b) To Share or not to share: modeling tacit knowledge sharing, its mediators and antecedents. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 70(4), pp. 411–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-006-9119-0>.

Lin, H.-F. (2007) Effects of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation on employee knowledge sharing intentions. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2), pp. 135–149. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506068174>.

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. London, United Kingdom: Sage.

Lu, Sha. (2022) 2022 年混合办公模式下三大趋势预测 [Three predictions for the hybrid work model in 2022]. *China Informationization Weekly Report*, 24 Jan, p.25. Available: CNKI [Accessed: 15 Sep 2025]

Lundin, R.A. and Söderholm, A. (1995) A theory of the temporary organisation. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 11(4), pp. 437–455. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0956-5221\(95\)00036-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0956-5221(95)00036-U).

- Lundin, R.A. and Steinhórsson, R.S. (2003) Studying organisations as temporary. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 19(2), pp. 233–250. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-5221\(02\)00006-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0956-5221(02)00006-4).
- Madison, P. (1968) Personality and assessment, *The American journal of psychology*. University of Illinois Press, pp. 609–611. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1421067>.
- Margerison, C.J., Davies, R.V. and McCann, D.J. (1986) Team management on the flight deck. *Leadership & Organisation Development Journal*, 7(4), pp. 1–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb053601>.
- Marinova, S.V., Moon, H. and Kamdar, D. (2013) Getting ahead or getting along? the two-facet conceptualization of conscientiousness and leadership emergence. *Organisation Science (Providence, R.I.)*, 24(4), pp. 1257–1276. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1120.0781>.
- Mathieu, J. *et al.* (2008) Team Effectiveness 1997-2007: A Review of Recent Advancements and a Glimpse into the Future, *Journal of management*, 34(3), pp. 410–476. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308316061>.
- McCrae, R.R. and Costa, P.T. (1997) Personality trait structure as a human universal. *The American psychologist*, 52(5), pp. 509–516. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.52.5.509>.
- McLure Wasko, M. and Faraj, S. (2000) “It is what one does”: why people participate and help others in electronic communities of practice. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 9(2), pp. 155–173. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687\(00\)00045-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687(00)00045-7).

Men, C. et al. (2020) Ethical leadership and knowledge hiding: a moderated mediation model of psychological safety and mastery climate. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 166(3), pp. 461–472. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-018-4027-7>.

Meyer, R.D., Dalal, R.S. and Bonaccio, S. (2009) A meta-analytic investigation into the moderating effects of situational strength on the conscientiousness-performance relationship, *Journal of organisational Behaviour*, 30(8), pp. 1077–1102. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.602>.

Meyerson, D. et al. (1995) Swift trust and temporary groups. in *Trust in organisations*. United States: SAGE Publications, Incorporated, pp. 166–195. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452243610.n9>.

Miles, M.B., Huberman, A.M. and Saldaña, J. (2021) *Qualitative data analysis: a methods sourcebook*. Fourth edition. London, United Kingdom: SAGE.

Miller, D. and Shamsie, J. (1996) The Resource-based view of the firm in two environments: the hollywood film studios from 1936 to 1965, *Academy of Management journal*, 39(3), pp. 519–543. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/256654>.

Mischel, W. (2009) From Personality and Assessment (1968) to Personality Science, 2009. *Journal of research in personality*, 43(2), pp. 282–290. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2008.12.037>.

Moan, I.S. and Rise, J. (2006) Predicting smoking reduction among adolescents using an extended version of the theory of planned behaviour. *Psychology & Health*, 21(6), pp. 717–738. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14768320600603448>.

- Mohammed, S. and Nadkarni, S. (2011) Temporal diversity and team performance: the moderating role of team temporal leadership. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(3), pp. 489–508. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2011.61967991>.
- Moon, H. (2001) The two faces of conscientiousness: duty and achievement striving in escalation of commitment dilemmas. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), pp. 533–540. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.535>.
- Moon, H. et al. (2008) Me or we? the role of personality and justice as other-centered antecedents to innovative citizenship behaviours within organisations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(1), pp. 84–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.93.1.84>.
- Moorman, R.H. (1991) Relationship between organisational justice and organisational citizenship behaviours: do fairness perceptions influence employee citizenship? *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(6), pp. 845–855. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.76.6.845>.
- Moreland, R.L. and Levine, J.M. (2002) Socialization and trust in work groups. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 5(3), pp. 185–201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430202005003001>.
- Mossholder, K.W., Richardson, H.A. and Settoon, R.P. (2011) Human resource systems and helping in organisations: a relational perspective. *The Academy of Management Review*, 36(1), pp. 33–52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2009.0402>.
- Nahapiet, J. and Ghoshal, S. (1998) Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organisational advantage. *The Academy of Management Review*, 23(2), pp. 242–266. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1998.533225>.

- Ng, T.W.H. and Lucianetti, L. (2016) Goal striving, idiosyncratic deals, and job Behaviour. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour*, 37(1), pp. 41–60. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2023>.
- Nonaka, I. (1991) The knowledge-creating company. *Harvard business review*, pp. 96–96.
- Nonaka, I. et al. (1994) Organisational knowledge creation theory: A first comprehensive test. *International Business Review*, 3(4), pp. 337–351. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0969-5931\(94\)90027-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0969-5931(94)90027-2).
- Nunnally, J.C. and Bernstein, I.H. (1994) *Psychometric theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Nunnally, J.C. and Bernstein, I.H. (1994) *Psychometric theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Officer, D.R. (2018) An Everyone Culture: Becoming a Deliberately Developmental Organization, *The innovation journal*. Ottawa: The Innovation Journal, pp. 1–6.
- Panteli, N. and Sockalingam, S. (2005) Trust and conflict within virtual inter-organisational alliances: a framework for facilitating knowledge sharing. *Decision Support Systems*, 39(4), pp. 599–617. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2004.03.003>.
- Peng, H. and Pierce, J. (2015) Job- and organisation-based psychological ownership: relationship and outcomes. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 30(2), pp. 151–168. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-07-2012-0201>.
- Pennebaker, J.W., Mehl, M.R. and Niederhoffer, K.G. (2003) Psychological Aspects of Natural Language Use: Our Words, Our Selves, *Annual review of psychology*,

54(1), pp. 547–577. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.54.101601.145041>.

Personality traits: their classification and measurement (1921) *The Journal of abnormal psychology and social psychology* [Preprint]. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1037/h0069790>.

Petrash, G. (1996) Dow's journey to a knowledge value management culture. *European Management Journal*, 14(4), pp. 365–373. Available at:
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-2373\(96\)00023-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-2373(96)00023-0).

Podsakoff, P.M. et al. (2000) Organisational citizenship behaviours: a critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research. *Journal of Management*, 26(3), pp. 513–563. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/014920630002600307>.

Podsakoff, P.M. et al. (2003) Common Method Biases in Behavioral Research: A Critical Review of the Literature and Recommended Remedies, *Journal of applied psychology*, 88(5), pp. 879–903. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.5.879>.

Polanyi, M. (1983) *The tacit dimension*. Gloucester, Mass: Peter Smith, pp.3-25. Available at: <http://stir.ac.uk/3hl>.

Preacher, K.J. and Hayes, A.F. (2008) Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in multiple mediator models, *Behavior research methods*, 40(3), pp. 879–891. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BRM.40.3.879>.

Qian, Yan. and Liu, Hong. (2007) 论构建临时团队的快速信任机制 [Building the rapid trust mechanism of temporary teams]. *Journal of Nanjing Normal University (Social Science Edition)*, (03), pp.71-75+134.

Qin, Kaiyin.; Du, Rong.; and Li, Yan. (2010) 临时团队中知识共享对快速信任与绩效关系的调节作用研究 [The moderating effect of knowledge sharing on the relationship between rapid trust and performance in temporary teams]. *Journal of Management*, 7(01), pp.98-102+110.

Quinn, J.B., Anderson, P. and Finkelstein, S. (1996) Managing professional intellect: making the most of the best. *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 71–80.

Rajan, A., Lank, E. and Chapple, K. (1999) *Good practices in knowledge creation & exchange*. Focus: CREATE, pp.35-42

Reagans, R. and McEvily, B. (2003) Network structure and knowledge transfer: the effects of cohesion and range. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 48(2), pp. 240–267. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3556658>.

Riege, A. (2005) Three-dozen knowledge-sharing barriers managers must consider. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 9(3), pp. 18–35. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270510602746>.

Robbins, S.P. and Judge, T. (2014) Personality and Values. In: *Essentials of organizational behavior*. Twelfth edition / Stephen P. Robbins, Timothy A. Judge. Boston: Pearson, pp.62-79.

Ruggles, R. (1998). The State of the Notion: Knowledge Management in Practice. *California Management Review*, 40(3), 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41165944>

Sacks, H., Schegloff, E.A. and Jefferson, G. (1974) A simplest systematics for the organization of turn-taking for conversation, *Language (Baltimore)*, 50(4), pp. 696–735. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/412243>.

Salas, E. *et al.* (2012) The Science of Training and Development in Organizations: What Matters in Practice, *Psychological science in the public interest*, 13(2), pp. 74–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1529100612436661>.

Sale, J.E.M., Lohfeld, L.H. and Brazil, K. (2002) Revisiting the Quantitative-Qualitative Debate: Implications for Mixed-Methods Research, *Quality & quantity*, 36(1), pp. 43–53. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014301607592>.

Saucier, G. and Ostendorf, F. (1999) Hierarchical subcomponents of the big five personality factors: a cross-language replication. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(4), pp. 613–627. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.76.4.613>.

Saunders, M.N.K., Thornhill, A. and Lewis, P. (2016) *Research methods for business students*. Seventh edition. Harlow, England: Pearson Education Limited.

Sawng, Y.W., Kim, S.H. and Han, H.S. (2006) R&D group characteristics and knowledge management activities: a comparison between ventures and large firms. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 35(1–4), pp. 241–261. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTM.2006.009237>.

Schepers, P. and Van Den Berg, P.T. (2007) Social factors of work-environment creativity. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 21(3), pp. 407–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-006-9035-4>.

Senge, P. (1998) Sharing knowledge. *Leadership Excellence*, 15(6), pp. 11–12.

Shannon, C.E. (1948) A mathematical theory of communication, *Bell System Technical Journal*, 27(4), pp. 623–656. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb00917.x>.

Sheeran, P. and Webb, T.L. (2016) The Intention-behaviour gap, *Social and personality psychology compass*, 10(9), pp. 503–518. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12265>.

Shook et al. (2004) An assessment of the use of structural equation modeling in strategic management research. *Strategic Management Journal*, 25(4), pp. 397–404. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.385>.

Sitzmann, T. and Bell, B.S. (2017) The dynamic effects of subconscious goal pursuit on resource allocation, task performance, and goal abandonment. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 138, pp. 1–14. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2016.11.001>.

Smith, C.A. et al. (1983) Organisational citizenship behaviour: its nature and antecedents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 68(4), pp. 653–663. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.68.4.653>.

Smither, R.D. and Houston, J.M. (1992) The nature of competitiveness: the development and validation of the competitiveness index. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 52(2), pp. 407–418. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164492052002016>.

Spender, J. -C (1996) Making knowledge the basis of a dynamic theory of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17(S2), pp. 45–62. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250171106>.

Srivastava, A., Bartol, K.M. and Locke, E.A. (2006) Empowering leadership in management teams: effects on knowledge sharing, efficacy, and performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(6), pp. 1239–1251. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2006.23478718>.

Sundaresan, S. and Zuopeng, Z. (2004) Facilitating knowledge transfer in organisations through incentive alignment and IT investment. in *37th annual Hawaii international conference on system sciences, 2004. proceedings of the*. IEEE, p. 10 pp. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2004.1265600>.

Swan, J. et al. (1999) Knowledge management and innovation: networks and networking. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 3(4), pp. 262–275. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673279910304014>.

Szulanski, G. (1996). Exploring internal stickiness: impediments to the transfer of best practice within the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17(S2), 27–43. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250171105>

Tabachnick, B.G. and Fidell, L.S. (2013) *Using multivariate statistics*. Sixth edition, Pearson new international edition. Harlow, England: Pearson.

Tajfel, H., Turner, J. (1979) An integrative theory of intergroup conflict, An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In: *The social psychology of intergroup relations*. Brooks: Cole Pub, pp. 33–47.

Tangirala, S. et al. (2013) Doing right versus getting ahead: the effects of duty and achievement orientations on employees' voice. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 98(6), pp. 1040–1050. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033855>.

Tausczik, Y.R. and Pennebaker, J.W. (2010) The Psychological Meaning of Words: LIWC and Computerized Text Analysis Methods, *Journal of language and social*

psychology, 29(1), pp. 24–54. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X09351676>.

Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A. (2009) *Foundations of mixed methods research : integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches in the social and behavioral sciences*. Los Angeles, California: SAGE. Available at:
<http://www.vlebooks.com/vleweb/product/openreader?id=Stirling&isbn=9781452208107>.

Tett, R.P. and Guterman, H.A. (2000) Situation trait relevance, trait expression, and cross-situational consistency: testing a principle of trait activation. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 34(4), pp. 397–423. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1006/jrpe.2000.2292>.

Tett, R.P. et al. (2013) Trait activation theory: applications, developments, and implications for person-workplace fit, in handbook of personality at work. 1st edn. Routledge, pp. 71–100. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203526910-6>.

Tett, R.P., Burnett, D.D. and Zedeck, S. (2003) A personality trait-based interactionist model of job performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(3), pp. 500–517. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.88.3.500>.

Tourangeau, R., Rips, L.J. and Rasinski, K.A. (2000) *The psychology of survey response*. New York, New York: Cambridge University Press. Available at:
<http://ezproxy.stir.ac.uk/login?url=https://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511819322>.

Tuckman, B.W. and Jensen, M.A.C. (1977) Stages of Small-Group Development Revisited, *Group & Organization Studies*, 2(4), pp. 419–427. Available at:
<https://doi.org/10.1177/105960117700200404>.

Tyler, T.R. and Blader, S.L. (2003) The group engagement model: procedural justice, social identity, and cooperative behaviour. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 7(4), pp. 349–361. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327957PSPR0704_07.

Tynan, R. (2005) The effects of threat sensitivity and face giving on dyadic psychological safety and upward communication. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 35(2), pp. 223–247. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.2005.tb02119.x>.

Van Knippenberg, D. and Schippers, M.C. (2007) Work group diversity. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 58(1), pp. 515–541. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.58.110405.085546>.

Vuori, V. and Okkonen, J. (2012) Knowledge sharing motivational factors of using an intra-organisational social media platform. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 16(4), pp. 592–603. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271211246167>.

Wang, Dengfeng. and Cui, Hong. (2003) 中国人人格量表的编制过程与初步结果 [The compiling process and preliminary results of Chinese personality scale]. *Acta Psychologica Sinica*, 35(1), pp.127-136.

Wang, S. and Noe, R.A. (2010) Knowledge sharing: A review and directions for future research. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20(2), pp. 115–131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2009.10.001>.

Wang, Xianya., Lin, sheng., Chen, Liyun., and Bai, Yin. (2014). 组织氛围、隐性知识共享行为与员工创新绩效关系的实证研究 [An empirical investigation on the relationship between organisation climate, tacit knowledge-sharing behaviour and innovation performance]. *Soft Science*, 28(5), pp.43-47

Wang, Yonggui. et al. (2019) The double-edged effects of perceived knowledge hiding: empirical evidence from the sales context. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(2), pp. 279–296. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-04-2018-0245>.

Wasserman, S. and Faust, K. (1994) *Social network analysis: methods and applications*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Wei, Xia., Yang, Chengli., and Luo, Zhenguo. (2024) *机组资源管理概论* [Introduction to unit resource management]. Chengdu: Southwest jiaotong university press.

White, H. (1980) A Heteroskedasticity-Consistent Covariance Matrix Estimator and a Direct Test for Heteroskedasticity, *Econometrica*, 48(4), pp. 817–838. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1912934>.

Willem, A. and Scarbrough, H. (2006) Social capital and political bias in knowledge sharing: An exploratory study. *Human Relations (New York)*, 59(10), pp. 1343–1370. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726706071527>.

Woolley, A.W. et al. (2010) Evidence for a Collective Intelligence Factor in the Performance of Human Groups, *Science (American Association for the Advancement of Science)*, 330(6004), pp. 686–688. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1193147>.

Xu, Ri. (2020). 疫情下的远程办公优化路径 [The optimal path for telecommuting under the pandemic]. *Management Informatization in China*, 23 (14), pp.117-119

Yuan, Rong. (2023). 基于 SECI 模型的航空公司安全运营管理的知识学习模式研究 [Research on the Knowledge Learning Model for Airline Safety Operation

Management Based on the SECI Model]. *Knowledge Management Forum*, 8 (06), pp.554-565.

Yujong Hwang and Kim, D.J. (2007) Understanding affective commitment, collectivist culture, and social influence in relation to knowledge sharing in technology mediated learning. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 50(3), pp. 232–248. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPC.2007.902664>.

Zhang, Chunmei. (2020) 个人主义/集体主义对团队创造力的影响: 隐性知识共享的中介作用 [The impact of individualism/collectivism on team creativity: the mediating role of tacit knowledge sharing]. Wuhan University. Available: <https://philosophy.whu.edu.cn/info/1038/13206.htm> [Accessed: 12 APR 2025].

Zhang, Kejun., Liao, Jianqiao., and Wen, Peng. (2009) 学习型组织中知识共享的障碍及治理策略研究 [Intellectual disability and governance strategies of knowledge sharing in learning organisations]. *Journal of Management*, 6(5), pp.580–586. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1672-884X.2009.05.002>.

Zhao, Hongdan. and Xia, Qing. (2019) 人际不信任、消极情感与知识隐藏行为研究 [Research on Interpersonal disbelief, negative emotions and knowledge concealment behaviours]. *Scientific Research Management*, 40(08), pp.284-292.

Zou, Jianxin. (2012). 浅议知识管理在我国民航业的应用[A Brief Discussion on the Application of Knowledge Management in China's Civil Aviation Industry]. *Traffic Enterprise Management*, 27 (09), pp59-61.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Interview Outline

访谈为半结构化,主要话题包括但不限于:

The interview is semi-structured, with main topics including but not limited to:

你觉得什么是知识? (顺便介绍知识和知识分享所包括的范围,以统一访谈内容的标准,消除受访者普遍存在的对知识的狭隘定义。)

What do you think knowledge is? (By the way, introduce the scope of knowledge and knowledge sharing to unify the standards of the interview content and eliminate the narrow definition of knowledge commonly held by respondents.)

你觉得机上客舱团队的知识分享包括哪些方面? 有哪些方式?

What aspects do you think are included in knowledge sharing among the in-flight cabin crew? What are the methods?

在航班值勤过程中,你和同事们交流多吗? 尤其是业务相关的信息方面。

During flight duty, do you communicate frequently with your colleagues? Especially regarding business-related information.

什么情况下,你和同事在机上交流多一些?

Under what circumstances do you communicate more with your colleagues on board?

航前直接准备阶段,互动多吗?

Is there much interaction during the pre-flight direct preparation phase?

航前准备阶段的互动深度,对航班执行过程种的交流有帮助吗?

Does the depth of interaction during the pre-flight preparation phase help with communication during the flight execution process?

有没有一种直觉,让你觉得知识分享会更顺畅,更被接受? 这种感觉或直接有帮助吗?

Do you have an intuition that makes you feel knowledge sharing would be smoother and more accepted? Is this feeling or intuition directly helpful?

心情对航班值勤有影响吗? 对交流有影响吗?

Does your mood affect flight duty? Does it affect communication?

对不同的技术等级人员,交流上有顾忌吗?

Do you have any concerns about communicating with personnel of different technical ranks?

对知识分享,有什么担忧吗?

Do you have any concerns about knowledge sharing?

你为什么做知识分享? 知识分享会有成就感吗?

Why do you engage in knowledge sharing? Do you gain a sense of achievement from knowledge sharing?

目前在值勤过程中知识交流分享较少,原因是什么? 缺乏成长进步的动机还是认为所从事的专业不需要太多知识?

Currently, there is little knowledge exchange and sharing during duty. What are the reasons? Is it due to a lack of motivation for growth and progress, or the belief that your profession does not require much knowledge?

怎样才能有更多知识分享? 是要有科学的技术等级管理制度,还是激励机制? 或者开展知识技能大赛?

How can we encourage more knowledge sharing? Should there be a scientific technical rank management system or incentive mechanisms? Or should knowledge and skills competitions be organized?

Appendix B: Questionnaire Scale

Questionnaire 1

尊敬的参与者:

您好!欢迎您参与本次调查问卷,本问卷为中国社会科学院大学&斯特灵大学研究小组设计,旨在对客舱工作人员的员工感受调研以供学术研究。问卷分为多次,此次是第一次问卷填写。本问卷的所有问题不分对错,请您根据您的感受填写,同时我们也会对您的回答严格保密,所有的问卷仅供学术调查使用,请您放心回答。另附《参与者信息告知》《受访者同意书》《参与者招募指南》。

Dear Participant,

Hello! Thank you for participating in this survey. This questionnaire is designed by the research team from University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences and University of Stirling, aiming to investigate cabin crew members' employee perceptions for academic research purposes. The survey is conducted in multiple phases; this is the first round of questionnaire completion. There are no right or wrong answers to any questions in this questionnaire. Please answer based on your own feelings. We will strictly keep your responses confidential, and all data collected will be used solely for academic research. Please feel free to answer honestly. Attached are the "Participant Information Sheet," "Participant Consent Form," and "Participant Recruitment Guidance."

*成就追求

* Achievement Striving

1.请思考您在多大程度上同意以下关于您自己的描述。

1. Please consider the extent to which you agree with the following descriptions about yourself:

(1)我有明确的事业目标并不断努力去实现。

(1) I have clear career goals and strive continuously to achieve them.

(2)我觉得我有成功的动力。

(2) I feel motivated to succeed.

(3)我会尽我所能实现目标。

(3) I do my best to achieve my goals.

(4)我力争将每件事都做到最好。

(4) I strive to do everything to the best of my ability.

*责任感

* Sense of Responsibility

2.请思考您在多大程度上同意以下关于您自己的描述。

2. Please consider the extent to which you agree with the following descriptions about yourself:

(1)当我做出承诺时,我总会努力兑现。

(1) When I make a promise, I always strive to keep it.

(2)我努力认真地完成分配给我的所有任务。

(2) I strive to complete all tasks assigned to me carefully and conscientiously.

(3)我总是严格遵循自己的道德准则。

(3) I always strictly adhere to my own moral principles.

(4)我做事认真谨慎,完成工作基本不会返工。

(4) I work seriously and cautiously, and my completed work rarely requires rework.

*知识分享动机

* Knowledge Sharing Motivation

3.请思考您在多大程度上同意以下关于您自己的描述。

3. Please consider the extent to which you agree with the following descriptions about yourself:

(1)今后我要更多与团队成员分享工作信息、工作方法、工作手册等知识。

(1) In the future, I intend to share more work-related information, methods, manuals, and other knowledge with my team members.

(2)如果团队成员请求我,我会给他们指明方向,或为他们推荐我认识的人。

(2) If team members request my assistance, I will provide guidance or recommend people I know who can help them.

(3)我会更有效地与团队成员分享我通过教育或培训获得的专业知识以及工作经验。

(3) I will more effectively share with team members the professional expertise and work experience I have gained through education or training.

*组织公平氛围

* Organizational Justice Climate

4.请思考您在多大程度上同意以下描述。

4. Please consider to what extent you agree with the following statements:

(1)目前评价个人工作业绩的程序和规则非常公平。

(1) The current procedures and rules for evaluating individual job performance are very fair.

(2)周围同事的待遇符合他们的工作表现和业绩水平。

(2) Colleagues around me are treated in accordance with their job performance and achievement levels.

(3)同事间相处平等、和谐,不存在相互的歧视。

(3) Colleagues interact equally and harmoniously, without mutual discrimination.

*风险感知

* Risk Perception

5.请思考您在多大程度上同意以下关于您公司的描述。

5. Please consider to what extent you agree with the following descriptions of your company:

(1)分享知识会降低我的工作稳定性。

(1) Sharing knowledge will reduce my job stability.

(2)如果我自愿将我所有的知识分享给同事,我将失去在组织中的地位。

(2) If I voluntarily share all my knowledge with colleagues, I will lose my status in the organization.

(3)主动分享知识可能会降低我的晋升机会。

(3) Proactively sharing knowledge may reduce my chances of promotion.

Questionnaire 2

客舱工作人员的员工感受调查问卷

Cabin Crew Employee Perception Survey

尊敬的参与者:

您好!欢迎您参与本次调查问卷,本问卷为中国社会科学院大学&斯特灵大学研究小组设计,旨在对客舱工作人员的员工感受调研以供学术研究。问卷分为多次,此次是第二次(航后)问卷填写。本问卷的所有问题不分对错,请您根据您的感受填

写,同时我们也会对您的回答严格保密,所有的问卷仅供学术调查使用,请您放心回答。

Dear Participant,

Hello! Thank you for participating in this survey. This questionnaire is designed by the research team from University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences and University of Stirling, aiming to investigate cabin crew members' employee perceptions for academic research purposes. The questionnaire is divided into multiple parts; this is the second (post-flight) questionnaire. There are no right or wrong answers to any questions in this questionnaire. Please answer based on your own feelings. We will strictly keep your responses confidential, and all data collected will be used solely for academic research. Please feel free to answer honestly.

*1.您在客舱团队的角色是?

*1. What is your role in the cabin crew team?

乘务长 Chief flight attendant 乘务员 flight attendant 安全员 safety officer

以下是了解机组排班动态化与服务场景多样化、管理安全化的题目。员工在客舱工作团队的工作中,常进行航班信息、公司动态、运行政策、手册程序、工作技巧、案例分析等知识分享。但在这个过程中,也受到了成员紧密关系(如师徒、好友、合作次数等)影响,也受到技术等级差异、工作氛围、政策支持等影响。请您根据当日航班值勤情况如实填写。

The following questions aim to understand the dynamics of crew scheduling, the diversity of service scenarios, and safety management. In their work within the cabin crew team, employees often share knowledge such as flight information, company updates, operational policies, manual procedures, work techniques, and case analyses. However, this process is also influenced by close relationships among members (such as mentor-mentee relationships, friendships, frequency of collaboration, etc.), as well

as differences in technical ranks, work atmosphere, and policy support. Please fill it out truthfully based on your duty situation for the day's flight.

*2. 以下描述多大程度符合您在最近一次航班工作的体验?

*2. To what extent do the following descriptions match your experience in your most recent flight duty?

(1) 以后我会更频繁地与团队成员分享我的工作信息,工作方法,工作手册。

(1) In the future, I will share my work information, methods, and manuals with team members more frequently.

(2) 如果团队成员请求我,我会告诉他们工作的方向,为他们引荐我认识的人。

(2) If requested by team members, I will provide them with work direction and introduce them to people I know.

(3) 我会更有效地与团队成员分享我通过教育或培训获得的专业知识以及工作经验。

(3) I will more effectively share with team members the professional expertise and work experience I have gained through education or training.

*3. 以下描述多大程度符合您在最近一次航班工作的体验?

*3. To what extent do the following descriptions match your experience during your most recent flight duty?

(1) 在工作中,我主动向同事传授业务知识。

(1) At work, I proactively share business knowledge with my colleagues.

(2) 我把有用的工作经验和心得与大家共享。

(2) I share useful work experiences and insights with everyone.

(3) 在学到对工作有用的新知识后,我进行宣传,让更多的人学到它。

(3) After learning new knowledge that is useful for work, I promote it so that more people can learn it.

(4)只要团队其他同事需要,我总是知无不言,言无不尽。

(4) Whenever other colleagues in the team need assistance, I always share everything I know without reservation.

*4.您的手机号后六位(仅为方便匹配上一期数据,您的信息我们将严格保密):

*4. The last six digits of your mobile phone number (provided solely to facilitate matching with previous data; your information will be kept strictly confidential):

*5.您最近一次执行出港航班的日期(填写示例:如4月9日填写为0409,仅为方便匹配数据,您的信息我们将严格保密):

*5. The date of your most recent outbound flight duty (Example: For April 9th, enter 0409. Provided solely to facilitate data matching; your information will be kept strictly confidential):

*6.您最近一次执行出港航班的航班号(填写示例:GY7101,仅为方便匹配数据,您的信息我们将严格保密):

*6. The flight number of your most recent outbound flight duty (Example: GY7101. Provided solely to facilitate data matching; your information will be kept strictly confidential):

*7.您与最近一次执行客舱工作的团队成员有无师徒关系?

*7. Did you have a mentor-mentee relationship with any team members during your most recent cabin crew duty?

有 Yes 无 No

*8.您与最近一次执行客舱工作的团队成员有无好友关系?

*8. Did you have a friendship relationship with any team members during your most recent cabin crew duty?

有 Yes 无 No

Appendix C: Participant Recruitment Guidance

APR 5TH 2024, EDITION: 2

中国社会科学院大学
University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

UNIVERSITY of
STIRLING

Participant Recruitment Guidance 参与者招募指南

1. Research Project Title

Study on the Influence Mechanism of Employees' Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour in Temporary Teams: A Case Study of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd.

1. 研究课题名称

《临时团队中员工知识共享行为影响机制研究：以多彩贵州航空有限公司为例》

2. Invitation to Participate

Are you interested in taking part in this research? You will be invited to complete an interview and a questionnaire survey. All flight attendants and aviation security officers are welcome to participate, regardless of age, education background, position, technical grade and working seniority. We need a diverse group.

2. 诚邀您参与

您有兴趣参与研究吗？您将接受采访或问卷调查。只要您是客舱乘务人员或航空安全员,无论年龄、教育背景、职务、技术等级和服务年限如何,都欢迎您参与。我们需要一个多元化的群体。

3. Timeframe for recruitment

Recruitment for the study will begin in April 2025.

3. 招募时间

研究招募将在 2025 年 4 月开始。

4. Expenses/Payments

This study does not offer any compensation.

4. 费用/付款

本研究并不支付报酬。

5. Name of researchers/student their status and their Faculty.

I'm the researcher. My name is Ling Fu, a student of University of Stirling School of Management (and also a student of the School of International Education, University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences). My Email: lif2@stir.ac.uk

5. 研究者信息

研究者为付令,是中国社会科学院大学的学生,邮箱: fuling0209@yeah.net.

论文指导老师是高中华教授,她的邮箱是: gaozh@cas.org.cn。英方导师是

Linda Perriton 教授,邮箱是: linda.perriton@stir.ac.uk

The Chinese co-supervisor is Professor Zhonghua Gao, and her email: gaozh@cas.org.cn

The dissertation supervisor is Professor Linda Perriton, and her email: linda.perriton@stir.ac.uk

6. Who has reviewed this research project?

The ethical approaches of this project have been approved through General University Ethics Panel of the University of Stirling.

6. 谁审查了这个研究项目?

该课题的伦理方法已通过大学伦理委员会的批准。

7. How to take part?

If you would like to attend, please contact me. My email: ling.fu@stir.ac.uk, cell phone number: 86+18980021969.

7. 如何参与?

如果您想参加,请联系研究者。我的邮箱: fuling0209@yeah.net,手机号码: 86+18980021969。

Appendix D: Participant Information Sheet

Version date: MAY 2024

中国社会科学院大学
University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

UNIVERSITY of
STIRLING

Participant Information Sheet 参与者信息告知书

1. Research Project Title

Study on the Influence Mechanism of Employees' Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour in Temporary Teams: A Case Study of Colorful Guizhou Airlines Co., LTD

1. 研究课题名称

《临时团队中员工知识共享行为影响机制研究：以多彩贵州航空有限公司为例》

2. Background, aims of project

To a large extent, the competitiveness of an organisation depends on its knowledge management ability, including acquisition, absorption, sharing, utilization and transformation of knowledge. Knowledge sharing within enterprises is an important basis and link to carry out the production and operation. This study aims to explore the mechanisms and influencing factors of knowledge sharing among members in temporary teams. I would like to invite you to participate in our research interviews and questionnaires.

2. 背景及项目目标

在很大程度上,组织的竞争力取决于其知识管理能力,包括获取、吸收、分享、利用和转化等。企业内部的知识共享是开展生产和运营的重要基础和环节。本研究旨在解释临时团队成员分享知识的原理和影响因素。在此,诚挚地邀请您参加这项研究的访谈/问卷调查。

3. Why have I been invited to take part?

You have been invited because you fit the criteria for this study. You may come from my personal network of contacts established in the company, or from a recommendation from other participants.

My research depends on recruiting a diverse group of research participants. As long as you are a flight attendant or an aviation security officer, regardless of age, education background, job title, skill level and working seniority, you are a potential participant.

3. 您为什么被邀请参与?

您被邀请是因为您符合本研究的标准。您可能来自研究者在企业建立的联系人网络,或来自其他参与者的推荐。此项研究依赖于招募多样化的研究参与者。只要您是客舱乘务员或航空安全员,无论年龄、教育背景、职位、技能水平和服务年限,都是潜在的参与者。

4. Do I have to take part?

No. You do not have to take part.

If you do decide to take part, you can withdraw your participation at any time without needing to explain and without penalty by advising me of this decision.

If you withdraw, I will not collect any more data from you. However, any data collected up until the point that you withdraw will be kept and used in the data analysis.

You will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form.

4. 必须参与吗?

不。非强制参与。

如果您决定参与,您可以在任何时候撤回您的参与,无需解释且不受惩罚,只需告知研究者这一决定。

如果您撤回,研究者将不再从您这里收集任何数据。然而,在您撤回之前收集的任何数据将被保留并用于数据分析。

您将收到这份信息并被要求签署一份同意书。

5. What will happen if I take part?

You will need to complete the questionnaire and interview.

The interview and questionnaire will be conducted in a place where you feel comfortable, such as a café, at approximately one hour. And the date and time will be scheduled accordingly.

In general, there is no follow-up visit unless the key information is missing.

5. 如果参与,会发生什么?

您需要完成访谈或问卷。

面试和问卷将在您感到舒适的地方进行,例如咖啡馆,时间大约为 1 小时。具体时间将作相应安排。

除非缺少关键信息,一般情况下不会进行后续的补充访问。

6. Are there any potential risks in taking part?

There are no foreseeable risks in taking part.

Issue of privacy: You may be apprehensive about the potential violation of your privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity. To address these concerns, I will ensure compliance with GDPR guidelines – which the University of Stirling is subject to - to protect your privacy. Privacy will be ensured through signed the consent form for everyone, and the data provided will be used exclusively for research purposes. I also will be taking additional measures for participant privacy, e.g. the snowball sample, where participants are asked to share my contact information via the participant information sheet with colleagues who are interested in participating. To ensure the privacy of the research participants in a study conducted in the company, several measures will be taken:

The information sheet will be shared with potential participants through participating colleagues. If a colleague is interested in the research, they will directly contact me. In the event where the participating participants ask me about their colleagues'

participation, I will not disclose this information. This step ensures that no one knows who else has participated in the study, guaranteeing privacy for all involved.

The questionnaire questions have been designed to avoid collecting unnecessary personal information, such as your name, private hobbies, marital status, etc., or any other identifiable information that could directly identify you, such as unique job roles.

6. 参与是否存在潜在风险?

参与没有可预见的风险。

关于隐私：您可能会对可能隐私受侵犯、机密性和匿名性感到担忧。为了解决这些问题,研究者将确保遵循 GDPR 指南、受访者签字同意、承诺所提供的数据将仅用于研究目的,来保护您的隐私。

研究者还将采取额外措施来保护参与者的隐私,例如雪球取样,这是指要求参与者通过参与者信息表将研究者的联系信息分享给有意参与的同事。为确保在公司进行研究的参与者的隐私,还将采取几项措施:

信息表将通过面谈的同事与潜在参与者共享。如果有同事对此研究感兴趣,他或她可以直接与研究者的联系。如果被访者询问研究者有关他们同事参与的情况,研究者将不会透露。上述措施将进一步确保没有人知道谁参与了研究,从而保证所有参与者的隐私。

问卷问题的设计旨在避免收集不必要的私人信息,比如您的姓名、私人爱好、婚姻状况等,或者任何其他可以直接识别您的身份的信息,例如独特的职位角色。

7. Are there any benefits in taking part?

You do not gain benefit directly from participating in this study.

7. 参与有什么好处吗?

您并不会直接从参与这项研究中获益。

8. ESSENTIAL IF COLLECTING PERSONAL INFORMATION: Legal basis for processing personal data

As part of the project, I will be recording and processing personal data relating to you. This will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Under GDPR the legal basis for processing your personal data will be public interest/ official authority of the University.

These are the most likely legal justifications under GDPR but if in doubt these should be checked with the Data Protection team at data.protection@stir.ac.uk. Note that the legal justification under GDPR should not be consent.

8. 处理个人数据的法律依据

作为项目的一部分,研究者将记录与您有关的个人数据。这些数据将根据《一般数据保护条例》(GDPR)进行处理。根据 GDPR,处理您的个人数据的法律依据将是公共利益/大学的官方权威。

这些是根据 GDPR 最有可能的法律依据,但如果有疑问,应与数据保护团队联系。请注意,根据 GDPR 的法律依据不应为同意。

9. What happens to the data I provide?

I am carrying out this study as part of my personal studies towards the completion of my degree. As part of the project, I will be collecting and storing data relating to you. The research data you provide e.g. questionnaire responses, interview responses, your job role and length of service, will be kept anonymous by using a code and not your name. All data will be stored using that code. Any quotes used from the data you provide will not be able to identify you, either by the removal of likely identifying elements or by the use of anonymization, e.g. Respondent A.

I will have access to research data (but will have signed a confidentiality agreement – for assistance with confidentiality agreements please contact the University Contracts Team at contracts@stir.ac.uk). If personal details are being shared with third parties their details MUST be included.

Your personal data will be transferred to a country outside the EU; the following safeguards are in place to ensure your personal data is protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The data you provide will be kept for 1 year on my password-protected notebook laptop, which access is only known by me, and then will be securely destroyed permanently.

9. 您提供的数据会发生什么？

进行这项研究是作为研究者个人学业的一部分,以完成学位。作为项目的一部分,将收集和存储与您相关的数据。

您提供的研究数据,例如问卷回复、访谈回复、您的职位和服务年限,将通过使用代码而不使用您的姓名来保持匿名。所有数据将使用该代码进行存储。您提供的任何引用都无法识别您,要么通过去除可能识别的元素,要么通过使用匿名方式,例如: 受访者 A。

研究者将可以访问研究数据(但会签署保密协议——有关保密协议的协助,请联系合同团队 contracts@stir.ac.uk)。如果个人详细信息与第三方共享,必须包含他们的详细信息。

您的个人数据将被转移到欧盟以外的国家,以下保障措施确保您的个人数据根据《通用数据保护条例》(GDPR)受到保护。

您提供的数据将在研究者的笔记本上保留 1 年,密码仅研究者自己知晓,然后将被安全销毁。

10. Recorded media

I will obtain your prior consent before recording. The data you provide will be destroyed after analysis and will not be used for other purposes. The recordings will not form part of a publication or be deposited in any public archive.

10. 录音媒体

在记录之前,研究者会获得您的同意。您提供的数据将在分析后被销毁,不会用于其他目的。录音不会成为出版物的一部分,也不会存入档案。

11. Will the research be published?

The University of Stirling is committed to making the outputs of research publicly accessible and supports this commitment through our online open access repository STORRE. Unless restricted by funder/publisher requirements prevent us this research will be publicly disseminated through our open access repository.

11. 这项研究会被发表吗?

大学致力于使研究成果对公众开放,并通过在线开放获取存储库支持这一承诺。除非资助方/出版方要求阻止,否则这项研究将通过开放获取存储库公开传播。

12. Who is organising and funding the research?

Nobody is sponsoring or funding this research externally.

12. 谁在组织和资助这项研究?

没有人赞助或资助这项研究。

13. Who has reviewed this research project?

The research ethical protocol of this project has been approved by The University of Stirling General University Ethics Panel.

13. 谁审查了这个研究项目?

该项目的伦理方法已通过大学通用大学伦理委员会的批准。

14. ESSENTIAL IF COLLECTING PERSONAL INFORMATION: Your rights

You have the right to request a copy of the information I hold about you and to request corrections or deletions of the information that is no longer required.

You have the right to withdraw from this project at any time without giving reasons and without any adverse consequences to you.

You also have the right to object to me processing relevant personal data. However, please note that once the data are being analysed and/or results have been published it may not be possible to remove your data from the study.

14. 您的权利

您有权要求查看研究者持有的关于您的信息副本,并请求更正或删除不再需要的信息。

您有权在任何时候退出此项目,无需给出理由,也不会对您产生后果。

您还有权反对研究者处理相关的个人数据,但是请注意,一旦数据被分析和/或结果被发布,可能无法将您的数据从研究中删除。

15. Who do I contact if I have concerns about this study or I wish to complain?

If you would like to discuss the research with someone, please contact me. My email: ling.fu@stir.ac.uk

Or my dissertation supervisor: linda.perriton@stir.ac.uk

You have the right to lodge a complaint against the University regarding data protection issues with the Information Commissioner's Office (<https://ico.org.uk/concerns/>).

The University's Data Protection Officer is Joanna Morrow, Deputy Secretary. If you have any questions relating to data protection these can be addressed to data.protection@stir.ac.uk in the first instance.

You will be given a copy of this information sheet to keep for your own record.

Thank you for your participation.

15. 如果您对这项研究有疑虑或想投诉,我该联系谁?

如果您想讨论研究,请与研究者联系,邮箱: fuling0209@yeah.net。

或者联系论文导师: gaozh@cas.org.cn 或 linda.perriton@stir.ac.uk

您有权就数据保护相关问题,向英国信息专员办公室对本校提起投诉:

(<https://ico.org.uk/concerns/>)。本校数据保护官为副秘书长乔安娜·莫罗 (Joanna Morrow) 如您有任何与数据保护相关的疑问, 可优先发邮件咨询:

data.protection@stir.ac.uk。

您将获得一份此信息表的副本以留存。

感谢您的参与。

Appendix E: Participant Consent Form

MAY 25th 2024, Edition :3

中国社会科学院大学
University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

UNIVERSITY of
STIRLING

Participant Consent Form 参与者同意书

Ethics Approval Number [GUEP 2024 15531 14212] Participant number []

伦理批准号[GUEP 2024 15531 14212] 参与者编号[]

Research Project Title: Study on the Influence Mechanism of Employees'

Knowledge-Sharing Behaviour in Temporary Teams: A Case Study of Colorful

Guizhou Airlines Co., Ltd.

研究课题名称: 《临时团队中员工知识共享行为影响机制研究：以多彩贵州航空有限公司为例》

Please tick each box. 请画勾于框内。	
I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet explaining the above research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project. 我确认我已阅读并理解解释上述研究项目的信息表,并且我有机会提出有关该项目的问题。	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time during the study without needing to explain and without penalty by advising the researcher of this decision. 我理解我的参与是自愿的,在研究过程中我可以随时自由撤回而无需解释,并且不会受到惩罚,只需告知研究人员我的决定。	
If I withdraw, researcher will not collect any more data from me. However, any data collected up until the point that I withdraw will be kept and used	

<p>in the data analysis. 如果我撤回,研究人员将不再收集我的任何数据。然而,在我撤回之前收集的任何数据将被保留并用于数据分析。</p>	
<p>I have been given a unique identifying number and know whom to contact should I wish to withdraw my data. 我已获得一个唯一的身份号码,并知道如果我希望撤回我的数据时应联系谁。</p>	
<p>I understand that my responses will be kept anonymous and I give permission for the researcher to have access to my anonymous responses. 我理解我的回应将被保密,我允许研究人员访问我的匿名回应。</p>	
<p>I consent to being audio recorded. The relevant data will be destroyed after collection and will not be used for other purposes. The recordings will not form part of a publication or be deposited in an archive. 我同意进行音频录制。相关数据将在收集后被销毁,不会用于其他目的。录音不会成为出版物的一部分,也不会存入档案。</p>	
<p>I agree for research data collected in the study to be given to the researcher, including those working outside the EU to be used in other research studies. I understand that any data that leave the researcher will be fully anonymized so that I cannot be identified. 我同意将研究中收集的研究数据提供给研究者。我理解任何离开研究者的数据都将被完全匿名化,以便我无法被识别。</p>	
<p>I understand how audio will be used in research outputs. I am aware that I will not be named in any research outputs. 我明白音频将如何在研究成果中使用。我知道我不会在任何研究成果中被提及。</p>	
<p>I agree for my personal data to be kept in a secure database which is located on the researcher's laptop with a password, so I can be contacted about future studies. 我同意将我的个人数据保存在一个安全的数据库中,该数据库位于研究者的笔记本电脑上并有密码,以便我可以被联系开展进一步的研究。</p>	
<p>I agree to take part in this study. 我同意参与这项研究。</p>	

Name of Participant 参与者

Signature (签名):

Date 日期: [Click here to enter a date](#)

Name of Researcher 研究者

Signature (签名):

Date 日期: [Click here to enter a date](#)